

**EVALUATION OF THE CURRENT PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT
SYSTEM IN THE ORTHOPAEDIC DEPARTMENTS OF THE
HOSPITALS OF SIALKOT DISTRICT, PAKISTAN**

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DECLARATION

I, Amer Iqbal, declare that this Dissertation represents my own work except where referenced to others and that it does not include work forming part of a Dissertation presented successfully for another degree.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to loving memories of my Father, Muhammad Iqbal and Mother who were very supportive and proud of me committing to this research project and who, unfortunately, could not live to see its completion.

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ABSTRACT

In the present competitive environment, all organisations are striving to improve their performance through the most appropriate strategies for obtaining the business advantages. There was a time when only private organisations were concerned about the performance management (PM) but now the scenario has changed and public healthcare systems are also highly emphasizing the PM because of diversity of challenges, public demand, and shrinking resources. Despite the real need and importance of performance management in this sector, it has been observed that a little attention of researchers in terms of analysis of performance management has been paid. The past studies were mostly conducted in the developed countries whereas the developing countries have not been given due importance in the context of performance management System (PMS). To address this research gap, the present study is conducted on the health care sector of Pakistan.

The major aim of this research is to examine the performance management system of the health care sector of Pakistan. The specific objectives planned for this research are; To review the existing performance management system, identify the factors contributing to it, and the challenges faced. The results and recommendations will contribute to help and support the stakeholders of the healthcare sector (Government, planners, managers, and project implementers), guiding the employees and practitioners, and strengthening the existing knowledge of the subject. The study approach is qualitative research methods (Creswell, 2005) involving four selected hospitals of Sialkot district. The structured interviews using open-ended questions (Blumberg, Cooper, and Schindler, 2014; Bernard, 2017) with 25 participants (purposive sampling; Bryman and Bell, 2015) were organized in orthopaedic department of selected hospitals. It was ensured that all categories of employees get representation and a fair male and female ratio (60:40) is maintained. The collected data has been analysed using thematic analysis technique (Marczyk, DeMatteo, and Festinger, 2005; Zikmund et al., 2013). These investigations have evaluated the system of performance management from the managerial and as well as employee perspective with a focus on performance assessment, training, employee commitment, organisational structure, and information technology. The challenges and deficiencies of the current performance management systems in hospitals have also been identified.

The data and information of the research indicated that the health care sector of Pakistan has implemented a formal performance management system in all the studied hospitals with minor variations in assessment parameters and duration. The participants of the study were not very happy with the current PMS and its development level but still they are of the view that it is helping a lot and better than the conventional system employed before 1990. They agreed that performance assessment became better but there are certain weaknesses like biases, lack of training, overloading of work, centralized organisation structure, less effective communication, using a mix of paperwork and computer, likeness/unlikeness, and taking less care of guidelines and feedback while use of IT is still at the initial stage. The employees' commitment has been acknowledged by the managers who are having complaints of lesser staff and poor resources. All the participants agreed that there is still a lot of room for improvement and there is need for a digitised-IT-based modern PMS. The recommendations for all the stakeholders have been formulated and future needs of research on the subject have been highlighted. The recommendations based on the opinions of participants are: The assessment and feedback system should be unbiased, the training system needs strengthening, the appreciation, awards, and rewards systems need enhancement, and the hospitals are facing shortage of resources, especially human resources. These are serious recommendations for the management to consider. On the other hand, employees need to refine their behaviour and performance by achieving assigned work, improving attendance, serving the patients better and showing engagement and commitment to their hospitals. The hospitals need increase in financial, human, and technical resources (Machinery and equipment), and finally the current PMS should be replaced with a modern IT-internet based PMS. The government may take a note of this suggestion. The results of the study have strengthened the knowledge base of the subject from this area. It is also required that future researchers should undertake their studies selecting hospitals from all the four provinces and the Federal capital Islamabad. They should also compare PMS of private and public sector hospitals for making a comparison. For more details, the appropriate sections (6.4.1 to 6.4.4) can be consulted.

Chapter One

Introduction

The current chapter covers the background of the research on performance management system, based on which the importance of PMS is emphasized and the need for its further investigation is drawn. In this chapter, the aim and objectives of the current study are clearly stated along with the problem statement. Furthermore, the significance and rationale of this research are emphasized in this chapter. At the end of this chapter, a structure of the dissertation is provided in which the overall design of the study is elaborated.

1.1 The Performance Management System (PMS)

A good performance by the government or private organisations is always desirable, but an outstanding performance is only possible by skilled and talented workers. The managers can ensure an excellent performance if they use available manpower of the company to acquire the assigned targets and objectives (Miller and Bellinger, 2014; Tyagi et al., 2016). All the actions and practices of managers and management teams are collectively called Performance Management. According to Van Tuijl (2007), Performance Management includes all activities of organisations which are aiming at an efficacious use of personnel of a firm. Van Dooren, Bouckaert, and Halligan (2015) reported that for managing skilled and unskilled labour effectually and providing efficient services to communities, the Performance Management System (PMS) is highly vital which can help to boost the achievements of a business firm. Of course, the PMS may prove as a significant driver for increasing achievement of assignments by the employees. Buckingham and Goodall (2015) have asserted that the institutions adopting effectively designed performance management systems can successfully compete with other organisations, rather they might outperform others due to very high performance obtained by appropriate utilization of human resources.

The health sector, especially hospitals, demands very high performance of services with passion, ethical and human welfare considerations. For achieving these objectives, the role of the Performance Management System (PMS) has been emphasized greatly by various researchers and writers. For instance, the importance of performance management system has been highly emphasized because of numerous challenges of the health care sector (Nazir et al., 2016). A good management entity and assessing performance of employees usefully, can help

to improve the achievements of organisations for attaining goals and ambitions (Rankin et al., 2016) because an appropriate, harmonious and cordial link is established between line manager and individual employee which helps a lot in effective communication (Babu et al., 2018). The performance management system has been in use to manage and evaluate employees' activities and achievements since decades, but with time, working environment, needs of patients, increasing demands for efficiencies and demographics of workforce, it has been changed extensively. These days, patients do not demand traditional services, but they want the use of advanced technology ensuring efficient and excellent services and procedures with probabilities of minimal harmful impacts (Arnaboldi, Lapsley and Steccolini, 2015; Shabbir, Malik, and Malik, 2016). The patients coming to hospitals are asking for immediate care and treatment. However, this is only possible through an effective and modernized PMS. The outcomes of modern era have forced organisations to improve the old performance management system into an innovative and digital procedures for managing and appraising performance of employees and organisations (Rashidi, 2015).

The improvement of performance management in healthcare organisations are not limited now to private sector only (Shaikh, 2015) but need to extend in the government sector as well. It needs smarter choices of management and hard work because ineffective performance management has emerged as a constraint that plagues the performance of different healthcare organisations (Cardy and Leonard, 2014). According to Cascio (2018), for dealing with these challenges, modern PMS can prove as a strong mechanism of workforce management in the current dynamic and competitive environment. In this situation, many business and service providing firms are restructuring their PMS for ensuring that their managing and monitoring processes become more meaningful and capable of achieving the objectives assigned (Dusterhoff, Cunningham and MacGregor, 2014).

1.1.1 The Needs to Improve Performance Management System (PMS)

Many authors have provided reasons for changing the traditional performance management systems with contemporary performance management systems. Van Dooren, Bouckaert, and Halligan (2015) explained that if changes required to improve performance management are identified and implemented in actual practice, the accomplishments rate of healthcare system of an organisation can go very high because according to Arnaboldi, Lapsley, and Steccolini (2015), the modern contemporary performance systems can be used to engage employees in work and job. Ahmed et al. (2016) highlighted that innovative performance management

models have become necessary for improving services and providing talent solutions to needy. The human resources are mostly limited with service providing organisations while PMS helps to do more with fewer resources by utilizing time and expertise of individuals more efficiently. The employees are assigned individual assignments and their achievements or failures are visible to them as well as the management. Thus, the new system is self-assessing and performance of individuals cannot remain confidential. The employees with low performance can be held responsible immediately.

Mir and Pinnington (2014) and Cascio (2018) have regarded performance management as a critical tool which can translate the organisational strategy into results and outcomes. An effectively designed performance management system can achieve all relevant organisational performance measures: productivity, quality, and satisfaction of employees and customers (Melnyk et al., 2014). The performance management helps to link people to service providers, as well as interrelates with different sub-functions of human resources development including planning, learning, training and imparting professional skills, career upscaling, and developing an integrated human resource management platform in the organisations (Arnaboldi, Lapsley and Steccolini, 2015). The performance management system can identify standards and parameters for assessment of the performance of workers' contributions and productivity as well as making aware of the requirement and activities of an organisation (Chapman, 2018). The development opportunities and ample learning emerge through participation of employees in different programs of leadership development. Evaluation through Performance Management supports distributing incentives and performance rewards on equated and fair basis as well as rewarding and recognizing good performance and providing more opportunities for career development.

1.1.2 Advantages of Performance Management System (PMS)

PMS can bring many benefits to organisations, employees, and managers in different ways (Devarajan, Maheshwari, and Vohra, 2016). The organisational benefits include cost benefits, clear accountability, overcoming communication barriers, improved productivity, employees' loyalty, and retention and consequently improved organisational performance. The cost benefits can be obtained by extracting more work from limited human resources due to increased efficiency of individuals and decreasing wastage of time because each one knows what he should do. He is also aware that in case of failure of achieving assigned work, the PMS will hold him responsible and accountable. Costello et al. (2015) and Ziguras (2016) have

explained that an effective performance management system works for evaluating employees, providing feedback, counseling, coaching, motivating and developing links between staff and managers. The innovative PMS eases the communication and the outcomes are increased. This system supports rapid communication, performance-dependent awards and promotions, transfers, and fair and impartial terminations (House et al., 2018). The better overall performance encourages the organisation to award and reward the employees which increases satisfaction of employees from their firm and they prefer to stay and serve for longer periods, thus increasing their loyalty and retention. According to Theriou (2015), the evaluation of performance may pivot job satisfaction and employees' loyalty due to transparent and open feedback and helps in developing an association between compensation and performance.

Van Dooren, Bouckaert, and Halligan (2015) narrated the managerial benefits which are decreased conflicts, time-saving, and consistency and efficiency in performance. When all employees and each stakeholder is very clear of his responsibilities and accountability on non-performance, the conflicts and wastage of time are curtailed significantly and contribute to consistency and efficiency in performance. With respect to employees, the system highlights employees' expectations, opportunities of self-assessment, accountabilities, enhanced performance and promotions, job satisfaction, and indication of career path (Parmenter, 2015). The modern PMS helps to identify the competencies and skill gaps of employees and individuals deserving training, awards and rewards. Therefore, the system helps to develop the training plans for employees on regular basis (Bergeron, 2017; Berger and Enflo, 2017).

The PMS permits managers to do comparison and evaluation of employees, without any bias, in different ways that are seen relevant to overall objectives of an organisation (Ahmed et al., 2016; Newton et al., 2014). Nepotism, as well as favouritism, could not thrive if managers do an evaluation of performance in terms of objectives and some defined standards. Concisely, the advantages of program of performance management touch every individual of an organisation and greatly reduce the paperwork (Parmenter, 2015).

A detailed discussion, information, and data of the health care structure of Pakistan and the study area have been presented in Chapter 2 of this manuscript.

1.2 Gaps identified in the past research and Need of the Current Study

The plenty of research work completed in the past associated with the PMS and its related constructs. A critical analysis indicated that most of the research work has been completed in

the developed countries of the West which does not indicate the true picture of developing countries of Asia and Africa (Wilden et al., 2013; Poister, Pasha, and Edwards, 2013; Rothwell, Hohne, and King, 2018). There are a few studies which have been accomplished in developing countries, thus highlighting emerging needs of research in the Eastern ambience as well (Arnaboldi, Lapsley, and Steccolini, 2015). So, there exist a significant contextual gap which has also been highlighted by authors like O'Toole Jr and Meier (2014), Podgórski (2015), and Ohemeng et al. (2018) as well. Further to this, Hoque (2014) has also highlighted the methodological gap indicating that the majority of the past studies were relevant to PMS and have been conducted using the quantitative methods. Under this scenario, authors like Devarajan, Maheshwari, and Vohra (2016) and Alves, Vieira, and Ribeiro (2017) have identified that new investigation should use qualitative approaches or combinations of methodologies for getting in-depth insight of the research issues.

An urgent need of reformation, rectification, and up-gradation of performance management is rising in developing countries like Pakistan where a conventional system is still in operation in many of the healthcare institutions (Harris, Cortvriend, and Hyde, 2007; Hassan, Mahmood, and Bukhsh, 2017). Although meagre research work has been carried out to understand and evaluate actual status and efficiency of the currently available performance management system, one study, by Arshad, Noordin, and Othman (2017), was highly useful. This evaluative research regarded the performance management system of Pakistan as ineffective due to weaknesses like shortage of competent staff, limited training of staff, lesser commitment of executives, poor generation of appropriate reports and health information and subsequent communication, poor electronic and online services for customers and patients, mistakes during collection of data, weak and less transparent system of accountability, motivation, awarding, and rewarding of employees, and the high costs of information technology adaptation and implementation. The study, however, was conducted involving famous hospitals of the capital city, Islamabad. No such investigation has been conducted in the healthcare system of the Punjab province. Therefore, the present research aimed at investigating performance management system of this area using the data from Hospitals of Sialkot District, Punjab, Pakistan. Different conceptual details such as performance management, organisational structure, information technology, human resources, training, award and reward system, evaluation of performance, conveying the feedback and assessment of required improvement are part of this research. Chapter 2 provides more details of this subject. (The Healthcare and Performance Management System of Pakistan).

1.3 Problem statement and the Research Question:

The performance management system holds a critical place in the strategy of every organisation. Without having a proper formal performance management system, organisations face several difficulties in managing working activities, performing duties and subsequent achievements of employees in a consistent, reliable and justifiable manner. Therefore, it is an imperative need of every organisation to have an appropriate system for managing the professional activities of employees and evaluating their performance in a justifiable manner (Van Dooren, Bouckaert, and Halligan, 2015). The health care sector is highly critical for every community of a country (Chandra et al., 2016). In Pakistan, many hospitals are not matching the required standards and satisfactory performance of their employees, including doctors, nurses, and staff. Due to poor management and administration, issues like ineffective treatment, low attendance, poor patient services, and inappropriate performance of hospital duties are commonly observed. This indicates that the health care sector, especially hospitals need improving their performance (Chowdhary et al., 2014). A modern IT-based online PMS can only handle the prevalent situation. Therefore, a real problem lies in the performance management of hospitals in this country. The present conditions of the hospitals of Pakistan direly need evaluation and identification of challenges and deficiencies, which must be communicated to the stakeholders of health care sector for addressing. This study was planned and conducted to understand and highlight significant problems in the real scenario for helping communities and patients.

Hence, a problem statement for the present research study is:

“Reviewing the Performance Management System (PMS) of selected hospitals of Pakistan including identification of factors contributing to performance and the possible improvement”

The research question evaluated by the current research study are as under:

Q1: Which Performance Management Systems (PMS) have been implemented in various hospitals in the study area and how efficient the current systems are in assessing employees’ performance?

Q2: What significant factors are affecting the Current Performance Management Systems (CPMS)?

Q3: Do the management and practitioners feel the need for a modern PMS or not for the improvement of performance and service quality of hospitals?

1.4 Aim and Research Objectives of the Study:

These investigations aimed at exploring and evaluating the currently employed PMS in the selected hospitals, and finally to provide evidence-based recommendations to policymakers and other stakeholders for innovating the system more effective and advantageous. The major target of the study is the assessment of performance management of employees (individuals and teams), their needs and problems, and improvement possibilities, but the performance of organisations as whole have also been studied through the selected participants from the studied hospitals.

The objectives investigated in the current research project are as under:

- i) To review the existing performance management system in selected hospitals of Pakistan.
- ii) To identify factors that are contributing to performance management in the Pakistani hospitals.
- iii) To coincide the results of the study considering currently available theoretical and practice-based literatures and finding a match in between both.
- iv) To formulate recommendations for different stakeholders (government, planners and policy makers, management, practitioners, and the employees).
- v) To strengthen the knowledge base and the literature of the subject of current study.

1.5 Significance of the study

Now, the demand for excellent services by hospitals is constantly increasing from customers and patients. Therefore, hospital managers should come up with the effective solutions of emerging problems, for which there exist a skill gap and talent crunch (Arnaboldi, Lapsley, and Steccolini, 2015). Managers should find out the solution to engage employees, increase their motivation and enhance their performance. The health care organisations and hospitals must have proper systems for managing, organizing, and assigning jobs to employees for attaining a good performance (Tasneem et al., 2018). The higher management is being remarkably emphasised for monitoring the performance through achievement of goals and objectives and the consequent productivity (DeNisi and Smith, 2014). Appraising and managing performance at individual, group and organisational level can only be achieved with effective performance management systems that may also meet conditions of a specific

situation. If the system does not fulfill all such requirements, it needs significant improvement (Van Dooren, Bouckaert, and Halligan, 2015).

Technologies are rapidly changing in all fields of life and digital techniques are dominating everywhere and replacing traditional olden methodologies. The healthcare sector has also been deeply affected and consequently changed into modern innovations and digital-dominated machinery, equipment, and management. The present hospitals are totally different than those existing fifty years ago. The expectations of all the stakeholders of hospitals like national and health authorities, patients, communities, managers and high management, employees, and evaluators have increased manifold presently. Health systems and hospitals should make improvement in strategies of performance management for becoming more successful. Many recent changes in rules and regulations of hospitals demand high-quality metrics, significant performance and more responsibility of employees than before and now leaders of healthcare are expected to provide some meaningful results (Glavas, 2016).

The organisations are facing real challenges in designing and implementation of an appropriate PMS which can manage and monitor performance in an intuitive, continuous, real-time and consistent manner. In this situation, it is the organisational structure, information technology and human resource management (employee commitment and training) which act as the levers for contributing a major part in designing and implementation of PMS (Certo, 2015). Therefore, this research focused on these three pillars of the performance management system and analysed how organisational achievements might be improved with the implementation of performance management system. The present study intended to evaluate and recommend changes to the PMS of Orthopaedic and other Departments of the hospitals of Sialkot District, Pakistan. In this research, performance management has been outlined, assessed, evaluated and recommendations are provided for further improvement.

In doing so, the hopes of hospital employees like growth, feedback, development and skill enhancement also required to be addressed. All these challenges can be coped through an effective PMS (Alves, Vieira, and Ribeiro, 2017). Hence, for this purpose, exploration of training and development needs, awards, rewards, and promotions have also been studied. This research has focused on how organisational structure, information technology, employees' commitment, and training (as basic measures) impact on hospital performance as well as their relationship with performance management system. The data and information yielded in the study will be highly useful for the stakeholders of health care services of the research area.

Other hospitals and practitioners can also benefit from this research on performance management system of the country. Therefore, practitioners can get valuable insight for improving the performance management system of their hospitals. The policymakers can also get key points from this study for developing a better performance management system for health care sector of Pakistan.

1.6 The Organisation and Structure of the dissertation

This manuscript comprises of seven main chapters which are Introduction, Literature Review, An Overview of Pakistan Healthcare system, Research Methodology, Findings, and Analysis – Part A, Findings and Analysis – Part B, and Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations. Each chapter has its own specific purpose and content so that the overall aim and major objectives of this study might be elaborated and fulfilled through findings.

Chapter one: Introduction.

The context of presented research has been set in this chapter where relevant and important background information is provided. The chapter provides the need to conduct this study. The rationale and importance of present research are being discussed, illuminating both academic and practical significance. Furthermore, aim, and objectives are constructed which has provided the foundation to current research.

Chapter two: Nature, Structure, and status of the Performance Management System in Health Care Sector of Pakistan

This chapter encompasses the nature, structure, and organisation of the health care sector of Pakistan. The status of the performance in public sector hospitals has been presented, the deficiencies and challenges have been identified as well, and the need for improvement elaborated. The relevant data and information have been provided.

Chapter Three: Literature Review

This chapter has reviewed the relevant literature for providing the theoretical underpinnings to present research study. Those research studies and theories are reviewed which were directly related to the research objectives of this study or could explain relevant aspects. Mainly, theories of designing, implementing and evaluating performance management systems are discussed. The pertinent past studies from Pakistan and abroad have been reviewed and presented.

Chapter four: Research Methodology

Chapter 4 encompassed the research methods selected for these investigations with support from the literature. A detailed rationale for selecting one method over the other method has been presented avoiding mere explanations of selected method. Why this study has adopted the qualitative research methods using open-ended interview strategy, has been explained. So, this chapter has provided all details about selecting methods of sampling studying population, data collection and processing. Ethical facets have also been explained.

Chapter five: Findings and Analysis – Part A

The qualitative conclusions from the interviews with employees of hospitals of Sialkot have been presented here. The collected data have been analysed using the thematic analysis techniques, and the themes found from literature and newly collected data are presented. These themes are designed to align with the research aim and objectives of the study. The chapter examined the PMS implemented in hospitals of Sialkot, Pakistan. It also provides the analysis of how training and development and organisational structure are influencing the performance of hospitals of the country.

Chapter five: Findings and Analysis – Part B

The findings of the thematic analysis of the interviews are included in this chapter. The chapter also provides the analysis that how employees' commitment and information technology influence the performance of hospitals.

Chapter six: Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

This chapter summarises the findings of the study and conclusion drawn thereafter. The findings of the study also highlight how each objective is accomplished. Moreover, the limitations of this research have been presented in this chapter, with a discussion on the horizons of future research by the new researchers entering this field. Recommendations have also been formulated for communicating to various stakeholders of health care services.

1.7 The Summary of Chapter one

The present chapter is introducing what the PMS is and why it should be implemented in hospitals. The aims and objectives of the study have been elaborated, the need to adopt PMS has been highlighted along with the expected benefits of the strategy. The significance of the

investigations, identification of the existing problem in hospitals of Sialkot District of Pakistan, Problem Statement, and the Research Question of the study have been highlighted. The significance of the study and structure of the present manuscript have been presented at the end of the chapter.

Chapter Two

The Healthcare and Performance Management System of Pakistan

Healthcare systems of the world have been modified, developed and modernized a lot during the last few decades, especially after the introduction of the computer, digitized devices, and the internet. A large disparity is visible now between healthcare systems of the developed countries and that of developing countries like Pakistan. These differences can be noticed in all components and sub-systems of healthcare services. Pakistan is far behind in healthcare machinery, equipment, human resources, and PMS. Even the evaluation of the performance of employees is not matching the systems in the advanced world where these have been totally digitized and automatized and based on online services. An analysis indicated that healthcare system of Pakistan and associated health policies are not very strong (Kurji, Premani, and Mithani, 2016). The Development Goals, planning, and implementation of improving and upscaling programs, strengthening of Public and Private sectors Partnership, refining human resources, developing infrastructure, and modernizing systems of services delivery and performance management. The numerous weaknesses like weak administration, limited resources coupled with unequal chances of access by needy people, Information Management System of lower standards, poor accountability and monitoring, non-consistent and un-directional health policies and subsequent planning, and shortage of appropriately trained and skilled staff makes Pakistan's healthcare systems inefficient. These health indicators for the last fifty years declare that the improvement rate has been very slow. Therefore, in-depth research studies are required for making recommendations to the Government to take strong initiatives. Hence, present studies have been accomplished evaluating the PMS of Pakistan.

2.1 The organisation and Structure of the Healthcare Sector of Pakistan

The four provinces of Pakistan; Punjab, Sindh, Khabur Pakhtunkhwa, and Baluchistan have been assigned major responsibility of healthcare services; after a constitutional amendment a few years ago while Federal Government has now only advisory and research role in addition to coordination with foreign countries and international Health agencies like WHO. Provincial Governments have established Health Departments at the provincial capitals, Lahore, Karachi, Peshawar, and Quetta. They have District and Tehsil (sub-district) headquarter hospitals which are offering healthcare services in big and small cities (Figure 2.1).

In addition, the private health care system has enormously developed in the last 2-3 decades and own some very large and specialized hospitals in big cities of the country like Shaukat Khanum Cancer Hospital, Lahore, Bahria International Hospitals in Lahore, Rawalpindi, and Karachi, Shifa Medical Hospital, Islamabad, and many others. About 70% of the population is being served by the private sector regarding healthcare requirements. The employees of the Pakistan Army, Railways, Local governments, and many semi-government organisations are getting healthcare services from their parent departments (Hafeez et al., 2010). A broad structure of Pakistan's Healthcare Sector is presented in Fig. 2.1. Hassan, Mahmood, and Bukhsh (2017) have elaborated the structure and facilities of health services in Pakistan which is being described subsequently.

2.1.1 The Healthcare at Primary Level:

The primary healthcare services ' comprise of two levels; Basic Health Units (BHUs) and Rural Health Centres (RHCs) which provide healthcare services to patients of nearby villages. These healthcare centres provide services (curative and referral) at the Union Council and village levels to a population of 25000 people from the catchment area. Preventive, Maternal and Child Health (MCH) services are also provided in primary healthcare. The clinical, logistical and managerial support is provided as well to Lady Health Workers (LHWs).

2.1.2 Secondary Healthcare

The secondary healthcare is responsible for services like curative, technical, therapeutic, diagnostic, and referral services at Tehsil and District headquarters. The patients are admitted, and various specialist doctors take care in these centres.

2.1.2.1 Tehsil Headquarters Hospitals

Tehsil Headquarter Hospitals (THHs), mostly with 40-60 beds, are serving a population of 50,000 to 1,00,000 people and are providing Basic Emergency, Obstetrics, and New borne Care. The patients are referred to these centres by RHCs, BHU and Lady Health Workers.

2.1.2.2 District Headquarters

District Headquarter Hospitals (DHHs) located at all district levels of the country are providing services of various nature (promotive, preventive, curative, diagnostics, inpatient and referral) to 1-3 million people while patients can also be referred to by THHs, BHUs, and RHCs to District Headquarter Hospitals.

2.1.3 The Healthcare Services at the Tertiary Levels

The more specialized inpatient cares and highly technical services are provided at tertiary levels by the big hospitals, setup mostly at provincial headquarters and very big cities. The patients are also referred from secondary level hospitals to whom these centres cannot treat due to deficiencies of doctors, machinery and other associated facilities.

2.2 Regulatory Authorities of Healthcare Services in Pakistan

A high level technical regulatory authority for all matters related to healthcare (teaching, treating, and rules and regulations) in the country is Pakistan Medical and Dental Council (PMDC) as a body corporate. The aim is furnishing quality services in the healthcare sector to the people of Pakistan. Under 18th constitutional amendment, powers of Federal Ministry of Health have become majorly limited, devolving to the provinces of the federation by Government of Pakistan on June 30, 2011. Thus, most of the programs and responsibilities of Health Ministry are transferred to provincial health departments while the Health Ministry at the federal level is only coordinating the health matters (Ministry of National Health Services Regulation and Coordination, 2018).

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Figure 2.1: The organisation and structure of the Healthcare Sector of Pakistan

2.3 Available Facilities of Health in Pakistan

More than ten thousand health facilities (Basic Health Units to tertiary referral centers) are components of the public-sector healthcare system of Pakistan and serve various number of people depending upon the available facilities. Presently, more than 28 big hospitals are located in very big cities (Tertiary care facilities) in Pakistan, which are mostly associated with teaching institutions as well in addition to treatment functions (Hafeez et al., 2010). The facts and figures of Economic Survey of Pakistan (2017) indicate that budgets of healthcare are constantly increasing but at a slower rate. The expenditure of the health sector for the last decade has been 0.5 to 0.8 percent of the GDP of the country. Clearly, the budget allocations are far below than the WHO standards, which is at least 6 percent of GDP for provision of services of healthcare and lifesaving. These values reveal the potential gap to be bridged to approach the healthcare services of the modern world and reach at the standards fixed by WHO in terms of GDP. According to World Bank Report, , Pakistan's per capita spending for health

services was US \$ 36.2 which is even lesser than 50% of the WHO'S low-income countries benchmark of US\$ 86 (World Bank, 2001). Even increase in number of registered doctors, dentists, and nurses has not decreased the population per doctor, per dentist, per nurse and per bed. This phenomenon was due to steady increase in population during the last five years even with the increase of doctors and nurses and other healthcare facilities (Table 2.1, Pakistan Economic Survey, 2016-17).

Table 2.1: Healthcare Facilities (Numbers)

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(Pakistan Economic Survey, 2016-17)

2.4 Basic Issues and Challenges of Healthcare System of Pakistan

There are so many challenges and issues being faced by healthcare system of Pakistan, but the salient ones highlighted by authors (Hassan, Mahmood, and Bukhsh, 2017; Kurji, Premani, and Mithani, 2016; Mashhadi et al., 2016) are that the structure of the system is poorly designed, which is providing fewer facilities at the primary level, out of the reach of poor communities, the cost of medicines and procedures is very high, and many times circulation of fake medicines have been found. A lack of experts, physicians, doctors, specialists, and planners, as well as training and development of the human resources of the healthcare system has been observed. Spending of money on the healthcare system is always less than 1% against the recommended 6% of GDP by WHO, which is the major root cause of all the deficiencies. Health education and awareness among communities are still very poor. There have been poor coordination and communication between various healthcare facilities and authorities. Health priorities need to be well defined and identified. The present performance management system

is poor and not clean of biases. Its modernization has been slower whereas there is poor implementation of digital and online technologies of the innovative world. The monetary help of the public-sector healthcare system by the business community and public-private partnership for creating advanced level health facilities in the country remained limited. There has been meagre medical research matching local conditions. The health system has been designed and implemented by politicians and bureaucrats rather than health experts, thus having basic deficiencies and poor capabilities.

2.5 Organisation structure of the Healthcare System of Study Area, The Sialkot District

The study area is situated in the District of Sialkot, Punjab Province. Sialkot is a city which is very famous globally for the manufacture of sports products, very particularly the footballs. The footballs are exported to several countries of the world as well as FIFA. This city has been a major provider of footballs to FIFA Cup 2018. This city is also famous due to the name of Allama Iqbal, an international poet of Urdu and Persian languages. The district of Sialkot has one District Headquarter Hospital located in the city of Sialkot. This district has four tehsils: Sialkot, Daska, Sambrial and Pasrur at which four Tehsil Hospitals have been set up. Most of the hospitals have various department like ENT, Eye, Orthopaedic, Children, Medicines, Gynaecology, and Surgery, etc. In the Sialkot city, there are seven big hospitals (Two in government sector and five in private sector): Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital, Govt. Sardar Begum Teaching Hospital, LRBT (Eye Hospital), Fauji Foundation Hospital, Idrees Hospital, Sialkot Medical Complex, and Memorial Christian Hospital. Out of these 7 hospitals, Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital, and Govt. Sardar Begum Teaching Hospital was selected for the study being government hospitals and representing district hospitals of the province and the country. In addition, two Tehsil Hospitals: Civil Hospital Sambrial and Civil Hospital Daska were also selected for this study as representatives of Tehsil Hospitals.

The organisation structure of the healthcare system of Sialkot District (The Study Area) is constructed of multi-layers: Administrative System, Hospital systems, Development and Training Systems, and The Outreach System. The hospital system comprises of District Headquarter Hospital, Tehsil Headquarter Hospitals (one at each Tehsil: Daska, Pasrur, and Sambrial), Basic Health Centres, Rural Health Centres, and Specialized Health Centres like TB clinics. In addition, the District Health Care System has many parallel programs and structures. The organisational structure of the healthcare services of the district Sialkot has been presented

in Figure 2.2. DCO (District Coordination Officer) is the overall manager of all the district departments who also coordinate in between them. Executive District Officer Health (EDO) is the overall in charge of the district health sector. The Medical Superintendents (MS) are the managers of District and Tehsil hospitals. The Project Directors (PD) looks up all the development programs of the district healthcare while DOH (District Officer Health) takes care of all other programs like Outreach, Training, and primary health units like Rural Health Centres and Basic Health Centres. He is assisted by DDOH (Deputy District Health Officer), DCs (District Coordinators) Programs, and TB Dots.

There are three training and human development institutions in the district which are: District Health Development Centre, General Nursing and Midwifery School, and Community Midwifery School. Some more details have been presented in training Section of this chapter.

The major administrative system of the Sialkot district healthcare system is presented in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Administrative Setup of the Sialkot District Healthcare System

Sr. No.	Name of Post	Sanctioned Positions
1	Executive District Officer Health	1
2	District Officer Health	1
3	Deputy District Officer of Health	3
4	Program Director DHDC	1
5	District Coordinator National Program	1
6	District Coordinator EPI Surveillance	1
7	District Sanitary Inspector	1
8	CDC Officer	1
9	CDC Inspector	88
10	Drug Inspector	1
11	District Superintendent Vaccination	1
12	ASV	3
13	Tehsil Sanitary Inspector	3
14	Inspector Vaccination	3

The outreach system consists of vaccinators, sanitation, nutrition and social mobilization personnel (Table 2.3).

Table 2.3: Outreach System of Sialkot District Healthcare services

Sr.	Post	Sanctioned Positions
1	Vaccinators	119
2	CDC Supervisors	88
3	Sanitary Inspectors	88
4	Nutrition Supervisor	88
5	Social mobilization NCHD	88
6	Sanitary Supervisor	05

2.6 Brief Characteristics of the Selected Hospitals of the Study Area

There are many hospitals under public and private sectors of the study area, The Sialkot District, Pakistan. A list of hospitals of the district has been presented in Table 2.4. However, only four hospitals: Allama Iqbal Hospital Sialkot, Sardar Begum Hospital Sialkot, Civil Hospital Tehsil Daska (District Sialkot), and Civil Hospital Tehsil Sasmbrial (District Sialkot) were selected for this study. Some salient characteristics of these hospitals are presented subsequently.

2.6.1 Allama Iqbal Hospital Sialkot City

Allama Iqbal Memorial Hospital (AIMH) is a government hospital established in the famous football manufacturing city of Sialkot (Picture 2.1). This hospital (Picture 2.2) also serves for teaching and training of undergraduate students from Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College. Therefore, the hospital is equipped with reasonably good diagnostics facilities. The hospital has Outpatient Departments (OPD) of Medical, General Surgery, Neurosurgery, Urology, Psychiatry, and Orthopaedic as well as pathology laboratory and radiological imaging facilities (Latif et al., 2017). Each department is headed by the senior-most doctor of the concerned department. The overall manager of the hospital is called MS (Medical Superintendent) who is helped by Deputy MS.

Figure 2.2: Organisation structure of healthcare services of Sialkot District, Pakistan

There are separate in charges of Human Resource Department and Nursing Department. A few other departments like IT, transporting, Maintenance and Purchase also help the technical departments. In addition to general duty doctors, the hospital has specialist doctors as Gynaecologist, Nephrologist, General Surgeon, Neurosurgeon, Dermatologist, Laparoscopic Surgeon, and Acupuncturist. The performance management is practiced by head of department in coordination with HR and IT departments. The performance of employees is done on daily basis but put in the records annually.

Table 2.4: Hospital Facilities in the Sialkot District under Public Sector

Sr. No.	Type of Health Facility	Number	Bed Strength
1	District Headquarter Hospital	01	400
2	DHQ Level Hospital	01	134
3	THQ Daska	01	179
	THQ Pasrur	01	40
	THQ Sambrial	01	40
4	Rural Health Centre	08	160
5	Basic Health Units	88	176

Sr. No.	Type of Health Facility	Number	Bed Strength
6	GRDs	02	--
7	RDs (ZC)	23	--
7	MCH Centre	14	--
8	Sub Health Centre	15	--
9	TB Clinics	02	10
10	City Dispensaries	03	--
11	Health house	2291	--

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Picture 2.1: Football Manufacturing in the famous city of Sialkot

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Picture 2.2: The building of Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital, Sialkot

2.6.2 Sardar Begum Hospital Sialkot

Govt. Sardar Begum Civil (DHQ Level) Hospital (Picture 2.3), Sialkot was established in 1992 by a businessman and was handed over to Govt. of the Punjab Health department in the same year. Its strength was 84 beds at that time. Due to the addition of 50 beds of W.C.H. (Women Child Hospital), the bed strength of this Hospital was raised to 134 beds in February-1999. Later in 2006, its founder added one more block increasing its capacity. At present, Govt. Sardar Begum Hospital is working as District Hospital and serving as Teaching Hospital as well for the Government Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College Sialkot. The hospital is headed by Medical Superintendent (MS) and helped by Deputy MS as well as specialist doctors: Anaesthetist (E.N.T., Eye), Surgeon, Gynaecologist, TB & Chest, Radiologist, Pathologist, Physician, Orthopaedic, Paediatrician, Dentist, and Emergency. The hospital has facilities of laboratory, operation theatre, X-Ray, ECG, Ultrasound, Blood Bank, E.P.I Centre, Family Planning, Power Generators, Ambulances, and Water Filtration Plant. The performance management system is like Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot.

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Picture 2.3 Government Sardar Baighum Teaching Hospital, Sialkot

2.6.3 Civil Hospital Tehsil Daska, District Sialkot

This hospital has been established at Tehsil headquarter Daska (Picture 2.4) of Sialkot District under the public sector of healthcare services of Pakistan. The hospital delivers primary and secondary healthcare services to the community of the catchment area. The communities can access and afford the services of the hospital which are sustainably improved for the health and quality of life. The major aims are provision of quality health services, developing health providers, generation of reliable health information, and making accountable the non-achievers of targets.

The hospital comprises of departments of Physiotherapy, Radiology, Ophthalmology, Cardiology, Surgery, Pharmacy, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, and Orthopaedic. In additions, programs are run to control TB, Malaria, Polio, AIDS, Hepatitis, and Influenza. The serving teams are administration, consultants, doctors, nursing and paramedics. The organisational structure is like Allama Iqbal Hospital, as described in the earlier section.

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Picture 2.4 Civil Hospital Tehsil Daska, Sialkot District

2.6.4 Civil Hospital Tehsil Sambrial, District Sialkot

Tehsil hospital Sambrial (Picture 2.5) serves a population of about 0.6 million and has bed strength of 40. The healthcare services like promotive, preventive, curative, and diagnostics are provided to patients by Tehsil hospital Sambrial. The patients referred by the Rural Health Centres for some specialist care are also taken care of. The hospital provides basic and comprehensive Emergency Obstetric and New-born Care (EmONC).

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Picture 2.5: Civil Hospital Tehsil Sambrial, Sialkot District

2.7 The Performance Management System in Healthcare System of Pakistan

The performance by healthcare institutions is a dire need because the workforce of hospitals is dealing with the lives of patients where any negligence cannot be ignored. However, developing countries like Pakistan are facing challenges in providing community services including healthcare systems and their effective implementation mainly due to limited resources and working capability (Hameed, Karamat, and Mehmood, 2012). Every employee

must show the required performance matching the known standards. An efficient Performance Management System only can ensure exemplary performance of individuals. Management of any organisation is directed towards two major goals; achieving the goals of organisations and achieving the goals of its employees.

The performance management has been there since long ago in public hospitals of Pakistan through olden and traditional ways. But, nowadays, healthcare management information systems are used to support the overall management of data and information about patient care, diseases, and resource management (Razzaque, and Jalal-Karim, 2010). So, the Government of Pakistan decided to revolutionize the healthcare industry and changing from manual data processing to electronic data processing methods in early 1990s. HMIS (Healthcare Management Information System) is an advanced innovated and integrated modern management system for hospitals of Pakistan. Therefore, the Ministry of Health, Government of Pakistan and provincial healthcare departments collaborated with international agencies in developing a National Health Management Information Systems (NHMIS) during 1990-93, which was implemented subsequently in provincial hospitals (Ministry of Health, 1995, & 1996). However, the current NHMIS has been implemented only in the Primary Level healthcare facilities. No significant data from these hospitals, have been recorded by the Health Departments of various province (Qazi and Ali, 2011).

The feedback on the performance of NHMIS in hospitals was received in 1999 (Ministry of Health, 1999). The Reports regarding performance of NHMIS indicated its lesser utilization while the staff considered it an extra burden of work. The monitoring of the system was also poor. It has been suggested that all efforts must be concerted to make NHMIS a success and hospitals are upscaled enough to provide quality health services to the patients (Hafiz et al., 2010, Qazi and Ali, 2009). The NHMIS are affected by a great variety of internal and external influential factors. The study of Qazi and Ali (2009 and 2010) indicated that the performance of NHMIS in Pakistan is affected by many external and internal factors. They also identified certain issues related to the system. For understanding the issues and challenges, Arshad, Noordin, and Othman (2017) performed SWOT Analysis using data collected from hospitals of Islamabad. The results of their SWOT Analysis have been presented in terms of Strengths, Weaknesses, External factors' threats and Opportunities, which are extracted as under.

2.7.1 Strengths of Improved PMS of Pakistan (where implemented)

The modern system of PMS, where implemented, has indicated that it can provide refined services of healthcare, decrease manual data collection and mistakes, facilitate better and improved data storage, safeguards the confidentiality of sensitive information, increases availability of timely data, reduces data loss, and enhances access to accurate and relative information. A fast communication between stakeholders and better reporting is possible. The documentation quality and originality are reformed, paperless environment is favoured resulting in establishment of solid and sound IT infrastructure. The new system is cost-effective and possesses more productivity for the end-users (Arshad, Noordin, and Othman, 2017).

2.7.2 Weaknesses

The SWOT analysis (Arshad, Noordin, and Othman, 2017) of new PMS in Pakistan revealed a few weaknesses which are: a shortage of competent staff and lack of appropriate training programs, poor commitment of top management, E-health services, interest and motivation in learning new systems, skilled staff for maintenance of hardware and software, accountability and transparency and good system integration. The reporting structure has been regarded as unprofessional. Limited access to internet, errors in recording healthcare data, and coordination between service providers are further problems which emphasized need for further training and collaborative tools/

Applications. Limited or no interoperability are the further complaints. The cost of implementation and IT adoption have also been reported to be very high.

2.7.3 Opportunities

While analysing the PMS, Arshad, Noordin, and Othman (2017) observed that there are so many probable opportunities as well which are attached to the new system. The opportunities could be improvement in reporting and data presentation, provision of quality healthcare services, better resources utilization, and good patients' trust and satisfaction. The public awareness and support programs, and training facilities could be enhanced. Better human resources and funds utilization and healthcare management are possible. The IT infrastructure, as well as internet availability and enhanced bandwidth, will become permanent facilities of the organisations.

2.7.4 External Threats

The external threats to PMS could be political interventions, shortage of human resources and trained staff, and transfers and postings of professional staff under external pressure. Data and information hacking, and end-users resistance to systems change and implementation could be further threats. Rapid changes in technology and IT systems, more reporting requirements, and load shedding and electrical surges might also be external threats (Arshad, Noordin, and Othman, 2017).

This analysis clearly indicates that performance management possesses very good strengths for future adoption on large scale, provided that identified deficiencies and weaknesses are tackled. This also serves as example and emphasizes that such studies are required at each district level of the healthcare system of the provinces so that improvement opportunities are understood well for a better consequent performance system.

2.8 The Scope of the study

The present research aims at investigating the performance management system using the data from Hospitals of Sialkot District, Pakistan, more specifically from Orthopaedic Departments. Different variables are used to analyse the performance of employees that could eventually reflect the PMS which is the focus of present performance management system, organisational structure, information technology, and human resource while different models and theories are part of this research as well that helped to set the foundation of this research. The major target of this study is exploring the currently employed performance management system in the selected hospitals, then to evaluate the performance management system within the context of management as well as employees and finally to provide solid recommendations based on evidence to make the system more effective and advantageous. Keeping in mind this background, present research benefitted from earlier studies on the Performance Management System of Pakistan (Harris and Samreen 2015; Rahimi et al., 2017; Zubair and Khan, 2014).

2.9 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, an overview, available facilities, and structure of the Healthcare System of Pakistan under the public sector has been presented. The challenges faced, and deficiencies identified by a few earlier authors have been highlighted. The budget allocations are meagre (lesser than 1% of GDP against 6% minimum standard by WHO), which are the root cause of many problems. Most of the hospitals remain understaffed and it seems very difficult to

successfully meet the curative demands of catchment populations. Resultantly, government hospitals are overcrowded and face so many challenges. Performance Management is still conventional except in the big hospitals of private sector. The SWOT analysis of NHMIS implemented during 1990-93 in the selected hospitals indicated strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and external threats that have been elaborated in the chapter. The present research was completed to address a few aspects of the evaluation of the Performance Management System of Pakistan.

Chapter Three

Literature Review

The review of literature is conducted for the in-depth understanding of the subject of a research study comprising of reviewing relevant concepts, ideas, and views of salient authors of the past and the conditions under which these research works were accomplished. The findings of former investigations can prove as guidelines to identify deficiencies, gaps, relevancies and future horizons of research on the selected subject. The purpose of this chapter is to set the theoretical foundations of this research-based upon reviewing the relevant literature. The literature review chapter is divided into six major sections and various sub-sections. The whole discussion is based on theoretical concepts using different theories and findings of previous authors.

3.1 Introduction

Many empirical and theoretical research studies were completed involving various features of the performance management (PM) like need of implementation of PM, success and effectiveness of the system, challenges and deficiencies, factors affecting the systems and variables involved, satisfaction of all the stakeholders, and strategies required for improvement of the system in different organisations. The performance management system (PMS) has now become multi-disciplinary and finding ways to enter almost all sectors (Van Dooren, Bouckaert, and Halligan, 2015; Rashidi, 2015).

The present techniques of performance management in healthcare organisations do not fulfill the emerging challenges. Therefore, a strong need for improvement is felt because good PMS acts as a powerful tool to achieve the assigned outcomes (Ginter et al., 2018). An effective PMS involves recognition of employees' performance, development, appraisal, coaching, and real-time feedback, setting of different goals and subsequently rewarding them (Van Dooren et al., 2015). Therefore, health care organisations should ensure that programs of performance management envisage motivation, collaboration, communication and teamwork in between employees and managers. The role of every individual should be subjected to similar measurements of performance (Bergeron, 2017).

The performance management may basically identify some standards of assessment, called performance indicators. Gorman (2015) suggested employees' experience levels as the best performance indicators while Baker et al. (2016) identified experience, talent fit on a position,

and engagement as the main performance predictors. Coaching and feedback should be kept open. In hospitals, good engagement of employees makes improvement in the productivity of services. Strom et al. (2014) recommended that more emphasis should be made over the strengths of the employees as compared to the weaknesses. A good communication should be made with employees, promoting a culture of recognition and trust which can develop employees who are seen connected to mission of hospitals. Therefore, performance management system cannot be overlooked in the health care sector. For most of the healthcare companies, simplicity can be used for sustaining and improving performance.

In addition to employees, leaders of healthcare are also considered very important in a PMS. The system providing a ranking of managers proves very good (Manuel, 2015). Through alignment of performance management with technique of leadership, leaders can do the positioning of their organisations/hospitals for higher performance (Weaver et al., 2016). Before making improvement in the performance management systems, leaders should challenge different false predictions related to performance management (Cokins, 2017). Through facts of performance management, a foundation can be laid down for a system that best drives effective outcomes of healthcare services. However, the research of Wager et al. (2017) identified that only 10 percent of HR leaders give the time worth to put into these processes. Cokins (2017) is of the view that before making investment in processes and technologies, leaders of healthcare should always rethink about performance management.

3.2 The Concepts, and Components of PMS

A Performance Management System comprises of performance evaluation of the workforce, utilization efficiency of the organisational resources, the performance of the organisation, and the satisfaction of all the stakeholders; the employees, patients, and management when referred to a healthcare service (The hospitals). The number of studies has defined the concept of performance management system by linking performance of employees to performance of an organisation. The subsequent sections investigate the concepts of Performance and Performance Management System and PMS components.

3.2.1 The Concepts of Performance Management

The concept of performance and performance management system has been under discussion for a long time and different researchers have given their own opinion to reach a common concept. The term performance management has got popularity in 1980s. Campbell's (1999)

identified the performance as a measurable variable that indicates the behaviours and actions of individuals helping them to achieve organisational goals. Another definition of performance by Jackson et al. (2014) shows that performance is the fulfillment of economic goals by using outcome-based financial indicators. Van Dooren, Bouckaert and Halligan (2015) and Shields et al. (2015) have found a link between performance and performance management system.

Ferron Vilchez and Darnall (2016) and Kerzner and Kerzner (2017) have regarded performance management system as a commanding framework that helps in appraising and managing employees' performance and fulfilling performance expectations from them through guidance and feedback. After an appraisal, it is possible to point out their deficiencies, if any, in discharging their duties and encouraging in case of good achievements. The appraisal outcomes can be shared with employees very easily and efficiently. The rewarding and awarding possibilities of PMS also motivate other employees to do work better so that they could also be considered for performance appreciation. Thus, the system helps in promoting effectively the opportunities considered as the operational and strategic needs of an organisation. Lee and Chen (2013) described that performance management systems help in integrating technology with familiar business methodologies because its digitized online ICT (Information and communication technology) component enhances the handling of information and data and communicating effectively to all relevant stakeholders including employees themselves.

Lopez et al. (2009) claimed that a great role is played by PMS for achieving the organisational goals. According to them, this system comprises of management tools like performance appraisal, job design, reward system, and assessment of training needs of individuals. Meeting the training needs of employees promote and refine their capabilities in the performance of their duties in better ways. Thus, the system helps in maximizing the individuals' and teams' performance and motivates them by involving work planning, feedback regarding their assessments, and institutional design. Institutional design is a set of formal rules and regulations relating to practice of organisations and the complying mechanisms by the managers and executives of the firms. Some performance indicators are used in this regard (WHO, 2010). This helps in directing, monitoring, and refining the utilization of human resources. However, performance management is not a tool for forcing employees to work more, rather it can make aware and motivate them to improve poor performance situations (Fernandez, 2004). He is of the view that PM helps in highlighting the values and competencies of organisations. This system helps managers and executives of organisations in aligning the performance of employees with organisational goals.

3.2.2 The Performance Management of Employees

Employees are the backbone of a performing system in achieving objectives and goals of an organisation. Assuring good performance of individuals and assessment of their performance without any biases is highly important. A good performance of an employee not backed with a justifiable appraisal is just like denying his performance. He must be encouraged and rewarded for good performance to motivate doing further good work. Thus, to get the full benefits of performance, a strong and effective performance management system is required that can arrange implementation of strategic tools to ensure the productivity of employees. Integration of different methods and tools is required to make things align accurately in the right direction. Further training and employees' commitment could eventually contribute to the performance management system (Lee and Chen, 2013). According to Bacal (1999), a performance management system should ascertain ongoing communication between employees and their immediate bosses. This helps in finding how employees contribute through their jobs in achieving the goals of the organisation and a consequent success. This establishes and strengthens working relationship between employees and their supervisors to sustain and improve the employees' performance.

Some studies have viewed individual performance as an objective variable measured by using market and financial indicators (Janssens and Steyaert, 2009; Khan et al., 2010). Lopez et al. (2009) elaborated that the performance appraisal helps in analyzing the overall potentials and capabilities of employees in a good performance management process. The parameters like employees' satisfaction and commitment, absenteeism, qualification, and experience, and customer satisfaction might tell about the performance of employees. The appraisal will require collecting, assessing, reviewing, and analyzing the data of individuals with regards to their current and past work behaviour and performance (Mathieu and Zajac, 1990). Habib et al. (2010) extend this argument by declaring that evaluative and developmental objectives of organisations can be achieved declaring the performance appraisal as the major objectives. The achievement of assigned duties by employees pools up to fulfilling targets of the institutions.

If the appraisal of certain individuals is found below, then the need arises to identify the barriers of attaining required performance by those employees. The performance management system can help not only to identify these constraints but also indicates the ways to remove such hurdles. Many barriers affecting performance of employees have been reported by various authors. For examples, Thomas (2018) from Forbes Council identified problems of Skills,

Working place Environment, and Motivation as the major barriers. Clapon (2019) has mentioned: Lack of communication and social interaction between colleagues as well as management, the constant absence of manager or team leader, too many rules in the way of working, new idea or suggestion does not get support, lack of a proper channel for communication and feedback, and no team activities outside of work as significant barriers. According to Deeb (2019), multitasking, poor communication, and inconsistent policy enforcement are the main reasons for poor performance by employees of an organisation. These obstacles can be removed by adopting policies ‘no room for errors’, improving working atmosphere, enhancing communication and feedback, increasing mentoring and guidance and reforming of rules, specifying performance expectations for all employees, fixing and conveying priorities of assignments, fulfilling the requirements of required work timely, appreciation of good work, ensuring accurate and unbiased appraisal with short intervals instead of after one year, and using all the human resources efficiently without overburdening any one of them (Clapon, 2019; Deeb, 2019; Thomas, 2018). It means that responsibilities lie upon management to remove the obstacles retarding the good performance of employees.

3.2.3 The Performance Management of Organisations

As far as organisational performance is concerned, the human resource management performance studies have not given any precise and compact concept or meaning of organisational performance (Janssens and Steyaert, 2009, Jashapara, 2004). Past studies did not mention any common concept for the measurement of organisational performance, rather different variables and indicators were employed by researchers to evaluate the performance of an organisation. Some of the studies used subjective measures for the evaluation of firm’s performance such as employees’ satisfaction and happiness, perceptions of executives, commitment of employee to the organisation, and satisfaction of customer (Dex and Smith, 2001). Whereas, some other authors are of the view to measuring it objectively, like financial and market indicators (Meyer and Allen, 1997). The performance of an organisational is very important and dependent on variables affected by so many internal and external factors (independent variables), but it has not been defined appropriately and clearly (Boxall et al., 2002). Thus, no common theory is related with organisational performance assessment and there are needs and enough scope to fulfill this gap (Guest, 2011, Mohammad et al., 2014), which provides sound logic to conduct the present study and future studies on this aspect.

3.2.4 Methods and Criteria of Performance Appraisal

The performance management system is a consistent process involving communication between supervisors and subordinates on regular basis to establish a clear understanding of jobs and goals. This also encompasses training the employees, monitoring and evaluating the performance, and providing the feedback on regular basis. However, it is highly important that the appraisal should be free of contamination and biases. The issue is that there are no common criteria for the exact measurement and appraisal of the performance of employees. Some appraisal criteria like rating assigned by a supervisor, peer review, or a stimulating work sample are used to measure performance of employees. Sometimes very hard criteria e.g. calculating revenue earned by individuals or a group of individuals, saving in cost, complaints from customers, and focusing on validity, and reliability may be used for this purpose (Bacal, 1999). A uniform rating system must be adopted for all employees because differences and variances may cause contamination in individuals' performance if not properly taken into consideration (Lee et al., 2015). Reliability issue can be resolved by making the observer fully trained (Boxall et al., 2008).

Gomes, Yasin, and Lisboa (2011) summarised the published research work on performance measurement for the last twenty years and prepared a list of performance criteria and performance measurement systems (PMS). According to his review-based findings, the PMS must be based on non-financial aspects, the criteria should consist of the means to formulate strategy and monitor performance results, goals of the organisational, critical success factors, and needs of customer could be assessed accurately by the system which must be able to accept dynamic changes and strategies, and has a potential to absorb quickly and precisely changes in the organisation and environment. Further, the system should be clearly defined, realistic, understandable and implementable easily, and focus on the long-term goals, explicit purpose, and needs of specific situations. A rewards system must be incorporated in the system allowing the PMS a continuous process of improvement.

3.2.5 Guidelines for Benefitting Performance Management

For improving or developing newly efficient PMS, leaders should understand the difference between real facts and conventional myths related to performance management (Bergeron, 2017). It is said that every individual can perform effectively with right procedure or through right training, but the fact is that talent which fits for a role effectively predicts the role performance. Many times, it is believed that similar performance measurements should be

integrated into all the roles. But the reality is that the definition of performance measurements should be done depending on the success within some specific roles. It is also misunderstood that experience works as the most effective predictor of good and effective performance and the combined influence of engagement, while experience and talent are identified as the best performance predictor. Likewise, it is believed that HR is held accountable to manage performance while the truth is that managers and employees are held accountable for performance management. In a similar way, the myth is evaluation of performance for once or twice within a year is found as enough for closing gaps of performance, but the fact is that acquiring desired outcomes demand direct, open and on-going coaching and feedback. It is also assumed that performance management should target to adjust the weaknesses, but the reality is that performance management should target growing strengths (Bergeron, 2017).

The healthcare company may own a world-class performance system, but the system is found only as much effective as the managers who implement the system. The study of (Ginter, 2018) identified that around 70 percent of employees rated managers being best and the systems of performance management as effective. However, in accordance with the research of Trevino and Nelson (2016), some of the employees of health care companies rated managers below average. Only 2 percent rated the performance management as 'very good'. According to Arnaboldi, Lapsley, and Steccolini (2015), good managers own the right talent to engage, position and support the staff. Such managers do empowerment of employees for making decisions; praise or identify achievements of employee; care for employees and have open and regular communication with employees. Health care companies aim to enhance employee and business productivity and performance should make more investment in acquiring right managers and should support the managers in engaging employees. Highly talented people own predisposition for performance and depict the better performance. For instance, when patient satisfaction and quality is used by hospitals for measuring performance, selection of employees from emotional associations enhance the likelihood that such measurements are met successfully (Almajali, Masa'deh, and Tarhini, 2016). According to Sozen et al. (2016), hiring of employees is seen dependent on some criteria of selection, particularly for major roles that drive organisational outcomes. It assists health care companies to acquire performance goals in most effective way.

The relationships of manager and employee are considered important for developing engagement in staff. In healthcare organisations, engaged employees are not only seen as productive but these employees are also seen as better in terms of engaging patients. Focus on

strengths, well-developed expectations, and meaningful conversations do the development of such employees who are seen more linked with mission of an organisation and not just with the ride (Ginter, 2018). In accordance with McCarthy and Allen (2017) for fostering engagement, managers should clearly communicate standards of performance and should communicate the good performance in roles. The regular communication on expectations of performance with team members should be done rather than once a year.

Leaders should target the strengths of employees because the research of Jenkinson (2016) indicated that only one percent of employees agreed that supervisor target on strengths than on weaknesses. However, 61% of employees were found engaging in their work. A study of Saint-Jacques, Turcotte, and Pouliot (2018) indicated that most of the supervisors were after the personal weaknesses and accorded the least consideration to their hidden strong potentials and capabilities. Their results also revealed impact of organisational context put on the strengths of employees. Through interpreting the strengths of employees, managers and leaders can assist employees in growing and learning in areas where the employees own more likelihood of success (Shogren et al., 2016). D'Andreamatteo et al., (2015), stressed that leaders should get benefits through strengths-dependent performance management techniques. The managers should apply strengths of team for acquiring performance objectives. Employees should be helped collectively and individually within teams. The alignment of talents should be done for fulfilling the expectations of different roles. The incorporation of strengths should be done into reviews and conversations of performance, employees should be assisted to set objectives dependent on strengths. Formal strengths-dependent management training should be considered for managers. The Corporate Leadership Council involved almost 20,000 people in their global study across multiple organisations and industries. The outcomes of the study were interesting and told that when strengths of people were focused, their performance increased massively by 36%. In contrast, focusing on weaknesses dropped the performance by 27% (Harter, Schmidt, and Hayes, 2002). Trenier, Harrington, and Jamnadas (2012) suggested that using strengths of people favours workplace engagement; the most engaged employees are those utilizing their strengths during major time of the duty.

3.3 Factors influencing performance management system

Understanding the factors taking part in a PMS is also very important. The number of studies has emphasized on different factors. The most important factors are organisational structure, information technology, training and employees' commitment (Habib et al., 2010). According

to Neely, Mike, and Chris (2007), factors influencing the development of a performance measurement system and consequently a PMS are numerous and complicated. Based upon their action, these can be divided into two groups: Drivers of change (factors that cause necessary change) and Barriers to change (factors that prevent a change from being effectively implemented).

The performance measurement systems factors have also been classified as internal and external factors by Pedersen and Sudzina (2012). Internal factors come under corporate culture like top management commitment and support, employees' training, rewards policy, organisational strategy and structure, and revising performance criteria (Baird and Schoh, 2012; Johanson et al., 2006; Kennerley and Neely, 2003; Tung, Baird, and Schoch, 2011). The external factors are those which are beyond the control of an organisation but commonly influencing business and performance of a company. For example, implementation of IT technology, the current global competition, and changing customer choices (Pedersen and Sudzina, 2012) or differences in various cultures (Aguinis and Gottfredson, 2012). Studies of various researchers (Atkinson, 2012; Kennerley and Neely, 2003) have identified six groups of key factors, which are highly important for developing a PMS. These are: related to processes, related to people, related to skills, related to employee needs, related to culture, and related to systems.

Performance is taken as a dependent variable to investigate the performance management system while various factors are acting as independent variables because they influence the PMS. These factors are discussed subsequently using evidence from earlier studies and researches.

3.3.1 Organisational Factors:

The organisational structure is significantly affecting the performance of an organisation that is reflected through performance management system. Several researchers have explained the relationship between organisational structure and performance of an organisation. More prominent are research studies of Wilden et al. (2013), Alamsjah (2011), and Siam and Hilman (2012). Findings of these authors revealed a significant and positive relationship. Some other researchers considered organisational structure as a part of strategy execution that contributes in the success/failure of organisational performance (Rahimnia, Castka, and Sharp, 2005; Delisi, 2006; Hrebiniak, 2006; Alashloo et al., 2005). Research work of a few more authors (Fernandez, González, and Sabherwal, 2004; O'Malley, 2000) suggested organisational

structure as the most effective strategy execution factor which has strong effect on organisational performance. Still, there were suggestions to assign a moderating role of some other factors such as strategic communication helping in examining the effects of organisational structure on performance (Andrew et al., 2011, Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). Considering all this background, a synthesis of different studies is presented here to stipulate to what extent the organisational structure is important in explaining the performance and performance management system.

3.3.1.1 Organisational Structure:

Health care services are much higher and exceptional than a profit earning business because the only intention here is to serve the patients, providing comfort, and cure them (Blass et al., 2017). The performance management of hospitals is much critical and important involving numerous qualitative factors, the effectiveness of which cannot be measured quantitatively. Due to this, there is a practical dilemma for professional performance management in the context of hospitals. The way organisational structure influences the performance is to be explored in further detail.

Organisational structure is defined as the division of labor into different tasks and then developing coordination among them (Mintzberg and Quinn, 1991; Wilden et al., 2013). Jackson and Morgan (1982) have defined organisational structure as setting up the duties to complete the tasks or to do the work. This can be presented in an organisational chart to make it self-explanatory. The organisational structure helps to organize the set of responsibilities and roles that allow employees to perform their tasks and channelize and integrate the things to solve the problems. In this regard, Sablynski (2012) presented his own view about organisational structure and explained that it involves dividing, grouping, and coordinating the job tasks. However, Wolf (2002, p. 78) presented a broader view of organisational structure and stated that “Organisation structure is the architecture of business competence, leadership, talent, functional relationships and arrangement”.

According to Katsikea et al. (2011), firms used organisational structure to perform three different tasks: firstly, as a control mechanism that helps in affecting work outcomes of employees, secondly it ensures the effective and efficient performance of tasks, and thirdly it helps in achieving the organisational goals. Daft (1995) included internal characteristics of the organisation into the definition of organisational structure. Internal characteristics broadly include strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats to an organisation (Keefer, 2018). On an

explanatory note, these may be Well-Known Company Policies, Strong Leadership, Handling Poor Performance, Effective Sharing of Goals, Great Teamwork, High Employee Morale, Offering Training Opportunities, Adapting to Opportunities and Changes, and Understanding of Risks (Johnson, 2018). Therefore, the above described internal factors are of very high importance for an organisation. Considering this importance, the organisation structure has been included as one of the components of present study.

Organisational structure allows the employer of a firm to allocate the responsibility and authority among the workers and executing the rules and regulation. Organisational structure helps in assigning job and tasks specifications among employees. More broadly, organisational structure is a system of allocating powers and responsibilities and carrying out the work by organisational members (Teixeria et al., 2012). A very compact and authentic definition of organisational structure is given by Jones (2013) that seems covering almost all aspects which say that organisational structure is an authority and task relationship and coordinating behaviours and actions of employees to achieve the organisational goals.

Slater et al. (2010) presented constructs of organisational structure i.e. formalization, centralization, and specialization. Formal rules and procedures to govern the decision and working relationships are formulated in accordance with the structure of the organisation, giving an authority to top management to make decisions or delegate the responsibility to lower management, and helps the organisation to employ experts for efficient and effective working. To further clarify this relationship, some other authors have presented a different structural dimension that uses a mechanistic-to-organic approach that can help in setting up a system to enhance the performance. Mechanistic structures involve centralized decision-making following formal rules and procedures whereas organic structures involve de-centralized decision-making and not emphasizing on formal rules and procedures (Lunenburg 2012; Wilden et al., 2013).

The structure of an organisation can be drawn as a flow chart from top to bottom, with each interlinked node showing a different position in the organisation. That position is responsible for reporting to the upper position and there is also a possibility that they are responsible for supervising the low-level positions. Performance management mainly includes the relationships between supervisors and subordinates. The guidance is provided regarding accountability of each position to monitor and review the performance of individuals at other positions (Camisón and Villar-López, 2014). According to Noruzy et al. (2013), from the

organisational structure, it is clearly delineated that who reports to whom and gets instructions from whom. Because of this, the ways and approaches through which handling of performance reviews is done get affected (Georgellis, 2015). In case of an organisation has long hierarchy as per structure of an organisation, i.e. people must work closely with their supervisors who guide them in setting performance objectives and responsible for performing a review of employees' performance on annual basis (Uzkurt et al, 2013). Real et al. (2014), however, argued that if an organisation has flatter hierarchy, the employees themselves are responsible for setting performance goals.

3.3.1.2 Effect of Organisational Structure on Performance

The structure is linked with the performance of organisations. For example, Subramaniam et al., (2002) found that the structure of an organisation is associated with output and personal behaviour of the employees of the organisations. The structure of a company and organisational commitment have been positively correlated in Australian. If the structure of the organisation appreciates performance by employees, rewards good work and addresses deficiencies of skills through offering of training, the performance of the organisation is certainly affected positively and significantly. Study of Folami (2005) has found that decision-making, communication, and performance are positively affected by various structures of an organisation. An organisational structure comprises of policies, authority and responsibilities, communication, and information flow of a business formation. It is commonly either a flat or hierarchical structure, but some companies can adopt a mix of these two (Meehan, 2019). According to him, a flat organisation has a few or no levels of management between management and employees with very lesser supervision, rather promotes their involvement in the decision-making process. Whereas in hierarchical organisation, every employee is subordinate to someone else except the CEO while the layout consists of multiple layers like a pyramid. Each organisation structure has advantages and disadvantages. However, organisation size, flexibility, technology, strategy, culture, learning, and innovation promote performance, effectiveness, high productivity, committing, and behaviour (Becker et al., 1996; Dalton et al., 1980; Dammen, 2001; Hao et al., 2007; Kessler, 2007; Ledbetter, 2003; Zeffane, 1994). A difference can be found among management style of public and private sector firms. Finally, they found a positive and significant relationship between organisational structure and organisational commitment that affects performance.

3.3.1.3 Organisational Structure Dimensions and the Performance

Organisational structure has different dimensions and many factors are combinedly form the organisational structure. According to Malhotra (2009), Organisation structure has three dimensions: Formalization, Centralization, and Complexity. Formalization is the description and standardization of various activities, and rules to be followed in that organisation. Centralization refers to the level of decision-making at higher level whereas Complexity is the degree of coordination, communication, and control within the organisation. However, this is not the final view of this concept because some of the authors also include trust level and organisational design in it (Dunham et al., 1994, Shaemi Barzoki et al., 2013). The results of Aghajani et al. (2013) showed that organisational structure has significant relationship with employees' creativity while the latter has a positive and significant relationship with the level of complexity, formalization, and centralization. If the structure of an organisation is complex and decision-making has been centralized, the working and performance become difficult.

Bhatti et al. (2011) included supervisory relationships, the flow of work and department structure in the organisational structural dimensions. In performance management, there is an involvement of systematic improvement in individual as well as team performance with the help of goalsetting and review of performance on regular basis. The organisational structure has a significant impact on performance management systems and standards and through setting performance goals, the structure of a company can be shaped appropriately. Through getting complete knowledge about interplay between organisational structure and performance management, the management in an organisation can get guidance in implementing effective performance management systems for structure of an organisation (Alegre and Chiva, 2013).

3.3.1.4 Organisational Structural Roles, and Control Rules Affecting the Performance

Organisational structure is the initial step for management and control of positions, roles, and accountability of employees, hierarchical levels, and processes for integration and solving issues (Dadfar et al., 2013; Shields et al., 2015). The organisational structure is, in fact, the developed pattern of relationships among various sections of an organisation and a framework of a company's authority and assigning tasks. It helps in describing the relations among various roles played by components inside a firm (Melnik et al., 2014; Patel et al., 2013). Organisational structure is a mechanism of grouping, distributing, collaborating, reporting, and monitoring task relationships for controlling, coordinating, and motivating workers to work effectively for fulfilling the goals of a firm (Camisón and Villar-López, 2014; Junni et al.,

2013). Thus, final goal of an organisational structure is to utilize human resources efficiently, but it depends on the extent to which employees are communicated and made aware with procedures and rules of the company to follow. These rules should be encouraging creative, self-governing, learning, and efficient working.

Alfes et al. (2013) discovered that there could be a positive impact of formal structure on performance in a stable setup; while in case of an unstable setup, a negative impact is achieved. He also pointed out that the performance control enhances decision-making and enlarges performance's predictability. Wilden et al. (2013) mentioned that performance in a firm is shaped by the organisational structure, which will appreciate good performers. The structure designed in a bad manner will yield poor performance. The structure of an organisation is attached to effectiveness (Hogan and Coote, 2014). They recommended restructuring of management to enhance productivity and efficacy of the firm if it is not meeting standards with the present structure. The structure and norms of an organisation should help to create a working environment which is conducive for good performance.

Karahanna and Preston (2013) have suggested that the firm must facilitate the growth of cultural norms, traditions, and values to achieve desired goals and behaviours. Alegre and Chiva (2013) observed, higher degrees of job satisfaction in decentralized firms having distributed control. A recent research work by Argyris (2017) mentioned that ambiguity of worker is decreased by good organisational structure, which assists in effective communication. Bellé (2013) explained that streamlining of information is necessary for accomplishment of a firm's targets and employees should be avoided to provide too much unnecessary information or too little information that does not meet the purpose.

Shields et al (2015) and Anderson and Eshima (2013) have found that leadership, interaction, and organisational structure influence efficiency and effectiveness of performance. The quick completion of procedures and happy willingness of every member are good indications of a performing firm.

3.3.2 Technological Factors

Innovative technologies have circumscribed almost all fields of the present world and gradually automatizing various processes of services provided and the businesses. Healthcare sector has also accepted many technologies in routine working while the equipment and machines have been totally changed. Consequently, the work of doctors and other employees

has not only been eased a lot but also causing a significant time-saving. The communication among employees and managers as well as other stakeholders have become not only very rapid but also effective due to the use of computers, smart mobiles, and online systems which was previously done through paperwork, typewriters, and photocopy machines. A manager of a hospital may check performance and communication of his subordinates even from far flanged place. An employee can be asked to reach hospital immediately using phone in case of an emergency. Conveying orders and urgent assignments and having feedback have become so quick.

The health services are affected by numerous factors related to diversity of technologies like complex machines and equipment, software programmes and tools, and techniques of internet (Al Bento and Regina Banto, 2006). DeLeon and McLean (1992) proposed a success model on Health Information System (HIS) implementation and adoption. His model indicated that Technological Factors have three broad dimensions: system quality, information quality, and service quality. There are many special features and challenges which are prone only to the health care sector and modern technology can help to cope with these problems (Blass et al., 2017; Ginter, 2018). Therefore, how modern technology can explore a distinct role in performance management of health care sector is highlighted as under.

3.3.2.1 Information Technology (IT) or Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and its impact on the performance of employees as well as PMS

The IT stands for Information Technology while ICT is an abbreviation of Information and Communication Technologies. Both referring to technologies of telecommunications consisting of Internet, wireless networks, and cell phones (TechTerms, 2018). It includes several technologies, such as mobile technology; email; two-way instant messaging; blogs; web pages; online shopping systems; downloading of images, audios, and videos (IGIGlobal, 2018). The IT or ICT is the most important technological help for performance of employees and the performance system of hospitals. Information technology (IT) is defined by different authors in many ways. Jackson et al. (2010, p. 240) reproduced the conceptualized definition by ITAA (Information Technology Association of America) as “the design, development, implementation, and management of computer-based information systems, particularly software applications and computer hardware”. According to Rezaei et al. (2014), the information technology processes, stores and transmits the information in an electronic format. They further explained that for processing information, physical equipment in the form of

computers, fax machines, and network tools, is used by organisations to create data and knowledge. Strohmeier (2013) was of the view that information technology produces and collects information and hence making the data available and accessible to anyone from everywhere. Many other researchers also contributed in this area to explain the version of information technology and its possible impacts. Eppler and Mengis (2003) elaborated that amount of information has been increased by the development of information technology. This view is consistent with the statement of Bawden and Robinson (2008) who stated that quick access to information became possible due to the new technology in the field of information. Filippov and Lastrebov (2010) agreed with Eppler and Mengis (2003), and Bawden and Robinson (2008) and stated that access to information has been increased due to information technology.

Information technology involves utilizing the information, spreading awareness and improving accessibility. European Commission (2007) explained that IT-based firms set global benchmarks in quality by strengthening the overall framework and adopting standards and best practices. The role of health information and communications technology in healthcare services has been widely acknowledged.

An efficient IT/ICT can impact the performance management of any organisation significantly because of more efficiency, time-saving, rapidity of two-way communication, and immediate problem-solving. Sebastian and Korrapati (2007) are of the view that losses may occur due to ineffective or inappropriate information technology. Song et al. (2006) stated that organisational capacity is increased due to the fast arrival of information through development of many technological applications. Grover and Crooker (1995) also found that information technology has strong impact on performance. There is almost a consensus that human society has evolved into an era of knowledge by the advancement in information technology that puts positive impacts on developing better performance system, definitely (Zhang, 2008).

It is now simplified and become very easy to access the information and spreading quickly. (Paghaleh, et al., 2011; Whelan and Teigland, 2010). This is also evident from the research of Fernandez et al., (2004), who have found that information technology acts as a catalyst in the improvement of organisation's performance. This statement is further validated by Suzana (2010), who verified a strong relationship between IT and organisation's performance.

Organisation's performance is affected by IT through different mechanisms. It affects management, communication, functioning, and overall structuring of an organisation and this

effect is quite significant that gives new patterns of work and put a significant effect on roles and responsibilities of the individuals working in the organisation (Edward et al., 1991). A few other researchers have emphasized the impact of information technology by focusing on its contribution in the field of organisational architecture and design that are considered the key elements which shape the organisation (Gerstein et al., 1992).

Information technology can impact not only on the organisation's performance but also on performance management system. The IT is based on learning, information processes, and technology advancement which is also considered a core foundation of PMS (Angelita et al., 2014). They are of the view that some organisations hire very professional and qualified top executives who act as the champions of performance management systems. They make their organisations successful at record level by benefiting from information systems such as Supply chain management (SCM), Customer relationship management (CRM) and Enterprise resource planning (ERP). Thus, IT-supported performance management system helps to enhance organisational communication (Patricia et al, 2014).

The organisations can be supported by IT system in many ways; aligns systems for obtaining desirable behaviours, acts as a catalyst in skills development, and provides a system where everyone must be accountable for his/her action in the organisation. Very prominent studies (Bharadwaj, 2000; Melville, 2004; Gu and Jung, 2013) validated the role of integration between information technology capabilities and other organisational capabilities. Authors have put an emphasis on the importance of aligning information technology objectives with organisational objectives (Feeny and Willcocks, 1998; Ness, 2005; Aversano et al., 2012). Research work considering the impact of human IT on personnel's behaviour, experience of using tools, and their interest to learn new tools have favoured IT-based performance management (Strong, 2002; Abugabah et al., 2009; Bradley, 2009). Even in measuring organisational performance, information technology can play an important role

3.3.2.2 The business value of Information Technology/ Information and Communication Technology

Any new technology to be implemented in an organisation must have business value as well. IT/ICT technologies have significant business values as well, because Melville et al. (2004) found that IT helps industries in capturing a substantive amount of values from their businesses. Information technology system enables firms to transform businesses and helps them getting competitiveness by improving their efficiency and productivity and making them cost-

effective. Therefore, large number of organisations are implementing information technology (IT) in their HR activities to enhance their efficacy (Van Dooren et al., 2015). Information technology assists in measuring and administering employee performance (Briscoe and Claus, 2008). It also assists in automating HR process, and thus results in saving a lot of cost and time and reducing human effort of doing work manually. A survey showed that more than 30% of respondent firms are planning to implement or are already using software for automation of performance management process (Hunter and Nielsen, 2013). With regards to business, value of information technology investment is very much acknowledged and accepted within the context of goods and services. Hitt and Brynjolfsson (1996), are of the view that internal strengths of the organisation should be assessed based on the resources. Several studies have identified the firm's information system and its information technology capacities as an important resource for bringing the competitive advantages (Bharadwaj, 2000; Rivard et al., 2004). Firms' performance is used and considered when the subject of information technology is put under consideration (Breznik 2012; Gu and Jung, 2013). The research studies of Bharadwaj (2000), Devaraj and Kohli (2003), Mithas et al. (2011 and 2012), and Melville et al. (2004) have used profit, cost reduction and productivity, while some other studies based the value used competitive position or market share to measure organisational level performance (Mata et al., 1995; Hitt and Brynjolfsson, 1996; Dehning and Richardson, 2002; Agan, 2011; Ceccobelli et al., 2012). Melville et al., (2004) used firm efficiency or firm effectiveness as an alternative to firm performance. They used firm efficiency within the context of cost reduction and productivity enhancement and achievement of objectives by attaining competitive advantages.

Some other studies have discussed intermediate process level and organisation-wide level within the context of information technology business value and its related impacts to measure the overall performance. Most prominent of them are Melville et al. (2004), Addas and Pinsonneault (2007), and Gu and Jung (2013). Some studies (Abugabah et al., 2009; Gu and Jung, 2013) have focused on explicit inclusion of product and service quality as a measure of performance. These measures are used to evaluate firm performance.

3.3.2.3 Information Technology/Information and Communication Technology for Performance Appraisal and Other Relevant Areas

The appraisal of the performance of employees is highly important in a performance management system. For performance appraisal management, firms are involving various

types of software for automation of performance management such as Talent Management Software (TMS) and Workforce Performance Management (WPM) systems. This software is helpful in recording data about performance of employee systematically, pre-determined goals and achieving outcomes, compensation, and various other HR-related concerns. Filling of various forms can be done online which will then be submitted to HR. Information achieved from forms is stored automatically as metrics where performance of current work can be contrasted with the standards and the targets. This automated software also assists in analyzing the training requirements of workers, automatically monitor their performance and their feedback, and enhancement required in performances (Poister et al., 2013).

Information technology has changed the monitoring system of performance from manual to electronic and continuously facilitating process of feedback by using many online software packages (Fletcher, 2001; Selden et al, 2001; Spinks et al, 1999). Some technology businesses such as Capterra.com (2015) are playing a role in providing software like performance appraisal software (PAS) that helps them in getting good results on performance management system which also tells them about the performance of individuals and team, and how they can improve the performance. These technology businesses provide a lot of web-based or installable products that can be used in performance appraisal system to improve the appraisal process significantly by cutting down extra labor and using automation that can help to achieve accurate, reliable, unbiased, and faster appraisal. These are also very helpful in saving the time that can be used somewhere else to deliver corporate targets and getting competitive advantages (Anderson et al., 1999). Some matured economies such as United States are the examples that are evidence of the key role of emerging information technology on performance appraisal (Chopra, 2014; Dobbs et al., 2015). It is important to communicate effectively for an organisation to achieve success. The most significant privilege of IT is its capacity of streamlining communication both externally and internally (O'Connell and O'Sullivan, 2014). According to Pulakos et al. (2015), one of the core privileges of Information Technology is its capacity to improve competitive advantage of an organisation in the marketplace, by supporting transfer of knowledge and strategic thinking. Accessing and influencing subscription databases and social networks, for example, resulted in providing organisations with the capacity to create, interpret and, convey information like that could be never in the past. Hence, businesses are provided with unmatched access to consumers, resulting firms to deliver enhanced products and services to their consumers. Organisations are

provided with tools which are required by them to assess patients and to incorporate techniques which are required for a competitive edge.

Information Technology can support Information management by storing, preserving, and maintaining data. It is required for a business to store and safeguard sensitive information of customers for longer periods, IT enables organisation with the capacity to save, share, and backup information to use later along with protection of data from unauthorized personnel (Vukšić et al., 2013). Sun and Van Ryzin, (2014) stated that organisations may find an implementation of IT expensive, however, in the long run, it becomes extremely cost-effective. by minimizing costs and time required by employees to do paperwork. It can be said that IT enables organisations to do more in less time, without compromising on value or quality.

Due to globalization, the ways of doing businesses have made the companies to focus on their core and essential capabilities by moving their trend towards outsourcing (Doh, 2005; Espino-Rodriguez and Padron-Robaina, 2006; Mol et al., 2005). For outsourcing, Tompkins et al., (2006) have recommended relationship management as a key factor that can help in successful outsourcing. According to Wang et al. (2006), management of the inter-organisational business has been facilitated by information technology that especially plays a role among supply chain members across borders. A very famous example can be given from computer industry i.e. Dell computer has been successful in employing information technology in its global operations through integration of value chain among suppliers, distributors, and customers. Dell has left a good example in global information technology industry by harvesting production efficiencies to improve speed and flexibility (Joan, 1998).

3.3.3 Human Resource Factors:

Human resource comprises of the individuals working in an organisation and playing a role to contribute to achievement of the goals and objectives of the organisation through their activities and consequent success. For the success of any organisation, it is very important to employ right people on correct positions. Armstrong (2009) considers core staff as the backbone of any organisation that can put the organisation on the track of success. Managing human resources requires a strategic, integrated, and coherent approach that also contributes to the development and well-being of people inside the organisation. By utilizing its human resource appropriately, the organisation can improve organisational effectiveness and capacity that makes it successful and competitive among its rivals (Rapert et al., 2002). Mustafa (2013) explained that performance management by the organisation has a direct relationship with

performance of employees. Achieving a better performance of employees means fulfilling organisations goals. Human Resource factors include growth of employees' motivations and skills, extension in skill base, training and development, extension in employees' responsibilities, continuous development of process of performance management, implementation of reward management system, and development of employees' relation strategies which help in enhancing performance (Sablynski, 2012). Studies have found that commitment plays an important role to achieve organisational performance (Powley and Nissen, 2012).

3.3.3.1 Employees' Commitment and Performance Management:

Managing human resources strategically helps in achieving competitive advantages and adds value to the firm (Boxall et al., 2002). Some researchers such as Noe et al. (2007), Bernardin and Wiatrowski (2013) and Mitchell et al. (2013) are of the view that attitudes, behaviours, and performance of employees is influenced by human resource management. The practices of human resource planning, training and development, performance management, and recruitment are the most effective, which positively affect organisational performance. Earlier, Pfeffer (1998) also agreed that reshaping human resource practices contributes to enhancing organisational performance and helps in gaining competitive advantages. Purcell et al. (2003) elaborated that despite hiring eleven thousand personnel, Kenya is still facing a lot of challenges in power sector that emphasizes the need of improved performance in addition to increase in human capital for the better companies' performance. This study largely contributed to analyzing the role of human resource in achieving business targets. Similarly, Alikhani, Fadavi, and Mohseninia (2014) and Biljana (2004) analysed the impact on labor efficiency by using the high commitment strategy or a control strategy. He found that firms having higher levels of productivity and quality were those practicing higher commitment strategy. Purcell et al. (2003) used the data of 12 companies and found that managing people significantly impact organisational performance. Implementation of human resource policies and practices by line managers is considered very important in developing a link between people management and business performance. The significant impact of human resources on performance has also been proved by Arthur (1990, 1992, and 1994) as well as Birasnav (2014) and Bloom et al. (2015) who focused on the direct relationship between commitment and performance.

Huselid (1995) came up with the results that employee motivation affects productivity while employee skills and organisational structure affects financial performance. Patterson et al.

(1997) argued that a significant variation in profitability and productivity is explained by human resource practices. Human resource contributes significantly to achieving a competitive advantage, having good performance and adding values to the firm (Camilleri 2002; Real et al., 2014). Studies of Rahimnia et al. (2005), Jackson et al. (2014), and Rees and Smith, (2017) indicated that hiring of skilled human resources and subsequent development pays back as increased performance of organisations and achieving assignments. The launching of controlling, evaluation, and training programs for employees can add high values to very high performance of various businesses. The performing human resource is an asset of a company and considered as a strong indicator of performance.

Commitment has been referred as performing the tasks by employees with full zeal and zest (Igella, 2014), the employees' psychological attachment with their organisation to achieve organisational goals that also make them ready to accept the challenges (Dolan, Tzafir, and Baruch, 2005; Dixit and Bhati, 2012, Gelaidan and Ahmad, 2013). It is also very important to create commitment among employees for the achievement of strategic goals (Brisco and Claus, 2008; Fugate, et al., 2009). Guest, et al., (2000b) has found that there is an association between use of human resource practices and a higher level of commitment that contributes largely in enhancing productivity and quality of services (Safarzadeh et al., 2011). The health care management is a discipline where the performance is managed on numerous objectives and it has quite large stakeholders. Here too, the organisational and employees' performance could be improved with the help of employees' commitment, training, and development (Gerrish, 2016; Rees and Smith, 2017; Rothwell, Hohne and King, 2018).

It is very important to create commitment among employees of a firm (Brisco and Claus, 2008; Fugate et al., 2009) because the employees having more commitment are likely to have more willingness to accept the change and less willingness to withdrawal behaviour (Lo et al., 2009). Zheng et al (2010) have analysed that appreciable consequences are expected from the committed individuals who are considered the main source of life of organisation. Meyer and Allen, (1991) and Nguyen, Mai, and Nguyen (2014) have found that commitment is a binding force that helps individuals to stick with the targets and provides a way to reach the target. The individual can experience this binding force by exercising their attachment and involvement with the target (McFarlin and Sweeney, 1992). Commitment is considered as the requisite capability to enhance the output and to obtain sustainable competitive advantages (Ali et al, 2010; Meyer and Allen, 1997).

Employees' commitment is a core factor in organisational performance. According to Hunjra et al. (2010), the highly committed employees are considered a primary, intellectual, and an important asset for any organisation because they take part in organisational tasks by contributing their time and energy for the attainment of organisational goals (Akintayo, 2010; Sarker and Afroze, 2014; Tumwesigye, 2010). Hence, organisations need to identify those aspects which may increase employees' commitment for their firms (Schwarzwald et al., 1992). A highly committed employees performs his jobs so nicely and successfully which even his managers may not expect at all (Sourchi, and Liao (2015). A high output and sustainable competitive advantages can only be obtained if the commitment of the employee is of extremely high level because there is a direct relationship between performance of an organisation and commitment level of employees (Rebecca, Obeidat, and Bray, 2013). Leadership style and retention rate have been considered by some studies in determining employees' commitment (Freyermuth, 2007; Vandenberghe and Bentein, 2009).

The employees having lesser commitment to their organisation could direct their commitment towards non-productive activities (Ajila and Awonusi, 2004). The commitments may be of various nature including job, attitudes, action, and people and leadership of the organisation. This consideration is consistent with the statement of some other authors too (Becker, 1992; Vandenberghe, 2009). Managers should be able to know that who are the best-committed employees and strong determinant of performance.

According to Cohen (2003), the higher productivity and enhanced performance is possible through higher level of commitment by employees in the organisation due to career commitment, work commitment and organisational commitment (Avolio et al., 2004; Lo, 2009; Ponnu and Chuah, 2010; Sohail et al., 2011; Rajendran and Raduan, 2005). Bin et al. (2011), Brown, et al. (2011), and Shastri et al, (2010) are of the view that higher commitment of employees results in increasing the job satisfaction of employees. In turn, better job performance, good productivity, and more sales turnover less intention to leave and absenting from duty.

Regarding the satisfaction level of employees, Chinomona et al. (2015) have found that higher level of commitment gives higher level of satisfaction. Zahedi et al., (2015) and Lee et al. (2015) have found a significant relationship between social reliance and organisational commitment. They have also found a relationship between leadership and organisational commitment that eventually cause performance. Finally, Abraham (2015) is of the view that if

reasonable working practices are provided to employees, their performance will increase that in turn will also improve the performance of the organisation.

3.3.3.6 Well-being of the Committed Employees

There must be relevance of outcomes of commitment with the target of the organisation. Many studies (Joo, 2017; Lee and Steers, 2017; Lam, O'Donnell and Robertson, 2015) have addressed the implications of commitment but a few studies have mentioned the relevancy of commitments with employee well-being. The well-being of employees is a more complex phenomenon than the commitment itself. Some researchers have analysed the relationship between commitment and employees' well-being (Siu, 2002). The employees' commitment is for better understanding of the concepts (Subramaniam and Mia, 2001) because there is an association between use of human resource practices and higher level of commitment that contributes largely in enhancing productivity and quality of services.

3.3.4 Role of training and development in performance management:

The innovative technologies are changing rapidly the machinery and equipment being used in hospitals for various treatment and operations as well as using the performance system. Accordingly, fresh training of employees is also required to make them well-versed of these dynamisms. Therefore, training should be adopted as a regular feature in various organisations to run with the present technology-driven world. In current competitive business world, training is a significant factor of workforce performance because it helps in increasing the skills, know-how, efficiency as well as effectiveness of employees and the whole organisation (Dhar, 2015). Aragón et al. (2014) stated that there is a significant impact of different factors on performance of employees, but among the most important factor is the training. Those employees generally perform better, who have more job experience, because of increased skills and competencies (Shastric et al., 2010). Hence, the management is required to provide training opportunities equally to all employees to the high performers, particularly. According to Elnaga and Imran (2013), cost of employees training pays to the organisation as high performance. Hence, organisation should consider trainings as investment.

There is a dependence of organisational performance on the individual performance of each employee, and human resource capital is one of the most important elements for company's growth and performance. Hence, for improving performance of employees as well as whole organisation, the management provides training to its employees for better performance

through professional development. It has been argued by Elnaga and Imran (2013) that training and development is an important activity for increasing the performance of companies operating in health sector. Moreover, Mitchell et al. (2013) claimed that improved performance of employees is viewed as a building block that assists in increasing performance of overall company. The performance of employees depends on various factors such as job satisfaction and knowledge management, but there is a stronger relationship between training and employees' performance (Banes, 2011). It clearly depicts that performance of employees is significant for improving overall performance of organisation and training and development is highly beneficial for improving performance of each employee (Baumeister and Leary, 1995).

Human resource management is considered as a backbone of every company being one of the most important assets by creating a good working environment, and assuring good performance (Chaplan, 2017). So, because of this belief, management of companies invest in their human resource capital, due to expected ultimate result in improving performance of whole company (Ford, 2014). Druskat et al. (2013) considered performance as a major construct that has various dimensions and its main aim is achieving outcomes and has a significant relationship with strategic aims of a company. For achieving the key goals of an organisation, it is important for the management to focus on improving performance of each employee for increasing effectiveness as well as efficiency of the company.

3.3.4.1 Appropriate Designing and Delivery of training

The effectiveness of training and development depends on the careful designing of training and its delivery. It is important for the management to design training in accordance with needs and requirements of employees and deliver it to deserving individuals who can be useful ultimately for the company. Kunze et al. (2013) argued that companies focusing on designing good training in accordance with companies' as well as employees' needs get better outcomes than other organisations. In case of having bad training design, management only wastes time as well as financial resources. There are different types of training that can be provided to employees for improving their performance. On- the- job training assists employees in getting knowledge about the job in a better way. Individuals usually get learning from their practical experiences in a better way in comparison to getting bookish knowledge (Vandenberghe and Bentein, 2009). Through providing on-the-job training to employees, cost and time can be reduced.

According to Real et al. (2014), delivery style is also one of the significant factors affecting the success of the training and development program. Employees show much consciousness regarding delivery style. If training is not delivered in an impressive way and audience' attention is not captured properly by the trainer, then this only results in wastage of time and resources. For ensuring high performance of employees as an outcome of training, it is very important for a trainer to ensure increased involvement of audience at the time of giving training (Dalton, 2000). There is much importance of delivery style in training and development activity. The management of an organisation is required to provide on the job training facilities to its employees for making them capable of learning in a practical way.

It has been argued by Shaw et al. (2013) that an employee usually feels much difficulty in performing well at the job place without getting pre-training about his or her job roles. Trained workers usually perform better than untrained employees, so it is highly important for a company to provide training opportunities to employees for achieving organisational goals in a better way. Saks and Burke-Smalley (2014) argued that training and development strategy proved to be costly for any type of organisation, but it provides several benefits in the long run. It is important for an organisation to develop its employees in accordance with the needs of dynamic business world so that it can compete with competitors in a better way.

3.3.4.2 Training Models and Approaches for Linking HR Practices with Outcomes

There are various models in which training and its organisational outcomes have been highlighted. The two key theoretical models about training and its effect on organisational performance are Resource-Based View and Behavioural Perspective View (Alfes et al, 2013). In accordance with Resource-Based View, an organisation can get a competitive advantage through the resources available within the firm. An organisation can get value effectively and efficiently utilizing its internal resources. Those resources can add value to the firm that is unique, not imitable and non-substitutable by its competitors. In accordance with this view, human resource is the most important resource through which an organisation can gain competitive advantage. It is important that management adopts those human resource practices through which skilled and competent employees can be developed, hence those employees can serve as a resource for adding value to the firm (Lin and Wu, 2014). It has been argued that while applying Resource-based view to training, it is suggested that training of employees can prove an investment on human resource. Moreover, it also ensures the performance of business

activities needed for achieving organisational objectives, thus have overall positive effect on performance of organisation (Somsuk and Laosirihongthong, 2014).

As per the Behavioural Perspective, the major focus is on employee role behaviour. It is claimed that employee role behaviour mediates in between the relationship of strategy and organisational performance. It is important that behaviours needed by strategy of an organisation is elicited and reinforced through human resources practices (Zhu, 2012). It is important to identify the most effective human resource practices through which desired role behaviours can be elicited. Then, the desired role behaviours must result in positive organisational outcomes. While applying behavioural perspective to training, it is suggested that positive organisational performance can result through training, as it helps in boosting those behaviours of employees that have best match with strategy of organisation (Arboleda, 2011; Wiengarten et al, 2013).

There are alternative approaches for linking HR practices with outcomes at an organisational level. These are usually termed as universalistic, configurational and contingency approaches. With the help of these approaches, various kinds of links between training and outcomes at organisational level can be explained in a better way (Xu et al., 2014). The most basic approach to HR practices is universalistic approach, because of which it has been claimed by various researches that there are some better staff management practices than others. Brewster (2017) identified link between selection of employees, their training, and productivity. Moreover, it was argued by Bratton and Gold (2017) that those organisations get success in improving productivity, in which formal training programs are implemented.

According to supporters of contingent perspective, it is claimed that there is an increased dependence of training policies and objectives on strategic orientation followed by each organisation (Schuler, and Jackson, 1987). This view has also been shared by some other authors (Bamberger et al, 2014) who claimed that there is high effectiveness of extensive formal training when used jointly with some organisational strategies. As per configurational perspective, different HR practice types can be used for materializing HR systems with better organisational performance. With respect to training, it is suggested by the configurational perspective that can help in enhancing organisational effectiveness if exploited in conjunction with other HR practices. Moreover, they must be used along with using promotion from within internal workforce markets, adopting performance contingent systems of incentives, and bonuses (Jackson et al, 2014).

3.5 The Summary of the Review of Literature and Identification of Gaps to be Addressed by the Present Study

Performance management has been investigated by academic researchers for many years. Its implementation and implications are quite diverse along with many challenges in different industries (Metcalf, 2017). Siegfried et al. (2018) have highlighted that performance management's implementation varies in different industries and there are always certain contextual factors which are specific to every industry and sector. However, as identified by Blass et al. (2017), health care sector is one of the underexplored sectors in context of performance management system. Therefore, this needs further exploration and investigations.

As mentioned by Ginter (2018), health care sector all over the world strives for resource allocation for achieving the best possible outcomes for patients and populations and with designing such performance management systems which most are more creative and effective for the organisation. A similar situation is also encountered in the health care sector of Pakistan, which is a developing country. For becoming successful in the uncertain and ambiguous environment of health care sector, organisations must opt accelerated pace of changes; continuous change in nature of work, rapid changes in technology, and changing workforce dynamics. In this situation, these organisations need such performance management systems which are engaging, meaningful, continuous, and dynamic. Such developments are also needed in Pakistan (Alves, Vieira and Ribeiro, 2017).

Due to these reasons, Fitzgerald et al. (2017) have invited more research studies in proliferation and propagation of breakthrough of performance management theories. Inter-disciplinary performance management research is another aspect that needs further exploration to know how its application can help organisations to improve their performance. After reviewing 100 years of research in this field, DeNisi and Murphy (2017) have also pointed that there is a need for more studies from different industries and contexts because these could help in coming to agreements.

Most of the earlier studies (Abugabah et al., 2009; Aversano et al., 2012; Bradley, 2009; Bharadwaj, 2000; Chopra et al., 2007; Dobbs et al, 2015; Fletcher, 2001; Feeny and Willcocks, 1998; Melville et al., 2004; Ness, 2005; Slater et al., 2010; Strong, 2002; Subramaniam et al, 2002; Wilden et al., 2013) have been taken in the western world where relatively more advanced technologies have already penetrated in the performance system while in Pakistan these are still in initial stages. So, only a few studies (like Ali et al, 2010) have been undertaken

to evaluate the newly established Performance Management System. Hence, systematic investigations involving all the three factors; organisational structure, information technology and human resources in the selected hospitals may provide solid grounds for further investigations under the scenario of Pakistan. The variation in results of different studies also provides a strong justification to conduct a comprehensive research to find out the actual impact of these factors within the context of organisational performance.

It has been observed in earlier discussions that organisational structure has a positive and significant impact on organisational performance (Jones, 2013; Slater et al., 2010; Wilden et al., 2013; Subramaniam et al., 2002). Similarly, information technology plays a great role in predicting organisational performance (Bharadwaj, 2000; Melville, 2004; Gu and Jung, 2013; Feeny and Willcocks, 1998; Ness, 2005; Aversano et al., 2012). Employees' commitment is another factor in favour of which evidence from literature have also been recorded (Lo, 2009; Zheng et al, 2010; Ajila and Awonusi, 2004; Ali et al, 2010; Akintayo, 2010). Likewise, training and development can also find link with the organisational performance (Ubeda-García et al., 2013; Phillips, 2012). Despite great support in favour of organisational structure, information technology, training and development and employees' commitment and their impact on organisational performance, there are few studies as well which disagree with the impact of these factors on organisational performance and on the strength of the relationship. This reveals further need to investigate these factors under total variable conditions of Pakistan.

The main purpose of the present research is to investigate the performance management system using the data from Hospitals more specifically from the orthopaedic department. Different variables are used to analyse the performance of employees that could eventually reflect the performance management system. For this purpose, three different areas are considered i.e. organisation structure, technology, and human resource. A further selection has been made to include employees' commitment. Hence, the detail discussion is made on the concept of organisational structure, information technology, training and development and employees' commitment and their impact on organisational performance and then their relationship with performance management system. This study develops, evaluates and recommends changes for performance management system for orthopedic department of health care sector of Sialkot. The present research also used different theories to develop a theoretical background and test the different factors to see their possible impact on performance management system.

3.6 Conceptual Framework and the Relevant Key Themes Emerging from Literature Review

The performance is a variable used to measure the professional behaviours and actions of individuals for achieving organisational goals (Campbell's, 1999) while Jackson et al. (2014) added the fulfillment of economic goals in the concept of performance. There is a link between performance and PMS (Van Dooren, Bouckaert and Halligan (2015) and Shields et al. (2015). The PMS is a commanding framework in appraising and managing employees' performance; pointing out their deficiencies in discharging their duties and encouraging in case of good achievements (Ferron Vilchez and Darnall, 2016); Kerzner and Kerzner, 2017). The PMS motivate employees of a company through performance appraisal, rewarding and awarding to do better work, integrating technology (ICT) with business methodologies, job design, assessment of training needs, and refining their capabilities, which are the operational and strategic needs of an organisation (Lee and Chen, 2013; Lopez et al., 2009). Some performance indicators are used in this regard (WHO, 2010). This helps in directing, monitoring, and enhancing the utilization of human resources but not a tool for forcing employees to work more (Fernandez, 2004). He is of the view that PM helps in highlighting the values and competencies of organisations and helps managers and executives.

Being the backbone of a performing system, performance assessment should be without any biases because unjustifiable appraisal is just like denying attainment of an employee. He must be encouraged and rewarded for good performance to motivate doing further good work. Thus, a strong and effective PMS is required for ensuring the productivity of employees, integration of different methods and tools, further training, getting employees' commitment, effective communication, and strengthening working relationship between employees and their supervisors (Lee and Chen, 2013; Bacal,1999). The parameters like employees' satisfaction and commitment, absenteeism, qualification, and experience, and customer satisfaction might tell about the performance of employees. The appropriate needs of appraisal, the major objective of PMS, could be collecting, assessing, reviewing, and analyzing the data on current and past work, behaviour and performance of employees (Habib et al., 2010; Mathieu and Zajac, 1990).

There could be constraints and barriers in attaining required performance like deficient skills, unsuitable working place environment, lack of communication and social interaction, absence of team leader, too many rules, and poor feedback, which may be identified and controlled by

a good PMS (Clapon, 2019; Deeb, 2019; Thomas, 2018). A uniform rating system is the foundation of a reliable PMS must be adopted for all employees because there should be no contamination in individuals' performance evaluation (Lee et al., 2015; Boxall et al., 2008). The PMS should not find weaknesses, but target growing strengths (Bergeron, 2017). Therefore, healthcare companies must own a world-class performance system in which the relationships of manager and employee could develop engagement of staff to make employees as productive (Ginter, 2018; McCarthy and Allen, 2017).

The factors impacting PMS are very important: the salient ones are organisational structure, information technology, training and employees' commitment. These factors are sometimes classified as Drivers of change (factors causing necessary change) and Barriers to change (preventing changes or Internal and external (Habib et al., 2010; Neely, Mike, and Chris, 2007; Pedersen and Sudzina, 2012), which may influence the development of MS. Internal factors comprise of corporate culture like top management commitment and support, employees' training, rewards policy, organisational strategy and structure, and revising performance criteria (Baird and Schoh, 2012; Johanson et al., 2006; Kennerley and Neely, 2003; Tung, Baird, and Schoch, 2011) whereas the external factors are impacting business performance of a company but are mostly beyond the control of an organisation itself. The examples are IT technology, global competition, and fast changing customer choices (Pedersen and Sudzina, 2012) or variable cultures (Aguinisand Gottfredson, 2012). Some authors (Atkinson, 2012; Kennerley and Neely, 2003) described factors with respect to their relation in a developing PMS: related to processes, related to people, related to skills, related to employee needs, related to culture, and related to systems. However, in the current research the salient factors (organisational structure, information technology, training and employees' commitment) identified by Habib et al. (2010) have been taken to form the conceptual framework of the study. Performance is taken as a dependent variable to investigate the performance management system while various factors are acting as independent variables because they influence the PMS. Just a brief account of each factor and relevant themes are being presented to elaborate the conceptual framework further under the light of research work from the literature resented in the foregoing discussions under various subsections.

The performance is largely affected by structure of an organisation these two are significantly related to each other (Alamsjah, 2011; Siam and Hilman, 2012; Wilden et al., 2013). Findings of these authors revealed a significant and positive relationship. Some other researchers are of the view that organisational structure contributes a lot in the success/failure of organisational

performance (Alashloo et al., 2005; Delisi, 2006; Hrebiniak, 2006; Rahimnia, Castka, and Sharp, 2005). A few more authors (Fernandez, González, and Sabherwal, 2004; O'Malley, 2000) regarded organisational structure as the most effective strategic execution factor in organisational performance because it performs a moderating role in strategic communication (Andrew et al., 2011, Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). The firms use the organisational structure for three purposes; to control work outcomes of employees, the efficient performance of tasks, and achieving the organisational goals (Katsikea et al., 2011). Mechanistic structures involve centralized decision-making following formal rules and procedures whereas organic structures involve de-centralized decision-making and not emphasizing on formal rules and procedures (Lunenburg 2012; Wilden et al., 2013). The allocation of responsibility and authority among the workers and rules and regulation are executed through organisational structure (Teixeria et al., 2012). The structure of an organisation can either be flat or hierarchical, but some companies can adopt a mix of these two (Meehan, 2019). A quick completion of procedures is a good indication of a performing firm Shields et al (2015) and Anderson and Eshima (2013). Considering all these facts, organisational structure has been included in the contractual framework of the current study.

Almost all fields have been encompassed by innovative technologies, the health services are also affected by diversity of technologies like complex machines and equipment, software programmes and tools, and techniques of internet (Al Bento and Regina Banto, 2006) which have gradually automatizing various processes and services provided to patients. The modern equipment and machines have been included in healthcare, consequently, the work of doctors and other employees has not only been eased a lot but also significantly time-saving. The communication and feedback among employees and managers as well as other stakeholders have become very rapid (Blass et al., 2017; Ginter, 2018). The IT is the mostly used technology in hospitals as well which made very easy to access the information and spreading quickly (Paghaleh, et al., 2011; Whelan and Teigland, 2010). Fernandez et al., (2004) narrated that It acts as a catalyst in the improvement of organisation's performance while a strong relationship between IT and organisation's performance has been found (Suzana, 2010). IT impacts through different mechanisms like management, communication, functioning, and giving new patterns of work and roles and responsibilities of the individuals working in the organisation (Gerstein et al., 1992; Edward et al., 1991). IT has been considered a core foundation of PMS (Angelita et al., 2014) by enhancing communication and coordination (Patricia et al, 2014), acting as a catalyst in skills development, and providing a system where everyone must be accountable for

his/her action in the organisation (Bharadwaj, 2000; Melville, 2004; Gu and Jung, 2013), aligning information technology objectives with organisational objectives (Feeny and Willcocks, 1998; Ness, 2005; Aversano et al., 2012). Even in measuring organisational performance, information technology can play an important role (Strong, 2002; Abugabah et al., 2009; Bradley, 2009). Therefore, study of IT role in MS will be art of conceptual framework.

The organisation can improve their effectiveness and capacity to become successful and competitive by appropriate utilization of its human resources (Rapert et al., 2002) by growth of employees' motivations and skills, training and development, extension in employees' responsibilities, refining performance management, implementation of reward management system, and development of employees' relation strategies (Sablynski, 2012). Attaining commitment of employees plays an important role in achieving organisational performance (Powley and Nissen, 2012) and competitive advantages (Boxall et al., 2002). Noe et al. (2007), Bernardin and Wiatrowski (2013) and Mitchell et al. (2013) are of the view that attitudes, behaviours, and performance of employees could be impacted by human resource management for which planning, training and development, performance management, and recruitment are the most effective, which positively affect organisational performance. The significant impact of human resources on performance has also been proved by Arthur (1990, 1992, and 1994) as well as Birasnav (2014) and Bloom et al. (2015) who focused on the direct relationship between commitment and performance. Therefore, creating commitment among employees for the achievement of strategic goals is highly important (Brisco and Claus, 2008; Fugate, et al., 2009). Guest, et al., (2000b) that has an association between use of human resource practices contributing largely in enhancing productivity and quality of services (Safarzadeh et al., 2011). The health care management critically requires commitment of employees which could be improved with the help of training, and development (Gerrish, 2016; Rees and Smith, 2017; Rothwell, Hohne and King, 2018) because the employees having more commitment are likely to have more willingness to work and less willingness to withdrawal (Lo et al., 2009). Appreciable consequences are expected from the committed individuals who are considered the main source of life of organisation (Zheng et al (2010). Moreover, commitment is a binding force that helps individuals to stick to organisation and its targets (Akintayo, 2010; Ali et al., 2010; McFarlin and Sweeney, 1992; Meyer and Allen, 1997; Sarker and Afroze, 2014; Tumwesigye, 2010). Hence, authors (Joo, 2017; Lee and Steers, 2017; Lam, O'Donnell and Robertson, 2015) have emphasised employee well-being. The well-being of employees is a

more complex phenomenon than the commitment itself. Considering contribution of employees' commitment in performance and PMS, this parameter has also been included in the contractual framework.

A fresh training of employees is required to make them well-versed of these dynamisms in innovative technologies, machinery and equipment. Therefore, training must be a regular feature in various organisations to catch the present technology-driven world. A regular training is a significant factor of workforce performance because it helps in increasing the skills, know-how, efficiency as well as effectiveness of employees and the whole organisation (Dhar, 2015). Aragón et al. (2014) regarded the training as the most important factor of PMS. Those employees generally perform better, who have more job experience, because of increased skills and competencies (Shastric et al., 2010). Hence, the management must provide training opportunities equally to all employees to the high performers whereas Elnaga and Imran (2013) mentioned that cost of employees training pays to the organisation as high performance. The training, as a factor of PMS, also became a part of study and the conceptual framework.

The foregoing factors: Organisational structure, Human resources, technology, Commitment of employees, and Training have been made components of the Contractual Framework of the current study. Some more details, including various works of researchers have been presented in figure 3.1 and grid form (Table 3.1 & Figure 3.1), as also has been tabulated by Arnaboldi et al. (2015) in their article.

Table 3.1: The Conceptual Framework comprising of PMS factors and Probable Themes/Key Attributes

PMS and its contributing Factors	Probable Key Themes/ Attributes	Relevant research work of authors	Comments
Assessment and management of employees' performance in PMS	Targets of performance assessment	Individuals performance assessment is an objective of PMS (Janssens and Steyaert, 2009; Khan et al., 2010; Lopez et al., 2009). The employees' achievements pool into targets of the institutions (Habib et al., 2010).	Hence, a PMS can assess the performance of individuals, teams and the organisations.
	Usefulness and effectiveness of the PMS in achieving goals	A direct link between performance and PMS, identifies deficiencies, helps to increase efficiency and integrating technology, and	In fact, the list of advantages is very long including increase of revenue, services (quality and quantity), winning trust of customers, becoming

		achieves organisational goals (Lee and Chen, 2013; Lopez et al. 2009; Shields et al., 2015;).	competitive and renowned, and saving of time and costs.
	Indicators and criteria for assessment	A uniform and reliable rating system using, qualification and experience level, engagement and fulfilling the assigned targets (Boxall et al., 2008; Gorman, 2015; Lee et al., 2015; Strom et al., 2014, Wager et al., 2017)	In actual practice, every organisation has adopted its own criteria, standards and indicators for the assessment of employees.
	Causes of poor performance	Working place environment, motivation, lack of communication, social interaction, absence, too many rules, multitasking, and poor guidance (Clapon, 2019; Deeb, 2019; Thomas, 2018).	In additions to these barriers, the personal interest in duties, poor skill, experience, and training, biasedness, injustice, and lack of appreciation may also add up for poor performance.
	Tackling of poor performance in the CPMS	Mechanisms for tackling poor performance could be improving working atmosphere, enhancing communication and feedback, increasing mentoring and guidance reforming of rules, appreciation of good work, ensuring accurate and unbiased appraisal, and giving punishment to low performers (Camisón and Villar-López, 2014; Dadfar et al., 2013; Shields et al., 2015; Uzkurt et al, 2013).	The biased-free and equation in assessment, appreciation of good work, and accountability of poor performance can ensure getting standard performance of all the employees.
Organisational Structure	Organisational Structure and Performance linkage	Organisation size, flexibility, technology, strategy, culture, learning, and innovation promote performance, effectiveness, high productivity, commitment, and behaviour (Becker et al., 1996; Dalton et al., 1980; Dammen, 2001; Hao et al., 2007; Kessler, 2007; Ledbetter, 2003; Zeffane, 1994).	Such good features of Organisational Structure favour good performance and final outputs.
	Organisational Structural Roles, and Control Rules	Organisational structure helps to specify management and control of positions, roles, and accountability of employees, hierarchical levels, and processes for integration and solving issues (Dadfar et al., 2013; Shields et al., 2015).	Every employee knows his roles and assignments and accountability which must be faced if work is poor or below standard whereas the managers and supervisors become clear how they will be controlling and getting work using human resources.
	Organisational Structure Dimensions	Organisation structure has three dimensions: Formalization (standardization of activities and rules), Centralization (authority of decision making), and Complexity (degree of	Appropriate specifications of roles and rules and good coordination favours better performance whereas centralisation mostly retards

		coordination, communication, and control), as elaborated by Malhotra (2009), Dunham et al. (1994), and Shaemi Barzoki et al. (2013).	performing of professional activities.
Technological Factors	Diverse technologies being used in health services	A diversity of technologies like complex machines and equipment, software programmes and tools, techniques of internet, mobiles, and IT technologies have been implemented in the health services (Al Bento and Regina Banto, 2006; DeLeon and McLean, 1992).	These technologies have changed all or most of the paperwork to online, making it easy and rapid to complete.
	Role of IT on the performance of employees as well as PMS	The information technology creates and collects data and information, processes, stores and transmits in an electronic format using computers, fax machines, and network tools, making the data available and accessible to anyone from everywhere (Bawden and Robinson, 2008; Eppler and Mengis, 2003; Filippov and Lastrebov, 2010; Rezaei et al., 2014; Strohmeier, 2013).	The implementation of IT in health services has revolutionised the sector.
Human Resource Factors	Employees' Commitment and Performance Management	Commitment of employees (performing the tasks with full engagement, zeal and zest and accepting the challenges) helps a lot to achieve organisational goals (Brisco and Claus, 2008; Baruch, 2005; Dolan, Tzafrir, Dixit and Bhati, 2012; Fugate, et al., 2009; Gelaidan and Ahmad, 2013; Igella, 2014).	Organisations having a greater number of committed employees show better performance and are generally successful to achieve their goals.
	Well-being of the Committed Employees	The commitment must be rewarded with well-being of employees which can help further for good performance of an organisation (Joo, 2017; Lee and Steers, 2017; Lam, O'Donnell and Robertson, 2015; Siu, 2002).	If the well-being of employees is cared by organisations, it pays it back by good performance and fulfilling of assignments and objectives.
Training and development in performance management	Linkage of training with performance and outcomes	There is a link between selection of employees, their training, outcome, and productivity. Therefore, completed training must create the desired role behaviours of trainees and result in positive organisational outcomes (Arboleda, 2011; Wiengarten et	The design and content of training must yield the desired outcomes in the interest of the company.

		al, 2013; Xu et al., 2014; Zhu, 2012).	
	Designing and Delivery of training	<p>The cost of employees training pays to the organisation as high performance. Hence, organisation should consider trainings as investment (Elnaga and Imran, 2013).</p> <p>The effectiveness of training and development depends on the careful designing of training and its delivery which must be in accordance with needs and requirements of employees as well as the company and delivered to deserving individuals (Kunze et al., 2013; Real et al. (2014; Vandenberghe and Bentein, 2009).</p>	The trainings to be imparted must be designed appropriately which is matching the needs and requirements of employees and the company for harvesting the full benefits.

Figure 3.1: A Diagrammatic Presentation of Conceptual Framework of PMS

Chapter Four

Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction:

This chapter provides the necessary details about the methods selected to complete the research study, along with a solid rationale for selecting the specific methods. The chosen methods have been explained to a reasonable extent. The statistical processes of data analysis and ethical considerations have also been elaborated. The limitations of the study are highlighted as well. More details are presented in subsequent sections.

4.2 The Research Process:

4.2.1 Theoretical Basis of Research Process

The research process is indeed creation of knowledge on various aspects of nature pertaining to various subjects. A Research philosophy is a system which deals with the beliefs and assumptions pertaining to creation of knowledge (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The individuals' views of the world are important in this regard which is linked closely to how they perceive reality (Burns and Burns 2008). Hence, a research philosophy is broad level trust having relation to conducting research.

4.2.1.1 Research Philosophies

The research disciplines have a very wide range, and accordingly, there could be many types of research philosophy. According to Bajpai (2011), Research Philosophy deals with the source, nature, and development of knowledge. He has identified four main research philosophies: Pragmatism, Positivism, Realism, and Interpretivism (also called Interpretive) in business studies. Saunders, Philip, and Thornhill (2012) agreed as well to these four classes and they presented the whole research process in their famous model called 'Onion Model' placing Research Philosophy in the outer most layer (Figure 4.1). However, in contrast, Andrew et al. (2011) have maintained three categories (Positivism, Constructivism, and Pragmatism). According to them, Positivism Philosophy advocates that knowledge is generated in a scientific method while Constructivism forwards argument that knowledge is constructed by scientists. Constructivism concept of research philosophy claims that reality is constructed through human intelligence when interacting with different experiences and is perceived to be

subjective. Thus, the present research study is also an effort to add knowledge into the huge store of the world and in a way covered under the concept of Constructivism. Pragmatism is just a mixture of both philosophical theories; Positivism, and Constructivism.

Another author, Neuman (2014), also made three broad philosophies of social research but named these differently: Positivist (Positivism), Interpretive (interpretivism) and Critical Social (The mixture).

4.2.1.2 Research Paradigm

Cavana, Delahaye, and Sekaran (2001) explained that how does an individual view the world is called 'Paradigm', and a research paradigm can be a set of common beliefs and assumptions that are agreed between scientists on how problems should be understood and solved. Dash (2005), has established a relationship between Research Philosophies, Research Approaches and Research Methods (Table 4.1). Cavana, Delahaye, and Sekaran (2001) explained that the way an individual view the world is called 'Paradigm', and a research paradigm can be a set of common beliefs and assumptions that are agreed between scientists on how problems should be understood and solved. Choy (2014) explained that research paradigms can be characterized through Ontology (what is reality?), Epistemology (How do you know something?), and Methodology (How do you go about finding it out?). Cooper, Schindler, and Sun (2006) indicated the relationship between above characters of paradigms through the following model.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Cooper, D.R., Schindler, P.S. and Sun, J., (2006). *Business research methods* (Vol. 9). New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin.

There is another concept, the Axiology which is the theory of values as in ethics, aesthetic or religion (Lee and Lings, 2008). Some more explanations of Ontology, Epistemology, and Axiology in research are presented as under.

4.2.1.2.1 Ontology

Ontology relates to the nature of reality that researchers investigate, whether it has the existence or is the product of one's mind (Carr, 1994). It merely answers "what" questions by examining the similarities and differences between existing entities and exploring relationships between the objects that exist. Though it determines reality in its purest form, it can only be interpreted through senses or experiences of individuals (Churchill Jr, 1979). Therefore, everyone has its own perspective of reality which ontology helps in representing and reasoning with a body of knowledge. Two main approaches usually dominate the ontological domain; objectivism and constructivism. Objectivism assumes that social entities exist in reality external to social actors concerned with their existence (Collis and Hussey, 2013). In other words, researchers view the world through a 'one-way mirror' where the data and analysis is relatively value free and so the observation process has no effect on the data.

However, an objectivist approach is relatively inappropriate when investigating a social science phenomenon which involves humans and their perceptions and experiences (Creswell, 2003). As the present study analyses performance management system, therefore, constructivist ontological approach was considered relevant. Constructivism presumes that social phenomenon is created from perceptions and consequent actions of the social actors where truth or reality is a belief system held in a context (Creswell and Clark, 2007). As explained by Collis and Hussey (2013), it also views reality as multiple realities where values and ideologies of social actors are inquired. As the study focuses on constructing reality depending upon interactions between the interviewer and respondents, therefore, the study follows constructivism approach to ontology. This helped in analysing the perceptions and experiences of the respondents by actively participating in the process of field work while looking at multiple realities at a time. Additionally, the research gap identified earlier (Section 3.5) asserts that there is a need of more qualitative research. This also supports the constructivist ontological perspective which facilitated in gathering detailed information from the desired participants while analysing multiple realities during the research process. According to Creswell (2003), identification of ontology at the start of the research process is significantly important because it determines the choice of the research design that will further be followed.

4.2.1.2.2 Epistemology

The second assumption, epistemology, concerns the study of the nature of knowledge i.e. how is it possible to gain knowledge of the world and focuses on the nature, validity and limits of

inquiry (Creswell and Clark, 2007). Epistemological philosophy assumes two domains as well; positivism and interpretivism. The positivist philosophy assumes a more objective approach adhering to the view that research findings are usually observable and quantifiable. Researchers are usually independent of the research process where human interaction is minimized (Creswell, Fetters and Ivankova, 2004).

4.2.1.2.3 Axiology

The branch of philosophy studying the values is called Axiology (Saunders, Philip, and Thornhill, 2012), especially the role of researcher's own value in different stages of his research study (Li, 2016). Axiology primarily addresses the aims and objectives of a research work clarifying what the researcher is trying to explain, predict or understand (Lee and Lings, 2008). In simple words, axiology is focusing what value is being considered as important for him in conducting of the research and the research findings. The Axiology elaborates relevant methods of data collection in qualitative research (Carnaghan, 2013), as in the present study as well as emphasizes ethical aspects (Saunders, Philip, and Thornhill (2012).

4.2.1.3 The Relevant Philosophy for the Current Study

The relevance of positivist philosophy is the least for the current study because it is based more on facts and considers the world to be objective (Creswell,1998). As the scope of the study requires more interaction with the respondents to determine the current performance management system in health care sector, positivist approach is inappropriate due to its objective and quantifiable nature. Because the Constructivism philosophy argues that knowledge is constructed by scientists (Andrew et al., 2011), it has more relevancy to the current study, therefore, it is applicable in the present situation. Hence, the present study followed interpretive approach which is accompanied by constructivist ontological perspective.

Interpretivist philosophy comes from the phenomenological paradigm understanding the social world while associating meaning to our interactions (Flick, 2015), basically focusing on interactions of human beings and the way meanings are associated to these interactions. The relevance of interpretive approach for this study can be explained taking support of the view of Greener (2008) who defined performance management as an interpretive approach which relies mainly on naturalistic methods of data collection; such as interviews so that adequate information is gathered to attach meaning to reality. Moreover, according to Hair (2007), the desired information from the interpretivist philosophy depends upon the perceptions of people

of what they think is right or wrong, the kind of problems they are confronted with and how they deal with them. It will facilitate understanding of the social processes involved to gather the meanings people attach to social phenomenon, which will not be possible otherwise. Therefore, interpretivist philosophy is considered suitable for the study as the perceptions of managers and employees are to be gathered and their experiences regarding the aspect of performance management in health care sector of Pakistan.

4.2.1.4 Philosophical Theory selected for the Current Research

This interpretivism philosophy is selected for the current study because has a more practical orientation and is opposite to the instrumental view of positivism which provides a subjective view of the world where individuals' interactions are interpreted as distinctive and unique (Jensen, 2013). In the positivist approach, the researcher is independent in data collection process (Mackey and Gass, 2013), because of this, the positivist approach was not suitable for this study, because of gathering the information about performance management from health care sector through interviews. This may not be required or possible to ask each respondent the same question in the same manner as their nature of duty and responsibilities were different. while the aim of the investigation was to understand multiple interpretations and perceptions of the participants. There are multiple realities of the performance management in different contexts and the same institutions or human actions are likely to have different meanings for different people being studied by the researcher (Hair, 2015; McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015). The respondents' perceptions were based on their experiences and subjective opinions, hence, allowing understanding performance management from individual point of view.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2012). *Research methods for business students, 5th ed.*, Harlow, Pearson Education.

Figure 4.1: The research onion model (Source: Saunders, Philip, and Thornhill, 2012)

Table 4.1: Relationships between Research Philosophy, Research Approach and research methods

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(Dash, 2005)

4.2.2 The Practical Research Process

According to Dudovskiy (2018), a typical investigation project should follow a few steps: Selection of the research area, Formulation of the aim, objectives, and research questions, and developing hypotheses. A literature review is the next step which involves finding, selecting, and collecting all relevant published work. Finalizing the methods of data collection, the researcher is going to adopt, will be the next exercise. Collection of the primary data, Data analysis, and drawing conclusions would be last steps on the roadmap. The most important step in research is the identification of the area of interest, followed by a research problem. The review of literature familiarizes the selected problem with a better and broader sense and helps to collect views and findings of earlier authors and researchers, specifically on the selected subject. Furthermore, the researcher is helped through review of literature to avoid any repetition and overlapping a part of the proposed plan with that already done at any place of the world. The review of literature will also help to select most appropriate data collection method, which will be first step in the practical path of research piece, as elaborated by research onion model of Saunders, Philip, and Thornhill (2012, Figure 4.1). From practical point of view, establishing an understanding of research methodological choice (Qualitative, Quantitative or mixed) is very important because the researcher must select which method is broadly matching to achieve objectives of his research.

4.3 Research Methods:

Identification of relevant procedures, which a researcher is going to use in his investigations, is highly important and gives a roadmap to him. After the identification of research problem, objectives of research study, and research questions, choosing an appropriate Research Approach is highly important because it should be in line with achieving objectives. In fact, a Research Approach encompasses the procedures which will be employed for data collection of the research piece under planning. A research approach comprises of procedures of systematically collecting and analysing information and data to understand a phenomenon under investigation. Thus, research approach elaborates a scheme of collection and analysis of new information from the selected data sources and can be quantitative, qualitative, or a mix of both. Quantitative research is concerned with measuring numbers or amounts of things which provide an objective approach of reasoning and focusing on quantifying data. Whereas qualitative research concentrates on experiences, themes, types, and quality things that are harder to measure. Because, Qualitative Research method was selected for collection of data

and information of the present study, therefore, it is being explained in some more detail along with pertinent reasons for its adaptation (Creswell, 2017).

Qualitative data collection helps in developing a deep understanding of the real and unique phenomenon and is appropriate to explore multiple insights of a phenomenon, adopting which will help an in-depth perception of various features of the PMS in the hospitals of Pakistan in the present research. The qualitative methods, due to their reliance on subjective interpretations of research, provide rich data about real-life situations and facilitate in understanding behaviour within wider context (Neuman, 2006; Punch, 2013; Quinlan et al., 2011; Rahi, 2017).

As the purpose of qualitative research is to gain an understanding of the prevalent trends in the opinions, this helps in recording, analysing and understanding the apprehensions of the targeted individuals and experiences of the selected sample of population in detail. Richard (2005) pointed out that the essence of a qualitative study is the search for the central experience containing both the outward appearance and inward consciousness based on the memory, image, and meaning. Saunders et al. (2009), explained that research methods and techniques are more often dictated by the research problem and research questions being considered. The collected information is richer and data collection involves direct interaction with individuals as singles or a group in the Qualitative approach, but it is more time consuming and costly. The approach is applied usually when the population sample is smaller, but information is assembled directly from the real world (Gill et al., 2008). Neuman (2014) made a good comparison between Qualitative and Quantitative Research approaches (Table 4.2) and elaborating the difference between both approaches.

Table 4.2: A comparison between Quantitative and Qualitative Research

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in: Neuman, W. L. (2014). *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Research Approaches (Seventh Edition)*.

The use of qualitative approach for the present research is due to several reasons which provides a reasonable justification and makes this research method more authentic and applicable. The qualitative methods enable the researcher to take into accounts the views and opinions of managers working in Pakistani hospitals and how they act and behave to improve the performance of their organisation. According to Myers and Avison (2002), identifying methods is significantly important to determine the procedures to be used during the research process but the more important aspect is the feasibility of selected method with the nature of research study. As the field of performance management is emerging and there is a need to utilize more qualitative approaches to fill the gaps (section 1.2) in theoretical perspective, so qualitative research methodology was considered appropriate for the current research study. Therefore, the researcher, in the present study, is trying to analyse the impact of organisation related variables on performance management using qualitative approach.

As the present research consists of a detailed analysis based on the opinions and judgments of participants selected for the research, data taken through conducting face to face interviews suits it best which pertains to a qualitative approach. However, it is not always possible to consider a larger sample size owing to the limited resources which are the requirement of Quantitative surveys, hence the approach was not adopted. According to Young and Hagorty (2007), quantitative surveys have the shortcoming of providing in-depth description and insight, so the Qualitative approach has been considered as the best for the present study.

With respect to the purpose of research, Neuman (2014) has identified three types of research; Descriptive, Explanatory, and Exploratory. Descriptive research is designed to provide highly accurate picture of conditions while Explanatory research is employed to test a theory's predictions or principle. According to him, Exploratory research provides basic facts and provide a general picture of conditions about a phenomenon. The purpose of the present study coincides with the provisions of Exploratory Study, therefore, falls under its scope because the study is evaluating basic facts and conditions of PMS in Pakistan. Exploratory research has a lot of flexibility for changes, low cost and lesser time consuming, but usually inconclusive, interpretation of data is judgmental, and frequently biased (Bhat, 2019). Therefore, this type of research should only be conducted to form the basis of precise research to be followed. Hence, it has been recommended that further refined research should follow the present preliminary studies.

4.4 Population and sampling:

This research is specifically conducted on the healthcare sector of Sialkot District of Pakistan, so the population of this study is all hospitals in this district however, the study was limited to public hospitals only. It is obvious that collecting data from the whole population (all government hospitals of Sialkot District) is highly difficult in an academic study, samples must be collected from a few selected hospitals. Sample selection is difficult job in social research because the number of interviewees depends upon the objectives of study, importance of the problem/issue being investigated, precision required, available time and resources, and the readiness of number of volunteer participants.

A review on this subject by Bakers and Edwards (2014) indicated that there is no unanimously agreed number in qualitative research, but many authors agreed-upon number of 15 or even 14. It has also been suggested that minimum of 25 respondents are required to gather enough information until it reaches a saturation point (Yilmaz, 2013; Cooper, Hedges, and Valentine, 2009) when no additional and new information is being shared by participants. For optimal sample size, gathering enough information was the focus where information started repeating. Therefore, the sample size consisted of 25 interviewees from four hospitals. As explained by Jackson (2015), when no ideal number for sample selection is available, decision can be made considering the nature of the study. Therefore, four hospitals of Sialkot: Civil Hospital, Daska, Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City, Civil Hospital, Sambrial, and Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City were selected for this study.

The evaluators of PMS (HR Department and in charge Medical officers), as well as those being evaluated (doctors, nurses, etc.), were included in the selected participants so that views of both factions get participation. Similarly, the Male/Female ratio of interviewees was also kept in mind. Out of 25 selected interviewees, 10 are female while 15 are male (40: 60 ratio). Each interview was conducted in respective offices of the participants (for easing them and saving their time) and completed within 30-40 minutes. For anonymising and concealing the identity of participants, different codes have been used. The Civil Hospital, Daska was coded as A and the 6 representatives were designated as R1A, R2A, R3A, R4A, R5A, and R6A. The Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City has been called as B and all the seven representatives have been coded as R1B, R2B, R3B, R4B, R5B, R6B, and R7B. The Civil Hospital, Sambrial Tehsil is coded as C and all the 5 representatives were coded as R1C, R2C, R3C, R4C, and R5C. The Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City has been coded as D and all the 5 representatives were

designated as R1D, R2D, R3D, R4D, and R5D. These codes will be used in describing opinions, results, and discussion in the subsequent text.

The reason for selecting these four hospitals is to allow the diversity in the findings of this research because if data have been collected from less than four hospitals; new insights from thematic analysis might not be visible. The Orthopaedic department has been selected as being one of the most important departments in every hospital. Moreover, this is the only department in all four hospitals where performance management concept has been implemented. Hence, it was considered more suitable for this research. Due to very important role of Orthopaedic department in the healthcare of Pakistan and more possibilities of getting accurate data due to personal contacts, these four hospitals were targeted for data collection under the limited resources and time. Belonging of the researcher to Sialkot city proved helpful to collect data and information reasonably and getting some good and reliable participants involved in the study.

4.5 Sampling technique

As compared to quantitative research studies, the sampling for qualitative research studies is slightly different. In quantitative research studies, the purpose of the sampling technique is to get a sample which can represent the whole population such that conclusions about the whole population could be drawn. In the case of qualitative studies, the importance of precise and definitive conclusions is less, and the goal of sampling is to learn from the skills and experiences of the participants (staff of hospitals participating in this study in present case). The importance of saturation point is higher in qualitative studies whereas the point refers to the state where similar themes start to occur from the responses of the participants and the new themes stop emerging (Punch and Oancea, 2014; Patten and Newhart (2017)).

Even though this sample can be smaller in the case of qualitative studies, it is still important to ensure that sample has resemblance with the whole group as close as possible. That is why, as emphasized by Sekaran and Bougie (2016), the characteristics of the group to be explored must be clearly known. It is important for researchers to select such a sample which can reflect the range of different and diverse people belonging to targeted group. Therefore, these aspects are considered while selecting the sample. A purposive (also called judgemental) sampling is mostly selected in qualitative studies, which is a nonprobability sampling based on study characteristics of the group and can be assumed logically to represent the group (Palys, 2008). According to Bryman and Bell (2015), purposive sampling technique (also known as selective

sampling technique) is mostly used in qualitative studies where the researcher relies on judgment to select the desired cases. The skills and capabilities of the researcher play an important role in identifying suitable individuals which help in contributing to the achievement of research objectives. To include the opinions and experiences of 'informed' participants, the present research attempted to select the participants on a purposive basis, so that each specific group (Managers, Supervisors, Doctors, Nurses and the allied medical staff) is represented in the sample. Many employees were willing to participate and understood the objectives of the study which depicts their knowledge regarding the HR practices prevailing at their respective hospitals. However, after getting consent, the participants were asked some preliminary questions to adjudge their available information level and shortlisting. By this way, the factual data could be collected, and opinion and judgment of all participants are accurately considered so that collected data is matching the aims and objectives of the investigations. Therefore, to answer the research questions and meet the objectives, purposive sampling technique was used for the study (Walliman, 2015; Zikmund et al., 2013).

4.6 Data Types

According to Gravetter and Forzano (2018), to deal with real-life problems, it is very important to collect accurate and actual data because it is not easy to make decisions based on insufficient information. There are two types of data which could be selected for any research; primary and secondary data. The secondary data refers to the already existing data while primary data is a collection of first-hand data (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Primary data collection makes research more authentic and genuine (Hair, 2015). The rationale for selecting the primary data collection method also relies on the fact that only this data type enables the researcher to address the specific research issues.

Every research issue is unique and when there is involvement of context-specific factors, it is not possible to rely on the existing data and it becomes necessary to collect the primary data (Patten and Newhart, 2017). Matthews and Ross (2014) have also asserted that it is not always the case that secondary data exists related to the research issue which is under observation. This was the case for the present study as well because performance management system of health care sector of Pakistan is not adequately explored in previous studies. The only secondary data available with the management of the hospitals is not accessible. So, the decision of relying on secondary data was discarded due to confidentiality issues. The present research makes use of primary data from interviews as a data collection tool.

4.7 Data collection technique – The Interviews:

Data collection technique which is selected for this study is semi-structured interviews. Interviews provide the opportunity to gather detailed insights into the perceptions and values of respondents. The questions mainly referred to the practices of performance management in the health care sector of Pakistan. This further helped in probing relevant information from the participants in gaining detailed insights about their experiences and their understanding of strengths and weaknesses of performance management in health care sector of Pakistan. The planned and structured interview might be the most widely adopted method in qualitative research, and the flexibility of an interview has made it so attractive, permitting the interviewer to focus on the research issue and interviewer also have the complete control over the interview hence the track of information which is provided by the interviewee can be maintained. Using interviews, nonverbal cues and emotions can also be noted. This is not provided by other methods like questionnaire. With the help of such cues and emotions, the interviewer can get an idea about the accuracy and trueness of the opinion presented by the interviewee (Blumberg, Cooper, and Schindler, 2014; Bernard, 2017).

In-depth investigation of any research issue could be made with the help of the interview strategy. It is possible to discover the thinking and feeling of the individuals regarding a certain topic and opinions being explored. The research issues which are sensitive and cannot be explored through the focus group can be investigated with the help of interviews. The present research issue which is about performance management cannot be critically examined in focus group settings, as employees and managers might be reluctant to discuss the weaknesses and negative aspects of their current performance management system in front of other employees and seniors. Therefore, instead of choosing any other strategy for collecting primary and qualitative data, interview strategy was considered as the most appropriate. The interview strategy provides the human dimension to the research study. Through this, quite detailed information could be obtained for the research issue which is under exploration and more detailed questions could be asked which is not possible in the case of other alternatives like questionnaire (Bryman, 2015; Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2013; Patton, 2005).

Moreover, Matthews and Ross (2014) have mentioned that the response rate of interviews is better. The use of this strategy enables the researcher to clarify any ambiguities in responses of the participants and even incomplete answers could also be followed up. In case of any confusion at the end of interviewee, this strategy allows the researcher to resolve such

confusions as both interviewee and interviewer are present at the same place. The responses of the interviewees are not influenced with the views of others, as it happens in the case of the focus group, hence more objective and accurate data could be obtained (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Fellows and Liu, 2015).

Considering all these reasons, in the present study, interview strategy is selected. The difficulty of time consumption and the extra cost was overcome through effective planning of the interview process. The bias of the researcher is reduced with the help of a formal data collection and data analysis process.

4.7.1 The Designing of interviews

The questions in the semi-structured interview were based on the themes identified in the literature. Interview questions were designed in a way that covers all variables to be investigated in this study. Interview structure was divided into different sections: section 1 General Information, section 2 Performance Management System, section 3: Organisational Structure, section 4: Information Technology, section 5: Employees' Commitment, section 6: Training of the Employees, and section 7: Demographic questions. This makes it easy for the researcher to ask questions in order and easy for respondents to give the most appropriate answer. All the questions asked in the interviews were directly related to the aim and objectives of this study (See Appendix A).

4.7.2 Data collection procedure:

Once interview designs were finalized, the actual data collection was started. Before starting the actual data collection, a pilot study was administered on three participants. This helped in rectifying mistakes in the intervening of the interview. After successful testing in pilot study, actual interviews were conducted with all the participants from different hospitals. The interviews conducted were from multiple levels within the hospitals such as lower, middle and higher managerial levels. The purpose of selecting participants from various categories of employees was to provide broad organisational perspective. As per the suggestion of Dooley (2001), to make the respondent comfortable, the interview process was initiated by generally asking about the performance management process before going into specific details. The interviews were recorded with prior permission from the respective organisations and in few cases where permission was not given; notes were made to record information. All the interviews were kept anonymous due to confidential request made by the respondents. These

interviews were conducted in Urdu, the national language of Pakistan, which were subsequently translated into English by the researcher.

As per the recommendation of Fixsen et al., (2005), it was ensured by the researcher to gain the confidence of the interviewee and encourage them to give candid and detailed responses around the topic. It was ensured making several minutes of small talk and ask easy, and non-threatening questions to set the interviewee at ease. The researcher has attempted effectively not to interrupt, even if answers are long and then guiding the interviewee back to the topic with the next question. Most importantly, as suggested by Kothari (2004), general questions and topics were moved at the beginning while more specific questions were asked at the end in all the interviews. During the interview process, questions were constantly refined, and adjustments were made according to the responses of the candidates. Once interviews were completed, transcribing was done manually. There are also professional transcribing services, but this can add to costs. The transcription of data was completed on the same day to ensure that data is not lost in any way. After transcribing the data, in certain situations, candidates were interviewed again to clarify certain concepts and gain insight regarding some aspects which seemed to be inadequate after the interview process. In a few cases, detailed notes are made, and these are ensured to keep them safe.

In two hospitals, candidates were quite knowledgeable in their areas and had a clear perception of the questions being asked. However, at the other two hospitals, majority of the employees lacked the basic understanding of most of the HR concepts where they insisted to contact the HR department only for the process of data collection. Furthermore, two hospitals were found to be more cooperative during the interview process as compared to the other two hospitals where the attitude towards the study was rigid. The employees had little information about the HR policies of their hospitals. Due to this, the information gathered from two hospitals was not enough and the sample size had to be increased to four hospitals accordingly. On the contrary, the other hospitals were quite confident in sharing the required information.

4.8 Time horizon:

A time horizon of any study is independent of the research methodology being used for that study (Kumar and Phrommathed, 2005). However, due to time constraints, data is collected at a given point of time. The time change may also affect the information and data collected because the improvements occurred in the system and implementation of new techniques and expert human resources may change the data on the same parameters. Therefore, specifying

the time schedule of the study is highly important. The data and information for this research have been collected from November 2017 to January 2018.

4.9 Data Analysis:

The qualitative data is made up of non-numerical information like interview transcripts, notes of the researcher, video and audio recordings, text documents, and images, etc. For finding some understandable outcomes, these data must be analysed. The analysis of qualitative data is diverse, complex and nuanced. Dudovski (2018) has identified various methods of data analysis like: Content Analysis, Narrative Analysis, Discourse Analysis, Grounded Theory, and Framework Analysis (also called Thematic Analysis). The thematic analysis is a foundational method for qualitative analysis and thus, the first qualitative method for new researchers to learn and carry out their research (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Therefore, to analyse the data, thematic analysis approach was used in which the data were identified, analysed and classified in themes. This technique systematically analysed the data to identify the precise meanings of the information. It helps in organizing and describing data in detail and interpreting the diverse aspects of the research topic. Various themes observed to be common among the participants were identified, but the ideas of a single interviewee were not ignored. These were also presented as sole themes. Keeping in view the identified themes, the detailed insight of the performance management system was understood and described (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Marczyk, DeMatteo, and Festinger, 2005; Zikmund et al., 2013).

Although analytical software, such as Nvivo is suggested to use for analysis, but these have limited searching capability. Hence, no software was used to analyse the data, as it was considered not very useful for this research because identifying themes is easier for researchers. Moreover, some of the collected data were in Urdu, hence translating the interviews from Urdu to English would not have been possible by the software. Since the nature of the research is subjective, the software might have created forced categories of themes which may not have been the true depiction of the prevailing conditions. The interpretive approach allows the researcher to be a participant as well of the research process to search and categorize data in themes and to allow for better understanding of gathered information. The audio recording of interviews helped a lot for later data analysis. Choys (2014) has identified certain steps to effectively implement thematic analysis which was constantly kept in mind during the analysis stage. Interviews were studied so many times and similar parts were coded, which were later developed into themes. Furthermore, data were constantly reviewed again and again to search

for new themes. Then the themes were named which further helped to input relevant data under the headings while describing the results of the study. The themes were reviewed many times before finalizing (Choys, 2014, Fugard and Potts, 2015). The themes were also compared and aligned with the themes emerged from review of literature (Conceptual framework, Section 3.6, Table 3.1).

4.10 Generalizability, Validity, and Reliability of Information and Data

Any social phenomena cannot be reproduced exactly. In qualitative studies, it is almost impossible that data could be recollected, or study could be replicated in the same context (Saunders, 2011). The importance of reliability and generalizability is quite higher in those research studies which are based on quantitative methods. However, these concepts have little relevance to qualitative studies. The purpose of qualitative studies is never to get such results which could be generalized to the whole population, but the aim is interpretation of existing conditions in such a manner that valuable insights could be obtained. In qualitative studies, replication is neither intended nor possible. Every research study is unique in its context and that is why the qualitative studies give lesser importance to the external validity of the research findings. Therefore, external validity is of little concern in the present study as well. This research, being qualitative, focused on the internal validity and how consistent to reality the findings are obtained. The research concentrated on reporting the authentic experience of those who have participated in this research. Therefore, following the suggestion of Creswell and Creswell (2017), it has been assured that as accurate as possible findings are presented and reported in this study to address the internal validity (Donald and Pamela, 2003; Greener, 2008).

Qualitative research studies' interpretation can become better when there is transferability, dependability, and conformability. Considering this, the present research has widely focused on these three aspects. Conformability in any research can only be ensured when there is a higher level of trust created among researcher and participants. This trust enables the researcher to gain multiple viewpoints on the research issue which are under observation. Therefore, the researcher tried that every participant is taken into confidence before the start of interview. An information sheet was developed which was handed over to all interviewees so that they can understand the purpose of this research and do not have any ambiguity regarding the purpose of interviews. The information sheet also informed the participants that this is an academic project, hence they should not worry about their data to be used for some commercial purpose.

As per suggestion of Yilmaz (2013), for gaining multiple perspectives regarding performance management in the health care sector, managers from different levels were interviewed. The responses were matched with each other which also enabled to ensure the conformability and credibility of the research findings (Hair, 2007; McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015; Veal, 2005).

Following the recommendation of Quinlan et al., (2011), for ensuring transferability in the findings of a research study, data are not collected from the single hospital, rather have been collected from four different hospitals varying in their size and services. This diversity in the selected hospitals has enabled the researcher to ensure that the findings will have the transferability in different healthcare institutions as well.

As suggested by Punch (2013), dependability is also fostered in this research. For this purpose, it was asked to all participants that they should present answers to the interview questions in the light of current and past experiences highlighting with clear examples for each argument. This dependability is much like the reliability of the research findings. So, by doing so, the reliability of research findings is also ensured.

4.11 Limitations

A few obstacles were faced during the research process which provides avenues for future research. Firstly, despite having strong contacts in the hospital sector, it was difficult to correspond with the upper managerial posts or HR department. It was practically impossible to consider every hospital in the health care sector which provides room for future researchers to target other hospitals to generalize the results over the health care sector. Furthermore, access to authority documents was a huge constraint during the research process. Confidentiality and sharing of real issues, problems, and policies of the health sector was the biggest problem faced by the researcher. Thus, there was a clear-cut disparity between academia and management. Time constraint was another impediment of the research. Due to the busy schedules of participants, data collection process took more time than expected. A lot of patience has been administered because the participants went astray from the topic under discussion or provided vague answers due to insufficient knowledge. However, the problem exposure understood from review of literature and the contact with healthcare organisations helped in understanding the performance management and keeping the interviewees on track during the holding of interviews.

4.12 Data and Information Access Issues in UK and Pakistan:

Access to real data for understanding a research problem in-depth is the high priority of a researcher, but access to data and information is a frequent issue with the organisations being investigated because they are conservative in sharing of their data and policies. The secondary data is easy to access, but such data could not be used for all the research studies due to exact relevance and specifications. Moreover, the research issue which is under investigation cannot rely only on secondary data. Keeping in view the aim and objectives of the study, primary data is a basic requirement. For the collection of primary data, there is a need to get direct access to the institution from where data could be collected. As a first step, permission from the University was taken because it is an ethical requirement of the research. Unfortunately, it was obtained twice; firstly, for London and secondly for Pakistan because research could not be conducted in London due to obtaining access from concerned organisations, as explained in the last paragraph (Newman and Benz, 1998, Saunders et al., 2009).

Written permission was obtained from the Medical Superintendent of each hospital, who is the in charge of the hospital. Initially, there was some reluctance of these interviews for this study, but on showing the university letter and providing all details about the study, they agreed for the interviews. All of them were concerned about not sharing the confidential information, so researcher ensured not to ask any such data which is confidential. The social contacts of the researcher have helped in getting access to the concerned person from the respective hospitals. Despite having social contact in these hospitals, getting access and extracting information from them was a daunting challenge despite the availability of official references. Considering Pakistan's reference-based culture, it was difficult to get access to Upper management, hence managerial and officer level employees from the HR Department were interviewed for the research (Dudwick et al. (2006).

Earlier, this researcher was planned to conduct in London. Approval for conducting this research was obtained from Health Research Authority (HRA), which govern all the research in the premises of the NHS. Ethical approval from the university was also obtained after the approval from Health Research Authority, UK. Then, the R & D (Research and Development Department) of Bart's Health NHS Trust was contacted to get local approval for conducting the fieldwork in the premises of the desired research site of the NHS. Despite willingness of General Manager and Services Managers, who were quite happy with the project, Bart's Health NHS trust did not show their willingness to participate in this research project. On further

direction of Director of Studies, the researcher then contacted with the Lewisham and Greenwich NHS Trust, Guys and St. Thomas NHS Trust, Kings College London NHS trust, and Chelsea and Westminster NHS trust to participate into my research and they were happy to participate but for the purpose of the data collection they gave the long appointment dates for participating. Rather some of these trusts took back their consent without giving any reason. The pivotal participants of my study did not prove very cooperative because they took very long to show their willingness and even some of them do not show their will due to their personal reasons. Hence, on the suggestion of supervisors, the researcher took decision to complete in Pakistan.

Hence, the researcher faced data collection access issue in London as well as in Pakistan.

4.13 Ethical considerations:

Considering the importance of ethical standards of the research, the researcher has clearly considered all those. Every research must include only those participants who do not have any objection or concerns with their participation (Burns and Burns 2008). This means that free and voluntary consent of the participants is of utmost importance which cannot be avoided in any case. Therefore, before the start of the interview, this consent was asked again from all the participants of this study. A consent form was got signed by all participants earlier. The ethical guidelines for doing research have given a formal procedure for inviting the participants for the interview (Cooper, Schindler, & Sun, 2006). Therefore, this procedure was followed by the researcher by sending a written request to all participants. After one week of this written request, follow up phone calls were made if replies from someone were not obtained. Those participants who agreed for the interview were considered for further procedure.

The researchers like Flick (2015) has recommended that consent is not only needed at the start of the interview, but it must be obtained throughout the research process. Therefore, it was ensured throughout the interview sessions that interviewees do not feel like they are forced in any way to participate in this study. They were clearly told that they have the right to withdraw if they want to leave the interview at any stage. So, they could do so at any time, and they would not be compelled to stay and complete the interview. Even they were at liberty to answer any question or not. Two of the interviewees withdrew from the study during the interview process and researcher did not force them to participate or continue with the interview. They were permitted to withdraw from the study without asking any further questions. Mackey and Gass (2013) mentioned another important aspect, which is the anonymity and confidentiality

of the participants of the study. Therefore, throughout the study, the researcher has ensured that personal information will not be disclosed to anyone and at any time during this research study or afterward. The sensitive information like the name was also not recorded of any interviewee. Even, the positions of the participants have not indicated anywhere in the text, so their confidentiality is protected. For saving the collected data, pseudonyms were designated and are used in the transcription of the interview as well.

Another important element of the research ethics is that researchers should have all relevant information about the research study for sharing with the participants (Greener, 2008). Therefore, all the necessary information was also provided to the participants. All the participants were clearly told of the aims of this research. Moreover, they were also informed that this is an academic project, hence, their data will not be used for any commercial purposes and it will never be shared with any third party. As it was necessary to record the interview, so this request was also made to all participants that the researcher wants to record the interview. Unfortunately, only a few participants allowed to continue recording with Dictaphone. These participants were also ensured that the collected data will not be saved with the researcher in any way that their confidentiality could be harmed, and it is promised to them that their data will be deleted after 10 years of completing the respective degree.

4.14 Chapter Summary:

This chapter has presented the research methods selected for the present study. This research has relied on qualitative approach in which primary data have been collected. For the collection of data, the interview method is selected. The sample was selected using the purposive sampling technique and thematic analysis technique was employed for processing of the data. Limitations of the study, ethical considerations, and data validity and reliability have also been highlighted.

Chapter Five: Findings and Analysis Part A

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the results of the evaluation of the PMS, implemented in selected hospitals of the study area, are presented. The results are based on a thematic analysis of the collected information from various interviews. Different aspects of the prevailing PMS like importance, working, deficiencies and challenges, the mechanism of managing the current system, and what are future resources development requirements, have been evaluated. Thematic analysis and data collected from four hospitals have been presented in the form of themes identified from various interviews of participants and aligning these with the themes from review of literature (Table 3.1). Most of the themes were similar to previous research findings while a few were totally new as compared to those available in literature because these findings emerged during thematic analysis of the interviews recorded for the study and are specific to the study area, the health care sector of Sialkot District, Pakistan. The finalised themes have been grouped into five major titles (Tables 5.1 to 5.5); Evaluation of the Current Management System (CPMS), Training of employees, Organisation structure, Information Technology, and Employees' commitment, which are discussed into various subheadings (Themes) subsequently. The results are presented and discussed with respect to the questions being relied by this study.

5.2 Q1: Identification of Current Performance Management System (CPMS) and evaluation of its efficiency

The evaluation of the existing Performance Management System and evaluation of its efficiency is the first basic research question of the present study and being discussed under the following four themes/subheadings aligning with the conceptual framework.

1. Assessment of the Current Performance Management System (CPMS) implemented in the studied hospitals
2. Indicators and criteria used for assessment
3. Usefulness and effectiveness of the CPMS in achieving goals
4. Managing and tackling poor performance of the employees

5.2.1 Assessment of the Performance Management Systems Currently Implemented in the Studied Hospitals

Because all the studied hospitals belonged to the government sector, therefore, like all other government departments, the performance evaluation is conducted on a yearly basis as Annual Confidential Reports (ACR). Under this performance management system, all the seniors write ACR of their junior employees on a prescribed Performa covering so many aspects of the employees. However, because of different nature of work performed daily, the hospitals have their own assessment systems, in addition, which are target-based. In such a system, targets and key performance indicators (KPIs) have already been set for everyone, which act as the foundation of the performance management. These systems have been designated differently in various hospitals: Performance Appraisal System Assessment, Indicator Management system, Indicator System, and Confidential Appraisal (Table 5.1).

The performance management system implemented in Allama Iqbal Hospital Sialkot City is the Annual Confidential Report (ACR). Under this system, all the senior and junior employees of this hospital are assessed on the annual basis and the timing of the review is end of December of every year. This performance review report is further used for training needs, and for bringing improvements. Once the appraisal is completed, objectives for the next performance period are also identified which include any kind of improvements needed for the coming period. Similar finding has also been reported by Aslam, Hamid and Ayub (2011) who examined the ACR based performance appraisal in the banking system of Pakistan. The Medical Superintendent is the sole responsible who must appraise the employee. The Nursing Superintendent is the Reporting Manager for all nurses (R3B). A similar method is also adopted in Tehsil Hospital, Daska.

The performance management system implemented in Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial is Indicator System (R4C), which is based on key performance indicators (R5C). It has been told by interviewees from this hospital that indicators are set at the starting of the performance period. These indicators are used for controlling and monitoring performance of all employees. As told by an interviewee:

'We assign a set of duties to employees then our seniors, managers, and HODs (Head of a department) check whether the assigned tasks are fulfilled or not' (R2C).

For measuring performance, in this hospital, performance dimensions consisting of punctuality of workers, a regular visit to the assigned patients, and the number of patients assigned are used as to assess performance of individuals. When any of the employees do not perform well, counselling is provided to them and they are provided with every possible opportunity to improve the performance. Despite the availability of the performance appraisal system, not all employees are clearly aware of the existing performance management system and they said that there exists no formal system and everything is done in an informal manner. Regular feedback and supervision are provided to employees so that they can accomplish their objectives effectively.

In Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City, a PMS with the name of Indicator Management System has been used. These indicators have proved helpful for employees to manage things. Meetings are arranged with the senior medical superintendent who indicates all employees what is to be done during a period. Every employee is assigned duties as per indicators in a way which work could be completed in an effective manner. It is supervised and observed whether all employees are performing their duties effectively.

5.2.2 Indicators and criteria used for performance assessment of employees

In any performance system, evaluation of achievements by the employees is based upon certain parameters adopted by organisations to their domain of working and goals to be achieved. Key performance indicator refers to a measurable value which is used for demonstrating how effectively an employee has accomplished the objectives (Van Dooren, Bouckaert, and Halligan, 2015). Kaplan and Norton (2001) have reported the implementation of KPIs based performance management system in which, it is clearly decided from the start that which targets and KPIs must be achieved in the prescribed period. The elements like regularity, punctuality, routine practices, number of patients attended/treated, qualification, training, and overall performance are included in the performance system. Rahimi, Kavosi, Shojaei, and Kharazmi (2017) suggested the indicators of staff satisfaction rate, staff turnover, training expenditures per capita, key Jobs' substitute, average hours of Internet use, the amount of the electronic medical record, number of days of sick leave to total employees ratio, employee absenteeism rate, and Rate of employee sick-leave for assessing employees performance. Ferreira and Otley (2009) stressed that performance parameters should be observed regularly for preparation of annual appraisals. Mostly, there is not any formal and proper structured method for recording or measuring the performance of employees, and everything is done on random basis by

managers. However, good hospitals use some Key Performance Indicators (KPI), as in Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot and Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial (Table 5.1). The KPIs may be like achievement of assigned targets, number of patients attended, quality of service provided to patients, the satisfaction of patients, etc. Various participants have pointed out these ongoing KPIs in the studied hospitals.

The performance appraisal form has both the columns i.e. desired and actual performance of the employees. The deviations among actual and desired performance are used to examine the overall performance of an employee through which it is concluded that how effectively an employee has performed in a certain period. The participant from one of the hospitals, designated as R1A, has provided an example during his interview:

‘For example, if an employee is assigned to look for 100 beds and he focuses on 90 or more than 90, then he is rated ‘good’. On the other hand, if someone comes with a smaller number of beds’ supervision, then he is rated ‘poor’. This is how our system manages the Performance Appraisal based on KPI system.’ (R1A).

Other than this, the total operations margin and the average length of stay are also used as indicators of the performance of a medical department and these are accordingly translated into the individual performance appraisals. One of the interviewees said:

‘Performance can be checked with a variety of methods: we check the total operation margin of our department and the patient’s average length of stay.’ (R4D)

The attendance of employees is also used as performance criteria in some of the hospitals. One of the study participants pointed out that:

“In this regard attendance can be mentioned here to elaborate this system. Just as, we have set a target for attendance that it must at least be above 85 percent of any employee. So, someone below this point is not doing well, and corrective measures are needed (R2A).

The punctuality of employees is important for managing everything and good performance. Only those employees are rated well who perform as per the requirements of punctuality.

Table 5.1: Identified themes and the summary of participants' thoughts regarding the **Current Management System (CPMS)** in the selected hospitals

Identified Themes	The essence of participants' interviews content regarding identified themes in studied hospitals			
	Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City	Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City	Tehsil Hospital, Daska	Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial
1. The Current Performance Management System (CPMS) implemented in the studied hospitals	Annual Confidential Report (ACR) evaluated by the in-charge of each employee (R4B, R7B). Quarterly and Annual Assessment (R5B)	Performance Appraisal System, Assessment after one year (R3D). Indicator Management system is used for management and evaluation of performance (R2D, R4D, R6D)	Annual Confidential Report termed as Performance Appraisal System in our hospital. Assessment is through job based KPIs (R1A, R2A, R3A, R6A)	Indicator System (R4C). KPI based system (R5C). There is no proper PMS implemented in our hospital, we are assigned a set of duties, then our seniors check whether the assigned tasks are fulfilled or not (R1C). Performance Appraisal's Annual system but since 2013 the Target System is working (R6A).
2. Indicators and criteria used for performance assessment of employees	The feedback system and the overall physical surveys forms are used for the evaluation of employees and seniors' performance evaluation (R6B). The feedback from the patients is taken as well to know if they have any problem or complaint regarding staff performance (R5B).	Comparison of time taken to perform various medical activities by different employees (R4D, R5D), rounds of seniors tell about good or bad performance (R1D). The performance of employees is assessed regularly on quarterly bases, six months bases and yearly bases using regularity and work done criteria (R3D).	The successful offering of service to the assigned patient beds (R1A), Attendance (85%) is one of the performance criteria (R2A).	Seniors visit and notice everyone's work and quality of performance (R6C).

<p>3. Usefulness and effectiveness of the CPMS in achieving goals</p>	<p>CPMS is proving helpful but the need for a structural system is felt (R4B, R7B). The assessment period is one-year, short term evaluation still may prove more effective (R3B, R4B, R7B),</p>	<p>CPMS is helping but we need HR department to improve (R2D, R3D, R6D). The assigning of duties to various employees and subsequent evaluation is proving effective (R2, R3D, R4D, R6D).</p>	<p>Our system is highly useful in evaluating the employees and achieving goals (R1A, R2A, R3A, R6A) The CPMS is proving effective, anyone can check it (R1A, R2A, R3A, R6A).</p>	<p>The CPMS is indicating good performance of employees (R1C, R4C, R5C, R6C). The system is performing effectively but we do not have an HR department which is needed (R1C, R4C, R5C, R6C).</p>
<p>4. Managing and tackling poor performance of the employees</p>	<p>Most of them have a positive view but a few are reluctant (R4B). The cause of poor performance is identified, and the employee is guided to improve it (R1B). Employees are questioned verbally about the incomplete assignment and asked to complete it if no genuine reason is described by them. If still work is not done, a written warning is issued which is put on record (R3B, R4B, R5B). Feedback from patients is also used to guide employees (R6B). Employees like only positive feedback (R7B).</p>	<p>They must follow the instructions and follow the criteria (R2D), although some of them do not like (R6D). The reason for low performance is tried to be identified (R3D). The employee not completing an assignment is first guided, but on no improvement, an action is taken against him (R4D, R6D). Employees with low performance are advised to improve within the allowed timetable while good performers are encouraged (R2D, R3D, R6D)</p>	<p>In the beginning, they did not like it but on implementation of awards and rewards like Employee of the Month, Best Employee and Monitoring Award, they accepted it (R1A, R2A, R5A). In the beginning, they find it difficult (R6A) A big difference between assigned duties and performed duties is regarded as poor performance and the concerned employees are guided to improve it (R1A, R2A, R6A). A poor performance, as well as good performance, are conveyed monthly to the employees (R1A, R6A).</p>	<p>Mostly. It is positive but low performers do not like it (R1C, R5C). When the incomplete duty is asked to fulfil again, the worker is not happy (R6C). Non-performers or poor performers are issued a warning slip (R4C, R5C, R6C). Employees are assessed in many ways like punctuality, a regular visit to the assigned patients and the number of patients assigned. In case of non-performance or low performance, they are first advised to improve, if no improvement is observed, disciplinary action is taken (R1C, R5C, R6C).</p>

Note: CPMS is an abbreviation of Current Performance Management System

There are still numerous criteria which can be used for performance measurement. Following the suggestions of Parmenter (2015), targets which must be achieved are decided for every employee over a specified time and will be acting as the benchmark for all employees. After

the end of the period, the performance of all employees is assessed against the KPIs which are set at the start of the period. It is recorded whether the performance targets are achieved or there is any deviation. In case of deviation, corrective actions are taken.

Further to this, the overall performance of a hospital also helps to indicate the performance of all employees collectively. The final outcomes for a certain period (say a month or a quarter) are clearly indicative of hospital performance and are a good measure for evaluation. As said by an interviewee:

'If the number of the patients was 1000 in OPD before six months and now it is 1500 patients in OPD. It means that performance is better because now people like to come here for treatment.' (R2A).

This shows that organisational performance is another criterion which can be used for assessing and improving the performance of all employees collectively, as used in Tehsil Hospital, Daska.

Hospitals, management should strive to set the targets of employees which are aligned with the organisational performance because eventually, this helps to improve the performance. The study of Den Hartog, Boselie, and Paauwe (2004) suggested that organisational performance acts as the criteria to measure how effective performance management of the organisation remained during a certain period.

Sardar Begum Hospital Sialkot City and Tehsil Hospital Sambrial are relying on the performance measurement through observation by seniors. The performance of employees is observed during regular rounds of senior doctors. Few of the respondents have mentioned this phenomenon in the following words:

'Most often it is checked via observations on the working place that whether the worker has attended the patients properly or not' (R1C).

'When our seniors take a round of the workplace, they get to know about the good and bad performance of the workers. We see whether they are working with responsibility or not. In this way, we get to know about the efficient and the dull worker' (R1D)

'Our seniors visit and notice everyone's work and quality of performance. They tell us how to manage who and this is how we get to know which employee works well, and which doesn't' (R6C).

'We access their performance regularly and on quarterly bases, six months bases and yearly bases and then we evaluate how much work he has done, and we had certain

parameters to assess whether he is regularly working and what he has done in this department, so we assess parameters right from A to Z and write appraisal.’ (R3D).

As also mentioned by Aguinis, Joo, and Gottfredson (2011), The above responses tell that performance is measured through observation on a regular basis (quarterly, six-monthly and yearly). Aguinis, Joo, and Gottfredson (2011) also suggested such criteria of performance appraisals.

The present research has found that comparative analysis is also being adopted for employees’ performance appraisals.

‘We do the comparative analysis that how many patients they had initially and how many they had afterward.’ (R5D)

As recommended by Aggarwal and Thakur (2013), survey forms are also used in hospitals with the intention to assess performance. These forms are distributed to supervisors of employees and they assess the performance of their subordinates. Once these forms are completed, these are sent for further review to the person managing performance management of employees.

One of the interviewees has used the following words.

‘Actually, we use the feedback system and the overall physical surveys forms have been distributed. They are being used in order to get the performance of the specific employee. By doing that, the performance is being measured by the managers and the juniors as well, and by this, the performance is being checked properly.’ (R6B).

Through this comparison, managers come at the better conclusion that how effectively employees are performing and how their performance has improved as compared to the past and as compared to other employees. Next, to this, patients’ feedback is also considered critical to know how effectively employees are fulfilling their performance objectives. There are numerous methods which could be used for getting feedback from customers. The complaint register, survey data, interviews or observations are few of the methods which can be used by hospitals for getting feedback from customers to assess how effectively employees are responding to the needs of customers. One of the respondents has said this;

‘We take feedback from the patients too that if they have any problem regarding our staff then the performance is checked accordingly.’ (R5B)

This has helped to reach the conclusion that feedback of patients is also an important source of performance assessment.

5.2.3 Usefulness and effectiveness of the CPMS in achieving goals

In the opinion of most of the participants, the Current Performance Management System (CPMS) of all the studied hospitals has been proved to be quite helpful because it is helping employees to work on the assigned duties and remain mostly successful to achieve the objectives and goals of these organisations (Table 5.1). Daniels, Tapscott, and Caston (2011) have also reported the effectiveness of Performance Appraisal System is in meeting their goals. The personnel of these hospitals assigned assessment duties of these hospitals deemed that the bad and poor performance of employees could be assessed and known how effectively they are working on their duties and goals. This has also enabled the managers to grow the respective department in a better manner.

When a clear target is decided and it is assigned to the employee(s), they can better follow the decided path to achieve that target. With the clear targets in hand, every employee can work on the given targets and both individual and organisational goals are achieved in an effective manner. Deficiency at any level is identified well in time and managed before the situation becomes worse. Although, many participants were satisfied with the use and efficiency of the CPMS, but some of them were having a few reservations and pointed out the deficiencies and bottlenecks like non-availability of HR department, need for IT-based online system, biasedness during assessment, and long period of evaluation duration, which is one year in two hospitals. A few quotes of the interviewee are reproduced here as evidence:

'We found it effective because it indicates about the improvement in the performance and highlights their grey areas (mean weaknesses)' (R3B).

'Yes, we have found CPMS effective. If there comes a structured evaluation system, then it would be helpful for improving the efficiency of the performance further' (R4B).

'No, we have not found it as much effective' (R6B).

'Yes, CPMS is effective. The reason is that our system is specially KPI based, so at the end of the month we rate the performance of people against the designed KPI' (R1A).

'Yes, it is effective because the deficiency and efficiency of the working staff can be recognized easily' (R6A).

'Yes! Our system is working well. The system's efficiency depends on the men power. More the men power, more will be the patient' (R3A).

'Yes, I think it is effective if it could be implemented properly. We get continuous supervision and employees get to know how to improve themselves' (R5B).

'Yes, it is effective because we all are cooperative, work together as a team, and can get great results' (R2C).

'No, I have not found it effective because we have a shortage of staff and the comparatively big number of patients' (R5C)

'I don't think it is efficient because we don't have a proper HR department, so we can't implement it properly' (R4C).

'It is effective but due to lack of staff and no proper HR department, difficult for us to implement' (R3D).

'Yes, it is effective. This makes us easy to supervise them on a continuous basis and secondly workers get engaged with each other and do the teamwork' (R6D).

Overall evaluation of the PMS in studied hospitals revealed that CPMS has increased the efficiency of work and enabled the respective department to identify the deficiencies, but the success and effectiveness are partial (quotes reproduced above). Cascio and Aguinis (2005) suggested that once problematic area is found through performance appraisal, appropriate actions can be taken to correct it. The CPMS also proved useful in this regard. It has also been asserted by one of the interviewees that this PMS has enabled them to improve the overall performance of the organisation. Not only employees or management believe that hospital has improved its performance but its customers (i.e. patients) have also opined the improved performance, as per the view of one of the interviewees.

'If the number of the patients was 1000 in OPD before six months and now it is 1500 patients in OPD. it means that performance is better in the opinion of patients because now people like to come here for treatment.' (R2A)

5.2.4 Managing and tackling poor performance of the employees

5.2.4.1 Reaction of employees to the CPMS

Performance management and evaluation is a major activity as well as a key issue for the management of organisations, may be of any type or size (Rahimi, Kavosi, Shojaei, and Kharazmi, 2017). This is essential for achieving objectives of organisations whereas workers have their own reservations in this regard. A performance management system may motivate individuals to learn and perform due to competition created among them. According to Aguinis

(2009), performance management system is useful for improving efficiency of individuals. However, those who are being frequently evaluated, sometimes do not like this practice because being questioned about assigned duties, held responsible for not doing some task and subsequent advice and actions are not appreciated by individual employees (Table 5.1). Therefore, one of the participants mentioned such a response in his interview while the other interviewee elaborated their reaction in more detail.

‘In the beginning, they find it difficult because before CPMS, there was no such system of assigning the targets beforehand.’ (R6A).

‘Some people feel relegated that they are being checked but majority takes it positively, as they think that it is good to be checked according to any evaluation system, they feel encouraged based on their work’ (R4B).

In case of good performance, performance-based awards are also given. Such a performance appraisal system has been recommended by many authors like Murphy and Cleveland (1995). As it was said by one of the interviewees:

‘In case of good performance, we have arranged Employee of the Month, Best Employee and Monitoring Award.’ (R1A)

The current performance management system is mostly implemented by managers and supervisors. Managers’ reaction is also found as positive and they are of the view that not only the performance of employees is increased but it is also possible to overcome their weaknesses. Hence, a positive change is possible because of the evaluation which is done by managers through guidance for improvement. For example, the response of one respondent in this regard is:

‘Initially, we faced problem regarding the counter check through CPMS, but with the passage of time when we informed them about the rewards of good performance or best employee on the behalf of Health Secretary and educated them about the monthly monitoring award, they started to accept it and they were ok’ (R1A).

The response of allied medical staff of one studied hospital to CPMS is quoted as under.

‘There are different responses, they like only positive feedback and are not happy when informed about their weaknesses. But still, there are some people who demand positive

criticism so that they can overcome their drawbacks and can become capable enough to bring the positive change'(R7B).

5.2.4.2 Tackling of poor performance in the CPMS

The employees of all organisations are never equal in their capability, motivation, commitment, and performance. There are workers who always do excellent work, rather they help others to achieve the targets of the organisation. However, there are poor performers who are neither committed to their assignments nor the organisation goals. They just work to attend the duty. According to views of participants of current study, such employees are tackled by their seniors and managers in different ways (Table 5.1). After identification of poor performance through CPMS, they are mostly guided to do the missed or incomplete assignments as a first step. Even awards and rewards are announced for good performers so that they are motivated as well. If still the work is not done properly, they are warned and some disciplinary action may be taken subsequently (R1A, R6A, R1B, R4C, R6C, R3D, R4D). A few quotes of the interviewees are reported here. Cascio (2018) mentioned that feedback is useful for highlighting those areas of performance which need improvement.

'As we have the reward system for good performance, similarly we have introduced a punishment system for the bad performance. We do counselling and assign an explanation, even warning is also issued afterward if required' (R1A).

'The workers facing any kind of deficiency in their performance and are unable to achieve the given task, they are assigned the task again. In case, any person is lacking capability related to the target, then he/she is attached with a more experienced person. In case the deficiency remains, then I personally give the lecture to the employee' (R6A).

'Those workers who face any kind of deficiency in their performance or they remain unable to achieve the given task, they are assigned the task again' (R3A).

'If an employee is not doing the job in the way supposed to do, we warn him/her first that the poor attitude is causing trouble here and you might lose your job. If he/she is unable to improve, a professional trainer is arranged. He/she keeps the job if becomes responsible, otherwise, the job is lost' (R1B).

'We identify the reason and cause behind the reduced work efficiency of the workers, which sometimes can be the deficient working by an employee. He is advised and guided but if even the problem persists, the worker is issued disciplinary action' (R3D).

'In case of any inconvenience from the side of employees, we start with verbal warnings, and even calling explanations if the problem exceeds the limit, then show-cause notice is served.' (R3B).

'We help them in correcting their work and if still not understood, a complaint is sent to the seniors by us and they tell us what to do next, their instructions are followed accordingly' (R6C).

There are most of the employees who take the criticism as positive while others do not, but a few individuals do not like that they are being checked and monitored by their supervisors and they consider this as negative. Rewards should be offered on the performance-based ratings (Jackson, Schuler, and Werner, 2009) which can enable hospitals to improve the overall work efficiency of all employees. Other than rewards, hospitals also use punishments for poor performance as well. An interviewee mentioned:

'In our hospital, we have introduced the concept of Best Employee of the month, this thing improves the work efficiency among the workers. We include all nurses and even paramedical staff. This trend has been introduced among us and is very helpful' (R2B).

Hvidman and Andersen (2013) have emphasized that sometimes it becomes necessary to associate punishment with the performance evaluation outcomes. As the analysis of the interviews shows that for tackling with the poor performance issue, the punishment system has been introduced where employees are answerable for their poor performance, same as they are rewarded for their good performance. As said by two of the interviewees:

'If any worker can't work properly, then he is warned, in case the situation remains same then serious action is taken but because of commendation, he fears getting punished' (R1C).

'We guide them on how to do a job. If they don't follow our guideline then we take an action where we might punish employees after sending complaint to the seniors, they decide what kind of action should be taken and then the action is properly implemented' (R4B).

Within the Pakistani culture, it is the punishment on poor performance which is working more effectively as compared to other factors. Therefore, if supervisors find out that there is no

alternative to manage the performance through other methods, they do not hesitate while opting for punishments which are not very common in other cultures, especially in western countries (Berry, Broadbent, and Otley, 2005).

5.2.4.3 Communication, feedback, and guidance to employees in the CPMS

Efficient communication is a basic requirement of an excellent organisation because if orders and assigned duties are conveyed timely to all individuals, their feedback is received in due time, and managers become aware of any deficiencies, problems, and complaints, they can remediate immediately. In the traditional systems, communication and feedback were mostly done through paperwork, which was inefficient, delaying and costly. Harris, Cortvriend, and Hyde (2007) has ascertained that having fresh data about performance of employees is an important task. Similarly, receiving their feedback on timely basis plays role in achieving the objectives. The PMS enables rapid and efficient communications and feedback through Emails and online systems. The inspections of seniors and subsequent feedbacks help a lot to improve the performance of employees. One of the respondents has explained how feedback acts as a tool to improve the performance of employees (Table 5.1). An unsatisfactory grade during a performance evaluation, and guidance on those aspects in which they could not perform well, motivate and trigger them to improve. So, the feedback and guidance system integrated into the performance appraisal system helps employees greatly to focus on improving their performance. His view is:

‘Of course, feedback is important in terms of improving performance because when it is time for them to get graded by us, they care about their position if they are unsatisfied with the grade they are marked by, the employees try to work hard on their weak point as they understand that serious action will be taken against them if the institution won’t be satisfied with their work.’ (R5A)

Thus, the role of the current performance management system is quite remarkable in all hospitals and these hospitals are improving their performance in a significant way with the implemented PMS. The current performance management system is also helpful in developing employee engagement. These results are consistent with the findings of Boachie-Mensah and Seidu (2012) who have mentioned that this eventually leads towards employee engagement. One interviewee has mentioned:

‘Workers get engaged with work and they do the teamwork.’ (R2D)

When employees know that their performance is to be tracked on daily basis and they will be provided with the performance assessment in a specific period, it will lead towards the employee engagement, dedication, and vigour to work.

The supervisors keep an eye continuously how employees are working on the given task. The outcome of the task, the efficiency of performing that task, and the effectiveness are also used to know how good an employee has performed, which is also shared with him. A comparison method creates competition for good work. As in words of an interviewee:

'Wherever I feel there is the demand for comparison between the workers, I do so.' (R3A)

The purpose of this comparison is not to identify weaknesses, but the purpose is to motivate employees through proper feedback that if others can perform well then why can't they perform as per the targets. As it was also highlighted by an interviewee as:

'I motivate them by saying that see that person is doing a good job so why can't you. So, I believe with the help of motivation we can bring improvement in their work.' (R3A)

Schläfke, Silvi, and Möller (2012) have pointed out that managing the performance is always challenging, hence there is always a need for appropriate programs through which, every employee is obliged and reinforced to perform well. To tackle poor performance, a proper monitoring system should be incorporated into organisations. Under this monitoring system, punishment, training and mentoring act as the building blocks. So, as also suggested by Armstrong (2006), if ever it is found that performance of any employee is not up to the standard, then management strives to find out the root cause of the problem with the intention to get the best performance results. Guidance and mentoring by some experts are also used as a tool to rectify the poor performance problem. Whenever it is identified that some employee is not performing well; the suitable solution is to put him under mentoring of anyone who has the capability to guide him.

The hospitals have also focused on counselling of employees for obtaining good results. By conducting face to face meetings, feedback is taken from employees and it is investigated why an employee is unable to perform as per standards. In such meetings, supervisors do not be offensive, and they start with the positive aspects of their performance. After taking them in loop, they are asked why they remained unable to perform as per the standards. Thus, they are properly guided to overcome their weaknesses. They are also helped if they are facing some

financial or social problem. The feedback and guiding strategy are mostly helpful to obtain a good performance of individuals and organisation collectively.

5.3 Q2 Factors affecting Current Performance System in the Selected Hospitals

The second question of the study is to identify the role and impact of important factors in relation to CPMS. The currently implemented Performance System in the Hospitals of the study area are affected by various factors which must also be understood to manage effectively for getting good performance of individuals, teams, and the institute as a whole as well as providing good quality services to the patients. Aligning with the Contextual Framework of the study emerging from the review of literature (Table 3.1), the impacting factors are being discussed under various headings.

5.3.1 The Organisational structure:

The organisational structure basically is setting up hierarchy of an organisational and assigning the duties to various employees deputed at different positions for completing the tasks and activities of work. This can be presented in organisational chart to make it self-explanatory (Jackson and Morgan, 1982). With the help of organisational structure, degree of formalization, centralization, and specialization is specified, and rules and procedures for governing the decisions of management and employees are developed. The delegation of authority and responsibility and effective decision making and working relationship management is also based on organisational structure. Organisational structure allows the employer to allocate the responsibility and authority among the workers and help them to execute the rules and regulation. The views of participants on various aspects of organisation structure are presented in Table 5.3 and discussed subsequently.

5.3.1.1 Types of organisational structure, control of roles, and chain of orders in the hospitals

Neely, Adams, and Kennerley (2002) described two identified types of organisational structure, which could be tall or flat; both types having their own way of working (Meehan, 2019). The organisational structure could vary in types and sizes. A business organisation may adopt any type fitting their nature of work. However, for service providing organisations like hospitals, a flat structure is preferable so that patients can be served within shortest possible time and the

employees must not wait longer for receiving orders. Some of the participants mentioned that their hospitals are having tall structure, which is mostly centralized because MS, helped by DMS and AMS, is passing most of the orders (R1B, R4B, R3D, R4D, R6D, R4C; Table 5.3). The organisational hierarchy is mostly tall and very limited authority and power is provided to departments of hospitals wherever decentralization is practised. According to interviewees, organisational structure helps in management to allocate the authority and responsibility in an effective manner, but this chain of orders should be narrowed and delegated to the head of departments. Under such conditions, both structures can be equally effective if well managed. In the opinion of Ashton (2004) and Mullins (2007), each type of organisational structure has its own advantages and disadvantages and it is not wise to take any structure better than others. Thus, it is not possible to declare any structure as good or bad. A few quotes of the interviewees are presented as evidence.

'In big organisations, the extent of formality is more as compared to small organisations where the people prefer to work based on their personal relationships' (R3B).

'There are two kinds of structures: Rigid and Mechanistic. Rigid structures are very difficult to work with, there is less chance of "right to say". Whereas Mechanistic structure is quite reliable. They are much more punctual, and they are much more mechanistic. In mechanistic structure, there is a proper command for everything. The structure we are using is mechanistic. Here is the chain command, everyone knows about his duties; how is he to work' (R1A).

'Because of the structure; everyone gets aware of his responsibilities, his reporting and his type of organisation.' (R3B)

'If the structure of the department is strong enough then the performance will also get improved. If we work according to the division of labor, then every department will have its own head consequently the workers will report their respective heads and the supervision of the workers will become easier in this way, and the moral of the management will be improved.'(R4C)

'Proper organisation and management are necessary because if there is a lack of organisation, no one will be attracted to it. Lack of appropriate organisational structure simply leads to nothing but loss.' (R6C)

As per the existing organisational structure, the hospitals having a centralized structure are ones where all department reports to a centralized authority, the MS. For example, orthopaedic department is answerable to MS. As per the views of interviewees, this is the reason for many problems, due to this centralized structure performance-related issues still exist. For every department to perform as per the organisational objective, decentralized system is needed. Only a limited role and authority should be with the central authority and every department should have the power and authority to make decisions. Within the performance management system, the organisational structure has an important place. Views of a few participants are as under.

'Decentralized and small organisation is beneficial because the problems are solved more easily. Bigger organisation leads the problems to spread quickly. Hence limited organisation is more beneficial' (R2B).

'For sure, the performance of any institution depends on the organisational structure. We have a centralized structure where the chain of orders is limited to the MS and we have found it effective' (R6B).

'There is a need to improve the present organisational structure. As an administrator, it is my thinking that Orthopaedic should be designated as a separate department. The institution mainly is dependent on MS. Orthopaedic dependency should not be in MS control. The Orthopaedic Department should be under the control of a self-equipment power. Secondly, if any employee is not performing well, then the controller should have power to deal with him' (R3A).

'According to me, the small organisation structure is far better than big one because bigger the structure, more complicated the structure will be' (R5B).

Table 5.2: Identified themes and the summary of participants' thoughts regarding the **organisational structure** in the performance of selected hospitals

Identified Themes	The essence of participants' interviews content regarding identified themes in studied hospitals			
	Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City	Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City	Tehsil Hospital Daska	Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial
1. Types of organisational structure, control of roles, and chain of orders in the hospitals	In our hospital, the chain of the ultimate orders is limited to MS, indicating a comparatively longer structure, but certain emergency orders are delegated to immediate seniors (R1B, R4B)	MS is the overall in charge of the hospital and controls the chain of orders, but emergent activities are handled by the next seniors (R3D, R4D, R6D)	There are two kinds of structures: Rigid and Mechanistic. The former is difficult to work with while the Mechanistic structure is quite reliable, MS controls the whole organisation (R1A).	The MS is overall In Charge of the hospital and manages various matters. Although. This reveals a long chain, but a few immediate orders can be issued by the Deputy MS and AMS (R4C).

2. Link of organisation structure to performance of employees and hospitals	An appropriate and small organisation structure surely helps in high performance (R1B, R3B, R5B) A good division of labor and duties into small units favour the successful achievement of assignments (RIB, R4B)	A structural organisation helps in good communication and assigning of tasks (R3D, R4D, R6D). A favourable structure enhances the performance of individuals and patient service quality (R3D, R4D, R6D).	If the organisation structure is favourable, performance will be better (R2A, R3A, R6A). A short chain of orders is preferable over long chain (R1A). There should be no discrimination between employees (R2A, R6A).	A clear structure helps employees to know the objectives of the hospital and their own duties. Better the structure better will be the performance (R4C). The quality of structure is more important than the size of the structure in achieving objectives and targets (R4C).
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Note: CPMS is an abbreviation of Current Performance Management System

5.4.1.2 Link of organisation structure to the performance of employees and hospitals

Organisation structure is highly linked with the performance of hospitals. According to Amaratunga and Baldry (2002), organisational structure holds critical importance in the performance management system. In this way, the role of organisational structure on the performance of the institution and employees is quite critical (Slater et al. 2010). However, only that structure could work well which is aligned with the organisational mission, vision, and strategy. So, the appropriateness of the organisational structure is quite important because the communication and information flow improves with it. When hurdles are managed in a more effective manner, then the performance of workers improve. One of the interviewees has mentioned this:

‘With the appropriate structure, organisational performance improves, and the main reason is that the communication is done in a better manner and for the employees and the organisation.’ (R6B)

This view of the respondent tells that a suitable structure will enable employees to communicate without having any difficulty and problem hence, everything will be done according to the requirements. A rightly designed and managed structure becomes a source of better organisational performance (Haoetal, 2007). The mechanism of improved performance when linked with organisational structure has been elaborated by one of the interviewees:

‘With the appropriate structure, the organisation would be split into smaller departments and people may know what flaws they have and how they have to improve them’ (R5B).

According to interviewees, the desired level of flexibility is dependent on the organisational structure. The study of Mullins (2007) has also found that when there is an appropriate level of flexibility provided by the organisational structure, chain of command becomes stronger, hence everything starts working in a smoother manner. This flexibility is only offered through the decentralized or organic organisational structure. With centralized structure, there are more difficulties in information flow and the gap between top management and lower-level staff continuously increases. Therefore, it could be said that when organisational structure is decentralized, it becomes the reason for improved organisational performance. Hence, it is reasonable to say that there is a strong relationship between organisational structure and performance (Nissen and Powley, 2012). As two interviewees said:

‘Organisational structure is closely interwoven with the performance of an organisation because the organisation structure leads to apex performance eventually’ (R2A).

‘The relationship between organisational structure and organisational performance is very strong. The type of structure you are having; the respective chain of command you will be having accordingly. It outlines the defined patterns and you must follow the directions. In this way, it has a great impact on the performance of the institution.’ (R3A)

The type of organisational structure which has been adopted for any organisation is determinant of the organisational performance (Laursen and Foss, 2003). It is believed by interviewees that decentralized and smaller organisational structures are conducive for the better performance of hospitals as compared to the centralized and large organisational structures. A few of the interviewee also said:

'I believe if the complete system is divided into a number of smaller units with each unit having a controller, then it will be a healthy step for the improvement of the institution as compared to the establishment of the larger structures. More the complicated and larger structure, it would be without division into smaller units, and more will be the complications and difficulties' (R2B).

'If the structure is better, the institution will improve. As every department has its structure, responsibilities, and authority in the decentralized structure, then the supervision would be done accordingly, which can improve the efficiency of the work of institution' (R2C)

The relatedness of a hospital organisation with the performance of employees has been reported in the literature. For example, Todnem (2005) says that with the appropriate organisational structure, the performance of employees could be managed in a more streamlined manner. Aghajani et al. (2013) showed that organisational structure has significant relationship with employees' creativity. Alfes et al. (2013) reported a positive impact of formal structure on performance in a stable setup which enlarges performance's predictability as well. Wilden et al (2013) mentioned that performance in a firm is shaped by the organisational structure. Shields et al. (2015) and Anderson and Eshima (2013) have found that leadership and organisational structure influence efficiency of performance and cause quick completion of procedures willingly by every member. Similarly, some of the interviewees have highlighted that having a better structure will be quite beneficial for performance.

'From my perspective, it is strongly linked with the employee's performance, as a good, the structure will affect directly the performance of an organisation. A good structure can affect the organisation in several ways like easier to delegate responsibility, decision making, and utilizing the resources, and potential of employees' (R5B).

'If the organisation structure is easy and smooth, performance and the development would be easier too' (R1A).

'Better the structure better will be the performance' (R4C).

'The relationship between organisational structure and performance is very strong. This has a great impact on the performance of employees and the institution' (R6A).

'In my opinion, the relationship is there in between the employee performance and the organisation structure. The smaller structure is better because the control is more in this case and the success could be achieved effectively' (R3B).

'From my perspective, organisational structure is linked with the employee's performance, as good the structure will affect directly on the performance of an organisation. A good structure can affect the organisation in several ways like easier to delegate responsibility, decision making, and utilizing the resources' (R5B).

'Organisational structure and performance are having a relationship. If the structure is improved; the performance of institution will be improved, because the workers will know the clear objectives that can play an important role in the efficient performance of institution' (R1C).

Thus, the results of this research indicate that responsibility delegation, decision making, and resource utilization are few fundamental roles of organisational structure affecting the performance of employees and the institution. If there are any problems in the organisational performance, then the appropriate structure should be adopted otherwise it will lead to further problems (Hrebiniak, 2005). The organisational structure is highly important for getting good performance of individuals and overall organisational achievements. The organisational structure can help to achieve targets if it is aligned with the goals and objectives of the organisation and effectively managed to match all needs of employees and management like authority, delegation, communication flow, and information management, and consequently affect the organisational performance.

5.3.2 Training of employees for improvement of skills, capabilities, and performance in the studied hospitals

The performance of employees, especially low performers, have been a big challenge for the managers of almost all organisations. Besides other reasons, an employee may not perform well because of deficiency of required skills and abilities. Therefore, training and mentoring is the first option to mitigate this problem (Table 5.2). A significant impact of different factors on performance of employees was found by Aragón et al (2014), but among the most important factors is training. It is critical for management of every organisation to provide the appropriate training for enhancing skills and capabilities of employees. Imparting of training enables employees to perform better. Training has an important role to perform in hospitals. Employees

are considered for training based on the skill gap. If training and development are provided to address training needs, it contributes significantly to the organisational performance. Though there are few challenges and issues related to training and development, these can be solved by giving due attention and providing needed resources to it. Various aspects of training and development are discussed in the subsequent sections.

5.3.2.1 Impact of deficient skills and training of employees on performance in hospitals

The prime objective of hospitals is to care and cure of patients and providing them a good quality service which matches the standards fixed for this purpose. The patient suffering from any disease, ailment or medical problem will ultimately reach different hospitals, especially poor people will mostly be coming to government hospitals. Therefore, it is direly needed that not only the hospitals should have multivariant facilities but also the employees should be trained and possess capabilities and skills to treat the versatile nature of patients and handle diverse medical activities and operations. In case a hospital is unable to treat a patient due to nature of his disease, he must be referred to another hospital, which is not a good deed for the hospital, but the life of the patient may be endangered, especially when he is already in a serious condition. Thus, deficiency of certain skills, which can be inculcated through training of staff, is directly related to the performance of hospitals (Table 5.2), as two participants of the studied hospitals said:

'If we have well-trained staff then the cases that we needed to refer to other hospitals, there will be no need for these. Obviously, there is a very significant relationship between employee training and organisational performance. If the hospitals have well-trained staff, good quality of work will be there due to which more patients will prefer the hospital' (R1B).

'If a person's performance is not up to mark, then either he is not given a suitable working set up or there is an issue with skill level. So, in case the department is providing Capacity Building Program, then there would be an advantage that the department will grow overall, and resultantly would be capable enough to facilitate the patients'(R1A).

Hersey, Blanchard, and Johnson (2007) have asserted that employees training, and performance are closely linked up. A clear impact of arranging required training for the employees is observed in an increased professional capacity and proving more useful for the

hospitals because rare skills could be imparted which enable him/her to perform multitasks. Thus, the overall spectrum of hospital services increases significantly. Consequently, the satisfaction and confidence of the patients and their relatives enhances a lot, putting the hospital in a specific and unique position, as some of the participants also agreed to it.

'Training provides improvement in work, make the worker performance well, and resultantly, the efficiency of work of the institution will improve the work which helps to achieve the goals'(R4C).

'Of course! The training of employee is important, as they are taking care of human beings. If they are not well trained, they cannot ensure good service quality. Training is the key to success' (R2D).

'Training is beneficial for both: it improves the confidence level of workers, as a result, a good performance can be received for the hospital. It can give an improved image of the department, resultantly the work efficiency improves. If a worker is trained properly on regular basis then we will be able to provide a better image of public hospitals to the people'(R4D).

The examples of some of the programs implemented in the studied hospitals are Medical Educational Development and Difficult Development Program. With these programs, the management keeps on developing computer skills and medical sciences' capacity building of employees. Salas et al., (2012), emphasized that both soft and hard skills of employees must be polished through training. Soft skills are needed to improve the behaviour and attitude of employees and these are mostly related to the aspect that how effectively employees deal with the patients. The hard skills are about the professional qualification and knowledge which is needed by employees for professional medical activities (Carvalho and Rabechini Junior, 2015).

5.3.2.2 Identification of needs and imparting of training

As suggested by Cascio and Aguinis (2005), and pointed out by some of the senior participants, training programs are offered based on the performance appraisal records. The areas and skills identified as deficient in the performance appraisal are used for training of employees. Both hard and soft skills are assessed by supervisors to identify whether there is some need for training in any of the related aspects. This is the senior management which can assess whether employees' current performance is matched with the job requirement or not.

The skill gaps are mostly the basis of deciding the required training for individuals. The skill gap is the difference which exists among actual and desired level of skills in employees (Vukšić, Bach, and Popovič, 2013). Such gap is also translated into the employee's performance over a certain period. When performance of an employee is not up to the standard, it is the skill gap which must be minimized. The work of identifying the skill gap is usually in the hands of supervisors and top management (Table 5.2). After completing the training, the performance review is again conducted to find out the degree to which a certain employee has managed to improve his/her deficient skill and the resultant performance. A few quotes are presented as evidence of the thoughts of the participants.

'It is the responsibility of the senior person to take care of them to inform about their skills and about their other things' (R3D).

'It is observed that what kind of dealing strategy is he having to deal with the patients, and it is also checked that is the worker having professional qualification related to the assigned task' (R5B).

Usually, when the manager or direct supervisor of any employee assess the performance, the weaknesses of employees are also highlighted. During the training, these weak areas can be targeted to improve employees' performance as well as that of the hospital.

Phillips (2012) suggested training need analysis for improving the performance of employees. Such an analysis is being conducted in the studied hospital. Any performance deficiency is discussed with the employee by the supervisor where the root cause of poor performance is explored. If supervisors find that it is the skill gap of the employee due to which he/she could not perform well; appropriate training is recommended. Some of the senior interviewees have explained that they also observe the performance and skills gap in an informal way:

'We can predict the skill gap through skill observation. We carry the observations on their workplace. If any client has visited them, then how much competence do they show? How had they handled the patient? How had they welcomed the patient? Then we observe the skills of workers in their Clinical Areas.' (R3A)

'The seniors observe the workers in their workplace. It is also checked how and what kind of work a worker is doing when he is assigned a duty' (R1C).

‘We observe their work by ourselves. This automatically reveals its performance. For example, we come across a dresser; we see personally whether he dresses properly or not’ (R4A).

If there are proper training and development, there are chances that work will be done using the standard procedures. This research indicated that all hospitals are not able to do this because the training and development department is not common in all hospitals. One interviewee said:

As such proper system of training is not there that can be followed, but when we want to recruit any new employee, we check whether he is eligible to go for the applied post in terms of his qualification, skills, and experience or not. Afterward, only the senior is there to see if the employee is going good or not.’ (R5B)

Table 5.3: Identified themes and the summary of participants’ thoughts regarding the **Training of employees** for improvement of performance in the studied hospitals

Identified Themes	The essence of participants’ interviews content regarding identified themes in studied hospitals			
	Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City	Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City	Tehsil Hospital Daska	Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial
1. Impact of deficient skills and training of employees on performance in hospitals	Certain patients are referred to other hospitals in the absence of appropriately trained and possessing required skills (R1B)	A deficient skill in an employee is depicted as his poor performance in a specified assignment (R2D, R3D, R6D)	Poor or deficient skill is revealed as poor performance if there are no other logical reasons (R1A, R6A).	A deficiency of skill of workers impacts the quality of service provided to the patient (R4C).
2. Identification of needs and imparting of training	Medical Educational Department and Difficult Development Program of the hospital identify the training needs (R4B)	If the poor performance of an employee is due to deficient skill, it reveals the need for training for him (R3D, R6D). A field tour of seniors and weekly meetings (R2D, R4D).	An employee is questioned about his skills at the time of recruitment as well as during performing of duties. These observations indicate their training needs (R1A), through checklists (R2A, R6A). We have a shortage of trained staff (R3A)	The skill deficiencies are identified in field tours by seniors and discussions (R4C).

3. Benefits of the training of employees	Useful for the employee and the hospital in performing assigned duties (R1B, R6B) and ultimately benefitting the patients and improvement of quality and increasing confidence level (R4B, R7B) Training is directly related to the performance of the hospital and helps in treating all patients (R1B, R4B, R7B)	Training increases the confidence level of the employee and enhances his performance potential as well as of the hospital (R2D, R3D, R4D, R6D) The trained staff increases the overall performance of the hospital and service quality for the patients (R3D, R4D, R5D)	The skill level is improved, and the personal and professional grooming of the trainee is achieved (R1A). A skilful worker is demanded everywhere because he boosts the performance (R2A, R3A, R6A). The employees become proficient and skilful and can tackle most of the healthcare cases (R1A, R3A, R6A). Training and performance are highly related (110%) (R2A)	The training pays in terms of better and increased performance of employees (R4C). The performance of the hospital in achieving the target and the provision of quality service to incoming patients are improved a lot (R4C).
4. Challenges faced in the training and development of employees	The hospital does not have any appropriate training system of its own (R1B)	No proper setup and budget are available (R3D, R6D).	The hospital is not developed enough yet to hold frequent and all the required training due to lack of HR personnel (R1A, R2A, R3A).	The hospital does not have any training setup and facilities (R4C).

Note: CPMS is an abbreviation of Current Performance Management System

5.3.2.3 Advantages and Benefits of the training of employees

The purpose of selected training in hospitals is nothing else but to ensure the performance, and personal and professional development of employees (Jackson, Schuler and Werner, 2009). Kunze et al. (2013) argued that those companies that focus on developing good training design in accordance with their requirements, as well as employees' needs, get better outcomes. This training is considered utmost important for the hospitals because through refresher courses, and training programs, employees' skillset is updated with the latest technology through which employees' performance could be improved in a significant manner. The training target that every employee is competent to perform the assigned job in a standard and satisfactory level using the minimum possible resources (Real et al., 2014). The efficiency of work and quality of service to patients is improved. Therefore, a skilful employee is quite important for the hospitals, as highlighted by an individual:

'The work efficiency depends upon the number of skilled staffs. If the skilful trained staff is less in number, the work efficiency falls to 50%, as a result, our orders will not be implemented so our result would be one order staffed.' (R4A)

Thus, it can reasonably be analysed that without having trained staff and training programs, the performance-related objectives cannot be achieved successfully. Moreover, these training and development efforts are eventually helpful for improving the overall organisational performance (Aguinis and Kraiger, 2009). As per majority of responses, both employee and employer can benefit from the training.

'It is obvious that when our well-trained employees will put in their best effort, they will benefit themselves as well as the institution they work in. Trained staff will obviously progress the institution in achieving its goal and if that would help the institutions, obviously the in charge will be happy and the employee gets to have more salary as a payback for his good work for the institution' (R5A).

'There is a strong and firm relationship between employee training and organisational performance. If the employee is well trained, then the organisation will get a good and presentable quality of work from the employee which will improve the organisation's image in the society' (R6C).

'Training benefits both the employees and the hospital. It increases the worker's morale, i.e. self-esteem because his skill will be increased, and as per the hospital, trainers will improve the hospitals' fame as it will have professional trainers and so more patients will go there.' (R6D)

Even though both employers and employees get benefits from the employees' training, one of the interviewees has also mentioned that the benefits obtained by the employers are far greater than the advantages obtained by the employees. The following words were used by the interviewee.

'Actually, I guess that the employer is having more benefit than the employee by the training. The main reason is that the skilled person will be there for the company and the betterment will be determined. On the other hand, the employee is getting benefits, as well as the skills of the person, are being increased which is the best thing to be considered.' (R6B)

The training provided to the employees is a significant determinant of organisational performance (e.g. Salas et al., 2008). When the performance of employees is not up to the specified standard, this means that there are deviations in the actual and desired performance of the hospital as well. So, through the ‘Capacity Building Programs’, the respective employee and the department can support to achieve the organisational objectives. Capacity building refers to the procedure under which skills and abilities are developed and strengthened in a way that organisational objectives could be achieved (Robertson, 2016), eventually leading the whole organisation with the competitive advantage. Like McNamara (2008), the interviewees also believed that without appropriate training of employees, the hospital can face a catastrophic situation. The importance of training is further enhanced when the nature of work is critical; as it is in case of health care organisations. For example, employees’ incompetence and skill gap may result in such situation where patients could suffer remarkably. In the case of hospitals, untrained employees in certain skills might also cause physical damage to the health of patients as well. The aspects which are learned during the training, enable the employees to improve their performance (Shaw et al, 2013). As it was also said by an interviewee:

‘During a training session we guide the worker with the best tools so that he/she may become a useful part of the company, and this is how the workers come with effective performances.’ (R3B)

Moreover, good patient care and quality improvement are also ensured through learning during training. So, when employees are provided with training; they are able to deliver good patient care and quality improvement, eventually leading towards the competitive edge for the hospital (Saks and Burke-Smalley, 2014). The importance of training has been highlighted by interviewees in the following words.

‘We are not having any proper set up for the provision of proper training courses that could help the workers to improve their level of skill. This is one of the major reasons that we are unable to provide proper care to the patient in the public sector.’ (R2D)

‘When we come to the training of our employees, we lack that. We do not have professional trainers to train our employees neither do we get to hold proper training sessions. Hence our employees don’t get the chance to learn new and latest things or practices that may help them in any way unless they try to learn something on their

own. Even though when the employees are new, only a little training is given to them by our seniors just to make sure whether the person is capable of the job or not.’ (R5A)

These quotes are indicative of the fact that training is mandatory for improving the skill level of employees. Only those hospitals become able to have good performance and deliver the services as per organisational objective (Daley, 2012), where employees do get training to enhance their current skill level.

The performance of an employee cannot be separated from the overall achievement of a hospital because the latter is the added-up performance of all the employees. Most interviewees believed that training is highly essential for improving confidence and skill level of workers which will not only prove beneficial for employees but also for organisations. The research study of Tahir et al. (2014) revealed that the role of training is critical for organisational performance. It is believed by interviewees that knowledge increases when training is provided to employees of hospitals. Not only the Orthopaedic Department, but all other departments are equally getting advantages from this, as highlighted by an interviewee in the following words:

‘There is a strong relationship between training and organisational performance. The training of the institution and workers is most important thing to be done. The institution should be aware of the needs of workers who want to do good work. The workers should be known to their full honesty towards their institution and their duties. If both the ends are interrelated honestly then the performance can be improved. Both should respect each other to get a good performance.’ (R4B)

‘Training is beneficial for both the worker and the hospital. It will improve the moral level and confidence of the worker; another major benefit will be for the hospital that more patients will visit the government hospitals.’ (R5B)

So, training is not only beneficial for employees at the individual level but is also critical for whole department and organisation (Guerci and Vinante, 2011). With the trained workforce in a department, better treatment reputation could be developed which is an important parameter and determinant of organisational performance. The employees start performing in a way that there are little chances of errors. Both improved confidence level and enhanced knowledge help employees to improve their performance and this eventually improves the performance of whole organisation. Hence, it can be concluded that training is an important element of the performance management system and performance can be remarkably improved (Alfes et al,

2013). Therefore, if performance must be managed in the most effective manner, then by incorporating required training in the performance management system of all hospitals is required. The participants of present research have suggested that the training implemented in hospitals is highly beneficial for achieving good performance. The training helps in setting standards in the mind of employees how they can improve their performance within these standards. Therefore, whatever work is assigned to them can be done in an effective and efficient manner, if employees are provided with the training and development opportunities as a regular feature. According to one of the interviewees:

'For the training, there should be frequent refresher courses. In this way, the trainees undergo regular counselling. I advise that there should be the 3 or 4-months' refresher courses so that we could also update the skills and knowledge of employees. The paramedical courses should continually be provided. But practically they are not being done. So, the frequent fresh courses for counselling of paramedical staff should be given'(R4A).

Blume et al. (2010), identified certain ways through which training contributes to the organisational performance. When employees have the necessary skills, which are needed for performing their duties, they can do it in a proficient manner. This proficiency of employees will eventually be reflected in the satisfaction of customers and stakeholders. Thus, the improved satisfaction level will become a fundamental resource of competitive advantage for the respective hospital. The training of employees is also needed for updating the skill and knowledge of employees for matching and coping the global changes which are occurring in the medical field (Lin and Wu, 2014) because this is dynamic environment and changes are continually taking place in the external and internal environment of hospitals., Without appropriate skills, employees cannot work in an effective manner. The improper management and implementation results in those organisations or departments where regular training is not imparted. For example, the thoughts of two interviewees in this regard are:

'To me, training has a great influence, 50% better result can be taken from the well - trained paramedical staff. On the contrary, we'll have to suffer downfall in the work efficiency, no properly trained staff means no proper implementation of orders.' (R4A).

'Training provides improvement in work. It will make the worker perform well and the institution to improve the working efficiency and achieving goals' (R4C).

New techniques, machines, and instruments are being introduced on regular basis in medical field as well due to rapid global changes in digital technology. So, there is a dire need to upgrade the skill level of employees as per the new technologies which are being adopted, as the respondents have also mentioned that:

'In medical science, innovations are being carried that introduce modern ways to work. Our institution is facing fewer opportunities for training that is the reason we can't implement the new ways of working in our place. Another reason is that we are unable to provide quality care to the taxpayer in the public sector. So, government will have to pay much attention to the training of Health Care System' (R4D).

'We introduce the new technology, for example, electric beds, if the workers would be trained to face and match new technology, it could become easy for them to perform their job' (R1D).

5.3.2.4 Challenges faced in training and development of employees

Despite the importance and very high contribution of appropriate training in performance and achieving goals, organizing training is associated with so many challenges and problems as well. Phillips (2012) and majority of top management members mentioned the constraints, complaints, and inefficiencies in getting desired results, and the financial and administrative problems during holding courses and training. For example, firstly, there is rarely a separate department or section for organizing various training in majority of hospitals. To conduct training is a long process and it cannot be done without the experts of this field who know how to conduct training, but such experts are not available in most of the hospitals. So, the second problem regarding training in hospitals is that there is no one who could look after training programs. Without training and development section and training experts, it is not possible to fulfil the training objectives in an effective manner. The third challenge is that due to linking of training with the promotion, a competition arises for availing of training as well as favouritism is there to recommend the liked person by seniors.

A motivation for employees, 'they will promotion if they get training' creates an environment for getting training by any means. The important point to be considered to tackle the demand of every employee for more training is that not all training is for all employees. The training should be specified and linked to positions. McNamara (2008) has suggested that management always must consider the constraint of the limited resources and training may be offered to

those employees who are at the critical stage. By this, he means that only priority-based training should be offered for those lacking certain skills which are of utmost importance for organisation. Those who terribly need these skills could be selected for training. Although trained employees are needed for effective implementation of daily work, due to limited constraints, all employees are not trained every time (Somsuk and Laosirihongthong, 2014). Fleck and Kraemer (2014) have also pointed out that sometimes it is not possible to provide training to all employees. Using the available resources, a few can be trained, but a problem arises when suitably trained employees are not available. The frequency of training matters a lot, but the desired frequency is not possible to be delivered due to various constraints (Aguinis and Kraiger, 2011). Luckily, there is an advantage in health care organisations of Pakistan that most staff consist of the doctors and paramedical staff which come to the hospitals after going through rigorous training and exam programs.

The training is a function in all organisations which encounters criticism from employees due to various reasons, especially not giving a chance to everyone. The participants are of the view that the staff suffers from depreciation because of overload of work and shortage of staff due to which they frequently perform extra duties. When there are fewer employees, there remains no chance for participation in any of training programs. The hospitals have already fewer opportunities for career development which go waste. When employees know that they will not get promotion opportunities even after getting training; their inclination and motivation for training remains lower. It is also found that hospitals do not offer training to all employees in the same manner. For being eligible for any training program, it is imperative to have enough experience, As highlighted by an interviewee:

‘Some of the staff members do not fall within the criteria set by government for availing training. According to the policies of the government the people with at least 3-year experience are recommended for training. The new staff is deprived of opportunities while the old staff faces less motivation’ (R3B).

Aguinis and Kraiger (2009) there are also other problems which need to be considered regarding training and development. Jackson, Schuler, and Werner (2009) have mentioned that finding trainers and training institutions is also an important task. This research has also provided evidence from the views of participants who explained that trainers and training institutions are integral components of organizing training, but these are mostly unavailable.

If there are no trainers of training institutions, by whom these sessions could be organized; there are higher chances that training effectiveness will suffer. As in words of an interviewee:

'Definitely, being a developing area, it has deficiencies of a lot of things including proper trainers and unavailability of the required institution' (R2A).

According to Phillips (2012), it is commonly believed that there is no need for proper HR Department and staff in health care organisations. Without this, the training cannot be arranged in an effective manner. Further to this, there is not any alternative management program through which the workloads of those employees who are sent for training could be managed and shared with other employees. Without HR department, these issues cannot be resolved because it is the responsibility of HR department to come up with the solution for such issues. Daniels, Tapscott, and Caston (2011) mentioned that daily workload management needs the attention of management. This can only be done with the help of proper HR management functions, as interviewees mentioned:

'We have lack of HR staff in our organisation and this leads us serious disaster. If we want to train the laboratory staff and would like to send them for training which could not be possible because of lack of staff' (R2A).

'Whenever there is a lecture conducted then it is quite difficult for the staff to be gathered at the same time. Health workers are much engaged in their working places. They need to work for 24 hours, because the number of patients is more there, so it results in a shortage of time. Whenever I need to conduct any training session there is no other problem except this' (R3A).

Chapter Five: Findings and Analysis - Part B

5.3.3 Information technology (IT)

The information technology is a highly important factor that enhances performance of employees and hospitals. According to Strohmeier (2013), it is used for producing and collecting information and hence making the data accessible to everyone in a way that healthcare functions could be facilitated through it. The main crux of using information technology is in making use of information as much as needed (Bawden and Robinson, 2008, Mapoma, 2017). The following three sections examine how information technology is adopted in hospitals and how it is facilitating performance management system (Table 5.4).

5.3.3.1 Adaptation of IT in the studied hospitals and its improvement requirements

The information technology is rendering a great help to adopt and implement the innovative and digital technologies in all field being rapidly developed on the globe, which is direly needed for health care sector as well because it is struggling to protect human health and lives. IT helps a lot to provide health services without any waiting, thus raising the standard and quality of all activities of a hospital. Just one click can show the responsibilities of any employee deputed for a patient, the completed duties, and pending performance. Any senior from technical or administrative department can look all account of cares and cure of any patient and any employee sitting even at a remote place and provide guidance and next orders for the treatments in progress. Mithas, Ramasubbu, and Sambamurthy (2011) said that information and data sharing can be improved in a significant manner with the implementation of information technology. It is especially useful in enhancing communication. However, according to majority of participants, despite a high need for IT in hospitals, it has not been adopted fully in hospitals of Sialkot District (Table 5.4). The opinion of a few interviewees is presented as evidence here.

'Although IT is very important for our institution, presently, we people pass the orders manually that is much time-consuming. However, if same thing would be practised online, then time will not be wasted, management will be easier, and orders can also be given online' (R5C).

'IT is very important because we can search and use all the research work done in the world. Every organisation should have it because of its importance and extended utilization, but we have not implemented in our hospital fully which needs updating' (R2D).

'We were not having the IT intervention in our institution but now we have launched a website that shows the complete details of our institution, where we keep all the information and data related to our staff up to date. Any employee that gives a good performance by the end of the month, he is informed via email and he is nominated as employee of the month on the website. With the advent of IT intervention, the working capacity of people has improved' (R1A).

'Information technology is the main source of the institutions' success. Computers and technology make things work faster and it is a source of easy success of an institute. If we get the latest technology, surely our institution will flourish, and people will prefer our hospital over others' (R1B).

'The computers, the systems, and the integrated processes are there, which are helpful because communication between different departments is made easy. The performance will be increased as the IT makes things easy for the employees if implemented fully' (R3B).

'Till now, IT is not satisfactory in our institution, but if we are provided with computers from reception until clinical room that would be beneficial for the achievement of goals. With IT, working efficiency can be improved, and patients could undergo multidimensional diagnosis services' (R3D).

5.3.3.2 The role of IT in improving the efficiency of work and the resultant better performance

A pivotal role is performed by the information technology in the PMS of almost all organisations in addition to many other activities. Information technology is helpful in achieving organisational targets. The performance of employees becomes efficient and they are greatly facilitated in performing their duties. The success of health caring increases significantly because even the patients get facilities; they can get bookings of doctors and treatments online, rather than standing in ques. They can find all information about hospitals online and select the most appropriate for them. According to the participants, the role of IT in

improving performance of hospitals is highly significant (Table 5.4). A few interviewees highlighted the importance and value of information technology using following words.

'It is like the backbone of our institution. If we are not having latest technology, then our system will not be efficient enough to access the basic data of the patients whom we must deal with. So, undoubtedly IT is going to improve employee's performance' (R5B).

'Information technology is the main source of institutions or any companies' success. Computers and technology make things work faster and it is a source of easy success of the specific institute. If we get latest technology, surely our institution will flourish, and people will prefer our hospital over others' (R5D).

'IT is very important to our institution because the doctor while sitting in his office can check the medical history of the patient online. We can easily order online our requirements and communicate guidelines instead of going physically if we shift our system from manual to online. This can reduce the clerical work 25 times' (R4C).

'Surely, IT has a big role. Employees have become punctual and observing time schedule after the implementation of a Biometric system. IT has made information receiving and gathering quite easy'(R6A).

Further details of roles performed by IT are discussed in the following subsections.

5.3.3.3.1 Improvement of Employees' and Hospitals' Performance by IT

Prajogo and Olhager (2012) suggested that by using the information technology, organisations can certainly improve their performance. The participants' view was also similar because, according to them, in health care organisations IT can help them to access all data about patients. Thus, it becomes remarkably easier for them to deal with the patients and deliver the services in an efficient and effective manner. This ability leads towards improved performance of employees which is eventually beneficial for hospitals' performance and success.

Table 5.4: Identified themes and the summary of participants' thoughts regarding **Information Technology (IT)** adaptation in the performance of selected hospitals

Identified Themes	The essence of participants' interviews content regarding identified themes in studied hospitals			
	Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City	Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City	Tehsil Hospital Daska	Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial
1. Adaptation of IT in the studied hospitals and its improvement requirements	IT has not fully implemented in our hospital and needs improvement (R1B, R4B)	We have only provided with computers, which apparently is not the implementation of IT complete system (R3D)	The hospital has a website and partly using IT, but all our activities are not IT-based yet. We are using Emails frequently (R1A, R2A, R3A, R6A).	Although IT is very important for our institution, presently, we pass the orders manually which is much time consuming and must be practiced online to save time' (R2C, R5C).
2. The role of IT in improving the performance of hospital and efficiency of work	IT can surely improve the performance of employees as well as hospital and provide excellent help (R1B, R3B, R4B, R6B)	IT can play an important role to achieve the goals of our hospital because medical follow up of the patients is possible (R3D, R6D). Everything should be online (R4D)	Surely, IT has a big role. Employees have become punctual and observing time schedule after the implementation of a Biometric system. IT has made information receiving and gathering quite easy (R1A, R6A). Due to IT, the improvement in performance can be doubled (R2A, R3A)	IT can improve work efficiency and a bigger benefit is that we could be able to get improved performance with the little manpower (R5C). The present era is termed as technological era, it is based on information technology which saves the time (R2C).
3. Problems faced in the implementation and running of IT	Deficiencies of investment resources and trained human resources (R1B)	Restricted resources and training in IT (R3D, R4D, R6D)	Strong IT training is required (R1A, R6A), Trained staff is short in number (R3A).	Funds are not available to meet installations of IT and training of staff in the hospital (R1C).

Note: CPMS is an abbreviation of Current Performance Management System

Griffin and Moorhead (2011) deemed that information technology influences performance in a direct manner. Using IT, hospitals have become better able to communicate, share knowledge and hence refine employees' performance and organisation (Bawden and Robinson, 2008). The interviewees think that IT acts as a tool through which performance can be managed. A few years back, some hospitals were not having any expertise in managing its functions through

information technology but recently they have shifted to IT and launched a proper website which is now being used for information sharing and management. Further to this, through the internet, hospitals regularly update their performance which is also shared with all employees. The information sharing on the website of hospitals helps all other employees to work with more dedication to get the status of best employee of the next month.

‘At the website, we keep all the information and data related to our staff up to date. Any employee that gives a good performance by the end of month, he is nominated as employee of the month on the website. Through this illustration, other staff members get informed about the competition. The person who was not nominated tries his best to improve his performance to get next nomination. With the advent of IT intervention, the working capacity of people has improved’ (R1A).

As said by a few other interviewees:

‘Technology has done a lot of help in performance management, for example, if I am seating here and another person is working on the 3rd floor, we can easily and quickly share the data in seconds, and with the help of our established video links, we can gather on the same platform in the whole Punjab or Pakistan. This was impossible before’ (R2B).

‘The present era is termed as the era of technology; it is based on information technology which saves our time. Occasionally, we need to contact some of the workers and if they are somewhere far from us, within the hospital then we are free to contact them either by phone, text message or WhatsApp’ (R3C)

‘I guess that the processes are different, and the overall better treatment is being done as the processes are aligned and different systems are integrated with the use of IT here. Moreover, the integrated systems could be seen with the help of the IT systems in the departments and they are really important’ (R6B).

5.3.3.3.2 Rapid and Effective Communication and saving time and labour

The communication through IT has become such important that IT has been re-designated recently as ICT (Information and Communication Technology). According to Schwalbe (2015) and agreed by interviews in the present research as well, that the communication has been revolutionized by the help of IT. In hospitals, such systems and intranet are used where

employees remain online all the time. If any employee wants to communicate with others, it can be done with a click of few buttons. Therefore communication in between individuals and at the group level has become more effective in organisations through IT. Information Technology has opened so many opportunities for organisations and their employees to benefit from enhanced communication process (Song et. al. 2006). Previously, the communication between different layers of management was quite difficult, but due to IT, continuous communication between all management levels in hospitals has become possible. Further to this, the efficiency and proficiency of few administrative tasks have increased. The interviewees have also mentioned that:

'Whenever the government has to introduce a new system, they call out a conference and we get connected online, saving our precious time' (R4C).

'Now because of the new Biometric System, the workers come on time and leave on time too, in this way the proficiency of the work has improved' (R3A).

'IT can improve work efficiency and a bigger benefit is that we can be able to get improved performance with the little manpower' (R5C).

In the health care industry, time is highly precious and plays a crucial role because if everything is not managed in time and effective manner, serious consequences may appear, eventually. Interviewees have mentioned that using information technology; everything could be managed in time. Paghaleh et al. (2011) also mentioned that the speed and efficiency of the work have been improved with information technology. The pace of work of employees is also improved significantly when appropriate information technology is employed. For example, the Biometric system helps in ensuring the punctuality. There was a time when everything was based on manual system but now everything has improved with the Biometric system. According to Ngai, Chau and Chan (2011), IT is another building block of the PMS in hospitals improving the efficiency of work and made many of tasks less time-consuming. Thus, IT is there to help when there is limited time available. The patient can be attracted if they see that a hospital has quicker and efficient systems. IT has enabled hospitals move to the paperless environment. The interviewees, in the light of their own experience, mentioned that:

'In order to centralize the tests, the required medicine and the dosing, our pharmacist can consult us to bring all the stuff under our consideration as soon as possible.' (R4A)

'Previously we were using a manual system, we needed to enter each data individually but now we have an automatic system where we just insert a single entry and we come across the complete history of that person. Now we are moving towards Queue Management System, initially the patients had to line up in the long queues in order to get the slip but now we are going to install such a system that at which time the patient will enter the hospital he will be able to receive a slip with just a single press of the button.' (R1A)

'If you use IT then everything will work efficiently like record keeping data. If there is a need to get information related to any patient, then everything would be present there' (R2B).

'The computers, the systems, and the integrated processes are there, and they are actually helpful as well as communication in the different departments are being made easy due to that. I will say that the performance will be increased as the IT makes things easy for the employees and it is actually the helping hand and betterment is being seen due to that.' (R26)

'IT is important for our institution. This will make our work more efficient. We will be able to get the record of patients online and patient history will get easy access.' (R2C).

'The improvised version of IT will improve the work efficiency of the workers. If the worker's efficiency improves then they will be able to give good performance and ultimately the institution's performance will improve.' (R5D)

5.3.3.3.3 Easy data handling, Proactivity of hospitals, and Improved Service Quality for the Patients

The implementation of appropriate information technology has made possible to manage external and internal demands in a more appropriate manner and doctors have not to do a massive administrative work manually. Laudon and Laudon (2016) found that the importance of information technology should never be overlooked for performance management in any organisation. Many of respondents in this research has mentioned that IT supports the hospital employees to achieve targets and managing waiting time for the patients.

Now, IT has enabled hospitals to become proactive where actions could be taken in sooner manner. This is also critical for speeding up with daily work activities. For example, the medical tests are speeded up and data maintenance has become quite efficient. The flow of

information is also improved with information technology. The doctors and specialists can refresh and update their knowledge by studying recent research and listening online lectures. A few views of interviewee are as under:

'Information technology is much more important for the institution's performance because every single institution's performance is dependent on the online system. The computerized era has improved the present performance of institution.' (R4B).

'If you are online or working in a computerized established system, then you will be able to get connected to latest medical information, it can be related to the performance and the attendance of the employees. It will be easier for us to attend the online medical lectures that could be held in America or anywhere else in the world' (R2B).

'It can be useful in many aspects. As per IT is concerned then it is beneficial in many ways. We have experienced the biometric attendance system that has been installed by the Punjab government. It helps us to check out the level of punctuality of the workers.' (R1C).

'IT might perform an important role to achieve the goals of institution. Till now implementation of IT is not satisfactory in our hospital. But if we are provided with computers from reception till clinical room that would be beneficial for the achievement of goals' (R4D).

'IT is very important because we can arrange medical follow up of the patients. It has become easy for the paramedical staff to get patient's details on a single click, the worker will have an easy approach to deal with the patient. IT and performance of the institution are in proportionate to each other. The complete system will become online'(R3D).

'IT is very helpful and efficient, but till now our institution is not online. It must be implemented at the Government level so that we could come up with improvements at larger scale' (R4B).

'It has significant importance because it helps to keep the entire data of the hospital, staff, and patients online that makes it easy to access by the doctors. The workers' performance gets better who can complete their work more quickly and efficiently with the help of IT' (R1B).

The overall findings have suggested a strong correlation between IT and organisational performance because many of the tasks have become easier, faster, and convenient now, saving time and labour of employees. The maintaining and checking records of employees and patients need a few clicks. Van Der Aalst, La Rosa, and Santoro (2016) say that data management and information sharing can be improved in a significant pattern with IT support. Stock management, procurement, and distribution of medicines, as well as maintaining balances, have become highly efficient and effective.

5.3.3.3.4 Problems faced in the implementation and running of IT

Despite countless benefits of IT, some problems can sprout during its implementation and utilization like a big capital investment requirement, and specialized training of managers, senior and junior employees, and paramedical staff. Finances and experts are also required to maintain the implemented IT system in hospitals. In the view of the participants from all hospitals; limited financial resources do not allow the installation of IT devices and subsequent training of hospital employees. A few are of the opinions that even provision of computers will work as the starting point of IT implementation in these hospitals. Most of the management of hospitals and their employees have realized that they need to shift to the system where everything is online. From securing patient's files to recording the medicines, everything should be technological oriented. This technology also has implications for HRM, for which HR department should be strengthened and trained properly as a first step. Then, all employees could be trained in using IT. With provision of training, efficiency of employees is also increased. Some of the interviewees have mentioned about problems of the information technology use:

'Deficiencies of investment resources and the trained human resources for IT are there'
(R1B).

'Restricted resources and training in IT are the major problems for IT implementation'
(R3D, R4D, R6D).

'Funds are not available to meet installations of IT and training of staff in the hospital'
(R1C).

'Trained staff is short in number while a strong IT training is required to use it' (R1A, R3A, R6A).

'Time to time there should be the refresher courses of IT for using the computers and other IT devices. Training techniques should vary from worker to worker depending on their duties and the department that had been allotted to them.' (R3C)

Other than training, resources are also needed to ensure that information technology system is working in an efficient manner. To transform the whole system from offline to online system is not without cost implications. Only those hospitals can get maximum benefits from it, which are doing enough investment in developing such system. Although there are numerous performance related advantages of information technology, it needs more system and facilities to have such employees who are efficiently using this.

It is concluded that information technology holds an important place in hospitals and their performance management. It was noticed that performance of employees and organisations improve with the implementation of information technology. The hospitals which have implemented the information technology are reaping the benefits, like improved efficiency and effectiveness, reduced waiting time, better customer satisfaction, improved information flow, and better communication. Though it is not easier to implement it, it is recommended to all hospitals that they should make a start from basic types of information technology.

5.3.4 Employees' commitment and wellbeing:

The employees' commitment is an important factor for the PMS of hospitals. Dolan et al., (2005) reported that commitment of employees is a psychological immersion of an individual that he shows to his organisation by accepting the challenges and makes himself ready to do the needful for the accomplishment of the goals of an organisation. Many of the researchers like Brisco and Claus (2008) and Fugate, et al. (2009) have also considered the commitment as quite necessary for ensuring employees work wholeheartedly regarding the organisational objectives. Armstrong and Baron (2000) have said that another determinant of effective PMS is the employees' commitment level. If an organisation has committed employees, there are more chances that the whole performance management system will remain successful. The views of participants are also like these authors (Table 5.5), which are being discussed in the subsequent sections.

5.3.4.1 The level of employees' commitment and role in achieving goals of hospitals

The managers, Head of Department, and seniors have reported that employees of many hospitals are quite committed towards their work. In terms of commitment, they also work

extra hours for their organisation. Even after doing extra work, they are always available for emergencies where they come to work on only one phone call. This is owing to their commitment to their work and the organisation. Thus, they are satisfied with the commitment level of most of the employees. One interviewee expressed his views as:

'Our people definitely are very much committed to making better performance from dawn to dusk. Rather their hard work has no comparison in foreign countries. Even after uninterruptedly working from 12 to 16 hours, they immediately accept the call in their off-hours too' (R1A).

The commitment of employees motivates them to perform their duties fully and successfully. They readily come to perform extra duties when called on the phone in case of emergency work (Table 5.5). When employees show such a commitment, their performance increases a lot, which consequently contribute to achieving the goals and targets of the hospitals in terms of good and timely quality service for the patients. This is indicated through satisfaction of patients and consequently their increasing number coming to hospital. When managers and seniors admire their employee's work and commitment, the team becomes very strong and enthusiastic and accept the goals to be achieved as a challenge. Good views of the management personnel are presented as ready evidence subsequently.

'The employees' commitment and taking high care of patients is definitely contributing to the achievement of the goals of the hospital' (R3B).

'Of course, the employees intend to work for the organisation with full commitment to help achieving its goals. They work on the task they're assigned very determinedly' (R2B).

'Yes, most of our employees (90%) are devoted and committed and show good performance. However, their good intentions are shaken under unfavourable circumstances like extreme shortage of the staff and very long duties they must perform. Otherwise, most of the employees are work loving' (R3A).

'Yes, in my organisation workers are honestly committed to their duties and work. They don't mind being called after the working hour for help when the organisation is in need. This contributes largely to achieve goals of our hospital'(R1B).

'Everywhere, there are good and bad people. But I believe those people who have the quality to maintain the goodwill are more in number in our institution. The people are more inclined to achieve the targets of the hospital' (R1A).

'A great lot is committed, and they do well to achieve hospitals' goals, but there are some lazy people who are asked again and again to do proper work' (R4B).

'In our institution, workers are much committed, punctual, and they even work hard to perform well to fulfil the objectives of the hospital' (R3D).

'Yes, our workers are quite committed, and they work hard as a team to achieve the goals of an institution' (R4C).

'Yes! They are committed. Their performance judges their loyalty and their commitment too. Their commitment helps in achieve hospital targets' (R7B).

'Yes, employees in our department are very committed towards the organisation and achieving our goals' (R5B).

For enhancing the overall output and quality performance by the employees, high commitment level is needed. The commitment also improves the teamwork which is beneficial for delivering good quality services. There is a role of religious factors as well in the commitment of the organisation. The employees of hospitals understand that their work is considered important as compared to others as they are serving humanity and our religion also emphasizes this. The respondents have mentioned this hadith which is 'the time you spend in hospital with the patient till then you are in the gardens of paradise'. From this it can be examined that owing to religious beliefs, the commitment of employees has increased. It is important to have such employees who are loyal and committed as well (Sharma and Joshi, 2001). Kusic et al. (2009) says that management must be vigilant enough to increase the commitment with low level. The views of selected interviewees are as under.

'Obviously, the commitment of the employee can play significant role in the performance of an organisation. It is very much important to get the commitment of the employee which can increase the performance of employees and overall objectives of an organisation' (R2A).

'If the employees are properly committed at the workplace, then in a good manner they can work like a team which will be very beneficial for an organisation to provide good quality of care to the patients' (RIC).

'Definitely, it is a respectable place. It is hadith that when you come to the hospital for taking care of the patients then it is the best place' (R3C).

'Many workers come here just to pass the time. There are some workers who just loiter here and there in their duty hours' (RIC).

Thus, to conclude this sub-section, it is very clear that the level of commitment to work of the employees is very high, in general with a few exceptions, and the urge to achieve the goals of all hospitals is contributing significantly for meeting the goals.

5.3.4.2 Developing and enhancing employees' commitment

The pivotal role in developing and enhancing employees' commitment is performed by appreciation, good salary package, and associated facilities, rewards and awards, and a sympathetic behaviour of seniors at the time when an employee is facing personal problems and difficulties. For example, Broadbent and Laughlin (2009) mentioned a good salary package in this regard. If a salary package of employees can match needs of all employees, they would work in an effective manner (Hunjra et al, 2010). Other than the salary package, many government awards are also given to employees of hospitals. The hospital also provides effective medical facilities and insurance to their employees. Enough leaves are also provided to all employees. The job security, due to being in public sector organisation, has also enabled them to work with the dedication and commitment. Sometimes, punishments for bad work, as an integral part of PMS of hospitals, enhance the organisational commitment of employees (Interviewees Table 5.5, and the following quotes). This was also confirmed by some of the interviewees. For example, quotes from interviews are:

'The implemented law is in terms of, reward and punishment. As a reward makes a person committed same is done by the punishment. We have reward for the good performance and punishment for the bad work' (RIA).

'Best Employee of the month and the free medical allowance has made the workers do good performance' (RIC).

'I think only the pay package is good, or we go with the nomination of Employee of the month. In this way an employee who is doing well, he is awarded, and other workers get motivated' (R2C).

'Like Punjab government has given good salary packages to the workers of the Health Department and annually the workers can have the rewards based on their performance and this has improved the commitment of employees' (R4C).

'Our Health Minister awards the good performer with a certificate; it improves the work efficiency of a worker.' (R5C)

Gul et al., (2012) opined to conduct informal gatherings for boosting employees' morale and commitment. Lectures to motivate employees for job commitment may also be found useful. Therefore, hospitals should arrange to get together for employees and put in all efforts through motivation for building high morale and enhancing commitment of employees. The peaceful environment is also quite conducive for fuelling the commitment level of employees. The enhanced commitment level is quite effective for improving the organisational performance, which can be caused by increasing overall compensation level of employees through different ways (Dolan, Tzafir, and Baruch, 2005). So those organisations or hospitals which are encountering any problem regarding commitment of employees must look at the compensation mix because the most important and basic motivator for employees is associated with the compensation mix which has been offered to them. If organisations could promote the best possible compensation mix, there will be nothing hampering, and all employees will start working with more dedication and commitment. The present research has found that commitment of employees is also obtained when merit is fostered at organisational level. Majority of employees become more attached and committed to their work when they realize that everything in their organisation is done based on merit. A few views of interviewees are as under:

'The significant thing that we consider in our institution is the merit of the employee that helps to increase their commitment' (R5A).

'Employees are encouraged by having some functions like arranging "Get together meetings". The media and parents are also invited in order to boost them up so that they could be able to do well' (R4B).

'If we need good work, we must treat our employees with kind behaviour because this helps in getting as much work as is fair to salary, we pay them'(R1B).

'They are financially supported, provided medical facilities, they can acquire leaves, and it is accompanied by the healthy salary package that is enough to deal with the basic needs' (R7B).

'So firstly, the workers and institution should be connected loyally, and the job conditions should be employees' friendly, then the workers will surely give a good performance. All employees should be treated alike based on merit and without any biase' (R4D).

'Actually, many things can be included for enhancing the commitment of employees. Here the salary package is needed to be increased and with that, the commitment with the organisation will increase. Moreover, the good working environment is also a good promotor that is needed to be there so that the betterment could be explored' (R3B).

Table 5.5: Identified themes and the summary of participants' thoughts regarding **Employees' commitment** to the performance of selected hospitals

Identified Themes	The essence of participants' interviews content regarding identified themes in studied hospitals			
	Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City	Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City	Tehsil Hospital Daska	Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial
1. The level of employees' commitment and their role in achieving the goals of hospitals	The employees' commitment plays a basic role in fulfilling the targets of the hospital, Sometimes, they work 15-18 hours (R1B, R7B). However, there are some lazy employees who are not committed to work (R3B, R4B)	Employees are mostly committed, punctual, determined, and hard worker (R3D, R4D). The commitment of employees decreases due to the increase in number of patients (R6D).	Employees commitment increases hospital commitment and fortunately, we have a greater number of committed people (R1A, R3A, R6A). People are working 12-16 hours and offering a quality service to patients (R2A)	The employees' commitment greatly helps in achieving the goals of the hospital with their excellent performance (R4C).
2. Developing and enhancing employees' commitment	Acknowledgment of work, good salary package, awards and rewards, and encouragement of	Good salary packages and benefits (R3D). Job conditions should be employees'	The award and reward, as well as punishment system, can increase employment	Appreciation of good work of employees through awarding certificates and

	employees (R1B, R3B, R6B, R7B). Best employee of the month is declared (R4B)	friendly and they should be rewarded for excellent work (R4D, R6D).	commitment (R1A, R2A, R3A, R6A).	monetary rewards (R4C).
3. Reasons for the weakening of employees' commitment	Biased practices and deviations from merit (R1B)	Our financial problems do not permit extending benefits to employees (R3D, R6D)	Our employees are putting in 100% efforts, but the budget problem is always there in government hospitals (R1A, R6A), the lack of professionalism is also there (R2A, R3A),	The behaviour and language of patients, when it is negative, can decrease the level of commitment (R4C).
4. Need for a uniform, modern, IT-based, and online PMS in all hospitals	Yes, it is urgently needed (R1B, R2B, R3B, R4B, R5B, R6B, & R7B)	Such a PMS could improve hospital performance significantly (R2D, R3D, R4D, R6D)	A modern online PMS could be highly useful to achieve targets and providing quality service to the patients (R1A, R2A, R3A, R6A)	A proficient working online PMS is the dire need of the hospital. The operators of that system should also be well trained (R1C, R4C, R5C, R6C)

Note: CPMS is an abbreviation of Current Performance Management System

5.3.4.3 Reasons for the weakening of employees' commitment

The major reasons of reduction in the commitment of employees could be weak financial and mental satisfaction, job security, differential behaviour of seniors and management, too many extra duties, biasedness, patients and their relatives' responses, especially when any patient is not getting relief in his diseases. Abdullah et al. (2007) said that despite having committed employees, performance-related problems are often encountered, and this is mostly due to the shortage of staff. The interviewees also agreed to this point of view as well that commitment and dedication of employees are reduced when they are overburdened due to the shortage of staff. The commitment level reduces because employees do not get enough time for resting and their personal life is disturbed with it. This problem needs to be rectified by removing the staff shortage.

As per the current situation, the major reason through which employees become less dedicated and less committed to their work is the extra burden on medical employees owing to the shortage of staff (Ongori, 2007). Employees do not remain committed in those instances where the workload is higher. Therefore, this is an implication for organisations that if the commitment of employees needs enhancement, job of employees must be complemented with

the appropriate workload which they could take on their shoulders. It was shared by various participants:

'The thing that affects most to their performance in actual practice is the unfavourable circumstances like shortage of the staff' (R4A).

'We have a shortage of staff, so we need to do overworking, resultantly more time is given to hospital and personal lives get disturbed because we are unable to give sufficient time to our families.' (R1C)

'We have a shortage of staff; the government gives short budget to the medical department that becomes the reason for not providing good treatment to the people.' (R5B)

'For example, people's mis-behaviour reduces commitment of employees. Especially, the ladies are fragile, so they don't say anything in response. But the present condition of hospital is better. Now our management has initiated the pass system. The patients are given pass numbers, according to the allotted turns they can visit the doctor. In this way, it becomes easy to manage the things' (R4D).

'The thing that most often affects the performance is to make employees suffer from overburden of work because the human body requires rest too. So, if he is not given proper rest, automatically the performance will suffer. However, it happens because of shortage of staff' (R3A).

Ashar et al., (2013) has found in their research that employee commitment is also based on the training sessions which are organized for employees. The current research has also found that when employees are not provided with the opportunity of training and development, their commitment to the organisation and work reduces. Clear evidence for this argument was being found in a hospital where interviewees mentioned that due to lack of training session, their commitment is lower. Moreover, the goals allotted must be realistic. When employees are assigned such goals, which are challenging enough and seem impossible to be accomplished, there are chances that employees' inclination to work effectively and efficiently will reduce (see quotes of interviewees asunder). Similar findings have also been reported by Mowday, Porter, and Steers (2013) who have concluded that there is a significant role to be performed by realistic and achievable goals in employee commitment.

'We have a much greater number of patients, as a result, the level of commitment decreases in our workers. For having a proper commitment, an institution should have set realistic goals, because if a worker is given 50-70 patients instead of 20-30, how would he remain committed' (R2D).

'If a worker is given 40 patients instead of 10, how would he be committed as his capacity is of only 10. So, till the time workload is not equally divided, it will not be helpful for employees' commitment.' (R5D).

'In my opinion, a lack of professionalism is great misfortune here, which can only be increased through training' (R2A).

'If the worker isn't committed then he will not be able to give a good performance. So, there is a need to focus on the commitment of the employee' (R2C).

5.4 Q3: Need for a uniform, modern, IT-based online PMS in all hospitals

Performance Management System (PMS) is an integral part of all organisations because, without an assessment of the performance of employees, the companies cannot achieve their targets. In case of hospitals, it is of very high importance because human lives are protected here. A precious human life may become at stake if an employee does not complete his duties. Griffin and Moorhead (2011) mentioned that the purpose of implementing PMS is to achieve the goals in a meaningful manner. The participants of this study are also of the view that performance management helps them to achieve their goals.

Despite so much importance of PMS, its modern version has not yet been implemented in the studied hospitals. In two hospitals Annual, Confidential Report is the performance system implemented (R4B, R5B, R7B, R1A, R2A, R3A, and R6A; Table 5.1). In the other two hospitals; Indicator Management System is working since 2013. Kurji, Premani, and Mithani (2016) found in his study that health care system of Pakistan is weak in health policies, development goals, improving human resources and infrastructure, and modernizing systems of services delivery and performance management. The current performance management systems are proving not too much efficient and effective, in the views of interviewees from these hospitals as well. A few quotes are reproduced here.

'There are some workers who don't look for the importance of ACR until and unless they come across the time of promotion or they get to know that they have covered the 5-year span in this job' (R3B).

'No, I have not found the current performance management system effective because we have shortage of staff and comparatively big number of patients to be checked. That's the reason we don't get enough time to focus on it' (R1C).

'The institution is currently facing scarcity of resources like we are unable to get the computers, as soon as we overcome the scarcity, the performance will be improved. So, there is much need to improve the things' (R2B).

Berry, Broadben, and Otley (2005) has mentioned that implementing the performance management system is never without problems and challenges. So, many problems and difficulties have also been observed regarding the CPMS in the studied hospitals, as pointed out by the participants. The first drawback is that some of the employees do not take performance assessment as serious. They only bother about their performance appraisal when there is a time for their promotion about after five years. So, such employees only focus on improving their performance appraisal in the last two years before their promotion. Initially, a remarkable resistance was being observed from employees but with passage of time, everyone took CPMS as part of their routine and became ready to work on the given targets. The introduction of rewards and punishment mechanisms proved further help to make the system acceptable.

Many interviews are of the view that organisational structure of hospitals is long-chained and centered which is not more favourable for the success of CPMS while MS is the final authority for deciding most of the matters, except some emergency orders, which have been delegated to head of departments and other seniors. The absence of HR department in hospitals has been one of the major complaints by the management All HR work is being managed by employees responsible for the administrative task. However, in a good PMS, employees should be managed through formal HR policies and procedures. This is the way through which performance management system could be implemented in an effective manner, as explained by Broadbent and Laughlin (2009), without formal HR department, different entities are held responsible, but they are not clear how the performance management system can be implemented effectively and efficiently. (Table 5.3, quotes of interviewees).

'Initially, we faced problem regarding the counter check, but with the passage of time when we informed employees about the rewards of good performance or best employee on the behalf of Health Secretary and educated them about the monthly monitoring award, they started to accept it and they were ok with it' (R1A).

'I don't think our performance management is helpful and efficient because we don't have a proper HR department, so we can't implement it properly' (R5C).

'Also, we need a proper and organize HR department with skilled and professional worker' (R5C).

'Performance management system is effective but due to lack of staff and no proper instalment of HR department, it is difficult for us to implement' (R4D).

Rapid and effective communication and feedback are the backbone of any PMS and considered efficient for improvement of the system (Buckingham and Goodall, 2015). For timely communication, implementation of IT is a basic requirement, but its full version is missing in hospitals. Some participants are of the view that providing computers and internet is not a real IT, unless all data, orders and objectives, and the information of patients are not online. An effective PMS is one where the feedback provided by supervisor is considered for making improvements within the allowed periods, but sometimes these are ignored. Therefore, appropriate training of employees is an integral part of a PMS. The training should be in professional fields, IT and using PMS. However, many of interviewees complained that hospitals have very limited training due to lack of training department, budget, and shortage of staff. Therefore, missing of required skills proved a great hurdle in showing good performance by employees and effectiveness of the PMS. The shortage of staff and limited training even affects the commitment of employees which reduces due to continuous overtime duties. A few interviewees are having complaint of biasedness as well in respect of recommendations for training, award and rewards, and annual assessment. The evidence from a few quotes of participants is as under.

'We don't have proper training systems and there is no selection based on merit, there is a trend of favouritism that is why we have less trained staff, so we need to refer them to other hospitals' (R5B).

'The difficulties I face; the shortage of employees, I am not independent in my decisions, internal problems of institution, administration, and employees sometimes. The biggest

problem I have is decision making regarding employee that create the problem in the implementation of rules and orders' (R3A).

'If we are provided with internet and computers from reception till clinical room that would be beneficial for the achievement of goals' (R3D).

'It is very important as well as its proper training. We can shift our system from manual to online and it will reduce the clerical work 25 times' (R4C).

'We don't have any training system; therefore, we don't have a very good staff that operate and manage everything professionally. Some people get employed based on references which leads us to poor quality of work' (R1B).

There are still more problems in the current performance management system of hospitals in the public sector. According to Aguinis (2009) and Jackson, Schuler, and Werner (2009), both external and internal factors have created challenges for performance management. For example, in case of late coming or absence of any employee, other employees get extra burden. Due to the shortage of employees, all employees must do more work than their capacity, hence quality of work is reduced. Local and political interference and media influence also affect the working of CPMS. Moynihan (2008) says that media is an important stakeholder for all organisation. If the media highlights smaller issues, the working of the hospital suffers.

There is another problem which is about the behaviour and attitude of customers. Many times, customers do not respect the employees of the hospital and they use foul language with them. Such an attitude, and behaviour of patients and their relatives could become a reason for decreased morale level of employees. The employees' personal problems may also affect efficiency of PMS, hence such problems must be considered and addressed by seniors. Otherwise, the lower level of morale of their employees could never be treated (Armstrong and Baron, 2000).

Further to this, problems like limited and scarce resources are also encountered in this hospital. Many times, the effective performance management system does not prevail in organisations because it does not have enough resources. Taticchi and Balachandran (2008) say that resources are always needed for effective implementation of performance management. it becomes difficult for managers and supervisors as well to focus on performance management system. This problem is equally encountered by all hospitals and the effectiveness of their hospital's

performance management could be improved further if they are provided enough resources. The thoughts of participants in this regard are:

'There are numerous problems that we get to face and there is too much unnecessary political interference, not enough governments help in running all the departments properly and shortage of instruments and technology in order to treat the patients perfectly' (R5A).

'There is no proper security provided to the health staff, and many patients use rough and abusive language that could decrease the moral level of the workers' (R5C).

'We have many difficulties in our organisation. As, in our country, there is a lot of local interference that makes us very much conscious. There is a messy involvement of media. Our media microscopes the tiny issues to get publicity. We have also faced a lot of political interference in our workplace' (R2A).

'Number of issues in our organisation like a lot of political interference, shortage of human resource department and the budget constraint from the Punjab Government in the health department' (R5B).

'We are facing a shortage of staff, so the staff gets overburdened. It gives the shortage of work efficiency and increased rate of absence of staff that is why the quality of work and Patient Care is affected' (R7B).

From this discussion, it can be inferred that there are many problems in the Current PMS; limited financial resources, shortage of staff, lesser chances of training to employees, Implementation of IT with full accessories and component including training. Irresponsibility and negligence of certain employees, loose and biased performance assessment, ignoring merit in some cases, least interest in incorporating the feedback of seniors for improvement of individual performance, weakening of motivation and commitment of employees, personal problems of employees, security, local, political and media influence, and behaviour of patients and their relatives are some further problems. The challenges and issues like poorly designed organisation structure, provision of lesser funds and facilities, poor coordination and communication, lack of expertise and skills, and training and development programs have also been pointed out by earlier researchers from Pakistan (Hassan, Mahmood, and Bukhsh, 2017; Mashhadi et al, 2016). The SWOT Analysis of Arshad, Noordin, and Othman (2017) also indicated similar weaknesses and threats. These problems are needed to be resolved on

prioritized basis if the healthcare system is expected to achieve objectives fully and provide the quality services to the patients.

When the participants were asked if they want globally available online IT-based PMS implemented in their hospital under the situation when they are already of the view that CPMS is not working appropriately and not achieving the goals fully. Their reply was positive unanimously (Table 5.5). Hence, they demanded the implementation of such a PMS as early as possible and the government should provide resources and infrastructure for modern digitized system. Just as evidence, a few quotes are repeated here.

'Yes, a big impact of modern PMS could be there, and our hospital can become a better public health provider. With the more men power, we can properly implement the PMS in our hospital' (R5C).

'I am of the view that a Modern Performance Management system is needed to be implemented in the organisation so that the better performance could be seen and the systems could be streamlined and the better performance of the employees could be examined and integration be increased' (R3B).

'Yes, implementing the best performance management system in our organisation, rather in all the hospitals is highly desired. We will have to select and choose the most committed and dedicated persons, and preparing such a generation that will be sincere, loyal, committed to the profession, and greatly handle this system to increase the performance of our hospital' (R2A).

'We need to invest much in public healthcare sector, for implementing a good PMS, hiring more workers, and training them to become highly skilled and professional' (R4C).

It can be concluded finally that there are many challenges related to CPMS. These challenges are from both external and internal factors. The effectiveness of performance management depends on how effectively these challenges can be coped up. Therefore, hospital management needs to devise proper strategies to deal with significant constraints. Rather, there is a dire need that special financial resources are provided to the healthcare system of Pakistan to implement an online IT-based PMS which is globally available. The personnel relevant to implement in hospitals and running it in these organisations should be provided with strong and appropriate

training. Merit should be implemented in all assessments and provision of facilities to the employees.

5.5 Summary of Results

Following are the major findings of the current study, which have also been presented diagrammatically as well (Figure 5.1):

All the hospitals have designed their own specific performance appraisal systems, which is helping them to manage the performance of employees as well as that of the hospitals.

The performance of individuals and teams could be maximized with an effective PMS as it motivates all related stakeholders to get involved in planning, feedback, and assessment.

It is also examined that employees' behaviour is aligned with organisational performance objectives.

Only those employees get good rating under this system who perform well as per the system needs. When standards of the performance are not fulfilled by employees, appropriate disciplinary and corrective actions are taken to ensure that performance of all employees could be aligned with the organisational objectives of the hospital.

Supervisors observe the performance of the employees and they rate their junior employees' performance on daily basis.

Shifting from manual PMS prevailing from olden times to the Current PMS including computers, internet, and partly IT use has proved quite helpful and partly effective for the studied hospitals because so much paperwork has been reduced and communication through Emails made the working of the system faster.

Of course, a few employees also took the feedback as negative and their reaction has not been positive, as disclosed by managers.

Managers from these hospitals have agreed that the engagement of employees in their work increases the outcomes of the hospitals.

Some employees do not take the performance appraisal serious because the assessment is mostly considered important at the time of promotion to next grade after about five years.

Most of the managers are using the technique of observation for evaluation, but there are chances of biasedness in visual observations.

Some other indicators should be included in the assessment like punctuality, number of absences, overtime performed duties, positive reply on emergency calls, and showing improvement if some feedback is given. Personal observations should not be used as only parameter.

This is a common complaint from MS of all the hospitals that they are provided with limited financial resources and medical sector associated facilities. They are short in staff at almost all the times even when they are facing calamities and emergencies.

There are both internal and external challenges which are encountered in these hospitals. The local, political, and media interference is higher in public sector hospitals which becomes a hurdle in their performance many times.

The appreciation and reward for good work and guidance, mentoring, and lastly the warnings and punishment for poor work are the strategies adopted in these hospitals to manage the performance of employees.

Within the Pakistani culture, it is the punishment option which is practised frequently and working more effectively as compared to other alternatives.

The training is not common in all hospitals because many of the participants complained that their organisation does not have any training department or a specialized mechanism. The management of these hospitals is still struggling to find ways to improve the performance of their employees.

IT has not been fully implemented (just provided with computers and internet) and the staff has not been appropriately trained to use it. Moreover, no mechanism has been introduced to maintain partially IT implemented system.

The organisational structure of studied hospitals is mostly long chained and centralized. The chain of orders rests with the MS and very little has been delegated to Head of Departments, managers, and seniors except for some emergency orders.

Most of the employees are committed towards their work and their managers are satisfied with their motivation and engagement. It is due to their commitment that they show their availability

all the times even after performing their routine duties and they are even ready to work for extra hours as well.

The interviewees are unanimous of the view that a digitized, IT-based and completely online PMS is required for all the hospitals of Pakistan, which will help a lot to fully achieve the targets and can ensure providing a quality service of international standards to the patients. Such a system may facilitate the management and employees for further increasing, improving, and assessment of performance.

Figure 5.1: Diagrammatical presentation of Results of the Current Study

5.6 Chapter Summary:

In this chapter, the current performance management system of four hospitals has been examined considering factors like organisation structure, training, IT, and employees' commitment. It has been observed, through interviews of the present research' participants that the current system is quite important and doing well but needs a lot of changes and modifications associated with the training, and development, counselling, rewards, and punishment components. The very basic role is performed by training and development and organisational structure in the PMS. Almost all the participants agreed that an IT-based online performance system must be adopted in hospitals for very good performance of employees and hospitals, as well as providing an excellent care and treatment service to patients.

Chapter Six: Summary and Conclusions

All the organisations seriously desire to use their human resources, which now are called human capital, to the maximum possible limits. For this purpose, an assessment of the performance of employees is direly needed. A performance management system (PMS) plays its role here. The PMS is known as a framework helping in managing the performance of employees and it includes the policy framework, planning and monitoring, performance agreement, and appraisal outcomes (Bacal, 1999). According to Bratton and Gold (2017), the purpose of performance appraisal is to analyse the potential and capabilities of employees; collecting, assessing, reviewing, and analysing the data about current and past performance of individuals, and ensuring their better future performance.

The major objective of the present study is to evaluate the Current Performance Management System (CPMS) of the public healthcare system of Pakistan, selecting 4 hospitals of Sialkot District as a sample. In total, 25 participants were selected for holding interviews and discussing various aspects. Various categories of employees, seniors, managers, Head of Department, Medical Superintendents and their assistants and deputies participated in this qualitative research study. The thematic analysis was performed, and 21 themes have been identified and discussed under 5 categories; Current Management System (CPMS), Training of employees, Organisation structure, Information Technology (IT), and Commitment of employees. The findings and results are being summarised and concluded subsequently under these five sections.

6.1 Current Management System (CPMS)

This research involved four hospitals for data collecting, assessing, reviewing and analysing the data about the performance of their employees. All the hospitals have designed their own specific performance appraisal systems, which is helping them to manage the performance of employees as well as that of the hospitals.

It has been found in this research that the performance of individuals and teams could be maximized with an effective PMS as it motivates all related stakeholders to get involved in planning, feedback, and assessment. All four hospitals have considered this system as a framework through which they are directing, monitoring and refining the human resource. Although there are certain issues and weaknesses, which has been found in the performance

management system of these hospitals, overall, it has been found that all of them has considered it as an integrated tool which is implemented with the intention to direct, monitor, and refine performance of human resources.

It has been found that Tehsil Hospital Daska has implemented the Annual Confidential Report (ACR) as its performance appraisal since 2013. At the start of each year, the key performance indicators and targets are set and these are discussed with employees. With the agreement of employees, key performance indicators are finalized for the coming period. Performance appraisal has both sections; actual and desired performance. So, on each of the identified KPI, the actual and desired performances are compared. Every employee is provided with certain targets in each period and these acts as the benchmark for employees and in whole performance period, they work on accomplishing these targets. If any deviation from desired performance level is observed, appropriate corrective actions are taken. To appreciate good work, this hospital has associated the good performance with the performance-based awards and compensation where awards like 'Employee of the Month/Year' are offered. Hanies (2004) has mentioned that a good PMS intends to promote and sustain business performance expectations and feedback. This helps to meet the needs and organisational goals and objectives. The seniors help and guide if any deficiency in performance and fulfilling duties are observed. Those employees who do not perform the assigned duties fully are warned and punished if no improvement occurs even after feedback and guidance. The management sets such targets for the employees aligned with organisational performance objectives.

Allama Iqbal Hospital Sialkot has implemented the performance management system like that of Tehsil Hospital Daska, The Annual Confidential Report. All employees working in the hospital are assessed and evaluated on annual basis under this system. This review is not only acting as performance evaluation system, it is also used for identification of training and development needs, including current weaknesses and areas of required improvements. Once these areas are identified, these are further considered for bringing improvements in the behaviour of employees with the help of training sessions. This training help in building competencies required to fulfil the organisational goals and objectives.

It is found that Tehsil Hospital Sambrial has implemented Key Performance Indicators which are set at the start of every performance period. This KPI based performance appraisal system is acting as a framework for controlling and monitoring the performance of all employees. For checking and reviewing the performance of employees, supervisors keep a check on

employees' daily performance and activities, and they assess whether they are performing the work assigned to them or not. Thus, daily performance is observed with due care by the supervisors, which becomes the foundation of the performance appraisal at the end of the period. The performance appraisal system provides an opportunity for correcting the performance and bringing the improvements in the identified areas. The KPIs are used for assessing the performance and if any issue is found, counselling is provided to employees in a way that behaviour improvements could be brought.

In Sardar Begum Hospital Sialkot, the PMS has been implemented with the name of Indicator Management System. Under this system, there are performance indicators which are defined for employees. Meetings are arranged with the senior medical superintendent who indicates all employees what is to be done in a specific period. Every employee is assigned duties as per these indicators in a way that work could be completed in an effective manner. It is supervised and observed whether all employees are performing their duties effectively or not. It is also examined whether employees' behaviour is aligned with organisational performance objectives. Only those employees get good rating under this system who perform well as per the system needs. When standards of the performance are not fulfilled by employees, appropriate disciplinary and corrective actions are taken to ensure that performance of all employees could be aligned with the organisational objectives of the hospital. Supervisors observe the performance of the employees and they rate their junior employees' performance on daily basis.

6.1.1 Advantages and effectiveness of the Current PMS

Shifting from manual PMS prevailing from olden times to the Current PMS including computers, internet, and partly IT use has proved quite helpful and partly effective for the studied hospitals because so much paperwork has been reduced and communication through Emails made the working of the system faster. One of the most important objectives of any performance management system is to align the behaviour, values, and goals of employees with the organisational goals and objectives and all hospitals have become able to realize this benefit with the help of their performance management system implemented there. With the implemented performance management system, these hospitals have identified those areas for their employees which need improvements. Once it is identified which aspect of employees' behaviour needs improvement, these hospitals are in better position to improve organisational performance. The organisational performance can be improved in a better way with the

appropriate performance management system (Ginter et al., 2018). The evidence of improved performance has not only been reported by management, but the number of patients coming to these hospitals has increased significantly, showing their satisfaction from the service being provided to them.

The effectiveness of this system is also proved with the aspect that it is not a stagnant system which only indicates the outcome, but it is a dynamic system which is acting as a tool for learning and development of employees. They have become able to identify their own weak areas. Knowing that they are continually being assessed, their motivation for hard work has increased. Many of the employees take this system positive because they are provided with the feedback to know in a clearer manner that which areas need improvement and how they can become better to contribute to the organisational objectives. Once any weakness is identified, seniors and managers help employees in bringing the performance improvements with the appropriate counselling and training sessions.

Of course, a few employees also took the feedback as negative and their reaction has not been positive, as disclosed by managers. Hence, this can be considered as an implication for the management of hospitals. Therefore, it is needed that manager should ensure that performance management system is implemented in a way that every employee could take it positively. At one hand, rewards are associated with better performance while on the other hand there are punishments which are ordered for the poorer performers. Management of these four hospitals is using verbal warnings for employees who do not perform as per the set standards and criterion. So, with the help of such rewards and punishment-based system, hospitals are in position to improve employee engagement as well, which is most needed for employees' outcomes these days.

Managers from these hospitals have agreed that the engagement of employees in their work increases the outcomes of the hospitals. When employees know that their performance is to be tracked on daily basis and they will be provided with the performance assessment during a period, the employee engagement could enhance and their dedication, and vigour to work will increase. Although, the participants favoured the advantages and effectiveness of the CPMS when compared with the old system before the last decade of the twentieth century, yet they were having so many reservations and complaints, and practically identified some working weaknesses of the CPMS and desired immediate addressing for efficient working of hospitals and providing quality service to the patients.

6.1.2 Challenges and problems of performance management system in studied hospitals

The present research has found that there are many challenges of performance management system implementation in hospitals covered in this research study. A few of these challenges can be tackled by management while others need the attention of the government. The introduced CPMS was initially resisted by some employees. However, introduction of rewards system helped in dealing with the resistance of employees. It has been observed that when employees were given performance-based rewards, they knew that their rewards are now based on their performance appraisal review, they accepted this system. Though this acceptance was slow in the start but now all employees have accepted it.

Some employees do not take the performance appraisal serious because the assessment is mostly considered important at the time of promotion to next grade after about five years. So, they do not consider focussing on it. It is also found that such employees are also there who do not incorporate the feedback of appraisal in their behaviour and activities. For such employees, hospitals are taking strict actions and started the warning and punishments which helped to cope with the situation due to such behaviour of employees.

Another challenging aspect of the performance management system is the parameters and indicators adopted for measurement and observing performance of employees. Most of the managers are using the technique of observation for evaluation, but there are chances of biasedness in visual observations. Therefore, the challenge to measure the performance uniformly and without any personal bias remains unsolved in these hospitals. Though observation method is widely adopted realistically, it is not possible to keep a check on performance of employees all the time. So, there is a limitation which is encountered while measuring the performance. Some hospitals compare the assigned work (number of beds) and the actual work done. This approach is comparatively better but does not solve the problem in total. Some other indicators may be useful; like punctuality, number of absences, overtime performed duties, positive reply on emergency calls, and showing improvement if some feedback is given.

The limited resources have always remained a challenge to manage organisations and this is especially true in hospitals which are mostly dealing with emergency and unseen situations. This is a common complaint from MS of all the hospitals that they are provided with limited financial resources and medical sector associated facilities. They are short in staff at almost all the times even when they are facing calamities and emergencies. They cannot arrange

emergency staff to face such difficulties. Shortage of employees is the issue which has been highlighted by many respondents, so this is one of the most important issues because it has become a root cause of many other problems as well. Without enough human resources, other employees are overburdened and ultimately, their performance is affected as well. Even the commitment of employees is weakened by over duties.

The time limitation is also another concern because when managers and supervisors, who are responsible for evaluating performance, do not have adequate time, the performance could not be managed effectively. The hospitals have the mission to serve the community and take care and cure of patients, therefore, providing quality service is the real performance. The employees and management should always consider it important, as hospitals are not business organisations working for profit.

There are both internal and external challenges which are encountered in these hospitals. The local, political, and media interference is higher in public sector hospitals and which becomes a hurdle in their performance many times. Internal issues are exaggerated by media which reduces the morale of employees. Government is also not providing adequate support in such situations. Due to shortage of resources, staff and external pressure, these hospitals often become unable to perform according to the fixed standards. Thus, quality of service to patients is suffering. All the hospitals do not have formal HR department and many HR related issues become often difficult to deal. As performance management is often handled by HR department and when hospitals do not have separate department of HR, all work must be handled by administrative staff which is not always capable enough to perform this strategic task in an effective manner.

The moral of employees is also not always very high due to the treatment which they get from customers and their relatives. Sometimes, the security of staff is threatened. Though it is out of the scope of the hospital management to do anything about the behaviour of customers, the issue of morale needs to be solved to ensure that overall performance of employees and organisation remains as per the standard.

6.1.3 Managing performance:

Once the performance has been evaluated and assessed, the next most important step is to manage it in a way that improvements could be seen and maintained. All hospitals are working on this aspect and they have implemented a monitoring system to tackle the performance-

related issues. The punishment, training, counselling, and monitoring are widely used for managing the performance of employees. Once any problem in performance of an employee is found, it is corrected with the help of feedback and training. Management of hospitals organise training sessions on weak areas through which the performance could be improved, and employees could become better able to contribute to the organisational goals and objectives. As mentoring has proved an effective tool for performance management, it is found that few hospitals are also using this mechanism with the intention to solve the problem of poor performance. Mentors are assigned to employees in these hospitals and they guide them to work on objectives which have been devised at the start of the performance period.

The experienced employees take the position of mentor and help the junior employees in accomplishing the targets which have been set. Further to this, counselling of employees is also done on regular basis. Those who perform below average are considered for counselling sessions where counsellors arrange face to face meetings with the employees and employees' view is understood that why they are unable to perform as it is required by the organisation. It has been found that these counselling sessions prove effective when both employee and supervisor openly communicate why the performance issues are occurring. Once both parties discuss, appropriate counselling is provided, and performance improvements are expected. If this strategy also does not work, then verbal warnings are considered. Once it is found that training, counselling and mentoring are not working to solve the problems related to poor performance, the next option is punishment which is adopted, considering the employee does not have skills and abilities or he is not ready to perform. Punishment in the form of verbal warnings and explanation is also practiced where employees are formally invited to answer their poor performance during the assigned period. After giving the verbal warnings, replacement of employees is done as it is not acceptable for any organisation to compromise the organisational performance due to few employees who do not want to correct their performance issues. Senior management is responsible for taking the final action about such employees.

Thus, it can be concluded that appreciation and reward for good work and guidance, mentoring, and lastly the warnings and punishment for poor work are the good strategies adopted in these hospitals to manage the performance of employees. Within the Pakistani culture, it is the punishment option which is practised frequently and working more effectively as compared to other alternatives. Therefore, if ever supervisors find out that there is no way out to manage the

performance through other methods, they do not hesitate to opt for punishments which are not very common in other cultures, especially in western countries.

6.1.4 Training and development

The role of training and development is highly important for getting good performance of employees in a performance management system of any organisation and specifically a reality for the hospitals because these are dealing with highly specialized jobs. The training is a path of development and refining skills and professionalism. During performance appraisals, managers of these hospitals are identifying the weak areas and skill gaps and appropriate training are provided to employees to enable them to meet the performance criteria. Once it has been found that performance gap is owing to the lack of certain skills or abilities, training is organized for employees. So, training is helpful for enhancing the employees' efficiency which consequently increases patient's satisfaction as well. The employee-related outcomes of training eventually lead to improve organisational performance.

The training is not common in all hospitals because many of the participants complained that their organisation does not have any training department or a specialized mechanism. The management of these hospitals is still struggling to find ways to improve the performance of their employees. Others who have focus on training are in better position to improve the performance issues. However, other problems associated with training like favouritism during making recommendations for training, motivation, and efficiency of employees, during training, lack of training programs and trainers and sustaining the trained employees in the hospital are highly important to mention for addressing by the concerned stakeholders. The nature of work is quite critical in the hospitals, the training and development function holds greater importance and is an integral component of the system. Hence, management must organize appropriate training and development programs for all employees, especially doctors and nurses.

6.1.5 Information technology

The information technology has an important role to perform in the performance management system of hospitals because it is considered the foundation of the institution and organisational success is dependent on how effectively information technology is incorporated within the service functions to gain maximum benefits. Most importantly, it helps in improving the efficiency and effectiveness of functions and activities due to rapid communication of orders,

subsequent feedback, putting all the data online, and seeing it subsequently with just one click. The paperwork has been reduced significantly. There was a time when the concept of information technology was new for hospitals but now every hospital has realized that they need this for performing all functions in an effective manner. The information technology is helping significantly for information sharing, knowledge updating and sharing, and communication. The managers can examine the work remotely while sitting thousands of kilometres away from the hospital. Through its use, hospitals have become better able to communicate, and hence improving the performance of employees and organisation. The satisfaction of all stakeholders, especially patients have increased as the service delivery time of hospitals has improved with the information technology.

However, two types of problems have been observed; in some of the hospitals. IT has not been fully implemented (just provided with computers and internet) while in others, the staff has not been appropriately trained to use it. Moreover, no mechanism has been introduced to maintain it. The implementation of information technology does need training; hence it is important for management of hospitals that they should introduce appropriate training programs when they implement IT systems. The hospitals which are still working on manual procedures are facing further problems of inefficiency. The management of these hospitals should realize that they can improve their performance with the help of information technology, so complete and appropriate IT systems should be introduced there. A one-time investment in IT will help these organisations to improve their performance for a longer period and their resources will also be saved. The IT system has implications in terms of resources as well, but management and policymakers need to be vigilant for this aspect, as this investment will solve many of the performance-related problems within the hospitals.

6.1.6 Organisational structure

The organisational structure is important for the performance management system. With the organisation structure of a hospital, responsibilities, reporting channels, and communication flow are determined, therefore, this is known as one of the important determinants of performance management. In the view of some participants of this research, both flat and tall organisational structure could exist, and none of structures is better than others. The effectiveness of any organisational structure depends on how effectively it has been managed within an organisation, but others think that small and decentralized structure is better in the context of hospitals due to urgency and emergent nature of orders here. The organisational

structure of studied hospitals is mostly long chained and centralized. The chain of orders rests with the MS and very little has been delegated to Head of Departments, managers, and seniors except for some emergency orders. This has resulted in slowing of processes and lower satisfaction of employees and the patients.

So many problems are occurring in hospitals owing to a centralized structure. It has an implication for management of hospitals that they should observe the needs and smooth running of their hospitals. There must be appropriate authority and power, given to all employees so they do not have to go to the higher authority for taking the important and sometimes emergent decisions. The organisational structure is important to be matched with organisational needs. The performance of hospitals is improved with that structure which is aligned with the mission, goals, and objectives of the organisation. Once appropriate structure is decided, there will be better chances of having smoother communication flow and appropriate level of flexibility. Therefore, present research suggests that responsibility delegation, decision making, and resource utilization are few of aspects which are related with the fundamental role of organisational structure and these have the potential to influence the organisational performance. These must be delegated to lower formations who are dealing with these problems on daily basis. The organisational performance of hospitals could be managed, improved and monitored in a more effective manner with appropriate organisational structure.

6.1.7 Employees' commitment

The effectiveness of the performance management system depends on the extent to which its employees are committed to their work. The results of the study of four hospitals in Pakistan indicated that most of the employees are committed towards their work and their managers are satisfied with their motivation and engagement. It is due to their commitment that they show their availability all the times even after performing their routine duties and they are even ready to work for extra hours as well. Their higher commitment is appreciated with the higher salaries, rewards and associated benefits. Such performance management system is implemented where they get reward owing to their performance level. The employees are also provided with the extra benefits and facilities in these hospitals for enhancing their commitment to their work and organisation. The profession of doctors and nursing is preferred by religion Islam. It has been considered by many of employees of hospitals that they are serving humanity by working in hospital which is taught by their religion as well. This is also one of the reasons that majority of employees in hospitals have higher commitment level.

What needed to be emphasized is that the transparency of the system should be visible to all and the decisions must be taken based on merit for increasing and sustaining the commitment of employees. The deviations from merit, favouritism, and biasedness may loosen the commitment of employees.

The major factor which is unfavourable for commitment of employees is the shortage of staff members. Resultantly, there is increased responsibility of all staff members and which could become a burden if continued for a long time and employees get more work than their capacity. Their commitment level reduces in turn because after all they are human beings having needs of rest, sleep, and doing personal duties. In such situation, there are more chances that performance will become sub-standard. Hence, hospitals should not overburden their employees, if they want to obtain a higher commitment of their employees, which is a determinant of performance.

Another important aspect for enhancing commitment is to provide training and development which is mostly not provided to many of employees in studied hospitals. The lack of training and development opportunities become a source of commitment problems. Likewise, to assign realistic and achievable goals is also important because when goals are not realistic, it becomes a source of reduced commitment in employees. It is of utmost importance for all hospitals to have proper human resource management strategies for dealing with the personal problems of employees for obtaining sustainable commitment. This commitment of employees is also needed for improving the overall organisational performance as well. Therefore, the areas which need attention of hospital management are training and work-life balance. The problem of shortage of staff members also needs to be solved to save employees of extra burden.

6.2 The need for a more efficient and digital PMS

The CPMS implemented in 2013 is working in the hospitals studied in the present research. Most of the participants are of the view that the implemented system is good when compared to the conventional olden system of the last decade of the nineteenth century. It has facilitated the management and employees in so many ways and preferable over the manual system in which a lot of paperwork was required. However, the current system has so many problems in implementation. Many problems still exist like: long-chained centralised organisational structure, least delegation of powers to senior staff and head of departments, comparatively lesser chances of training and development, limited financial resources, shortage of staff in all categories, limited application of ITC, still a lot of manual work, and urgent need of putting all

data and information online using innovative digital devices of the present era. Moreover, lack of appreciation on overwork and high performance, favouritism and likeness/dis-likeness, biased appraisals, delayed promotions and carelessness about the feedback is some further problems occurring during practical operation of the system. The interviewees are unanimous of the view that a digitized, IT-based and completely online PMS is required for all the hospitals of Pakistan, which will help a lot to fully achieve the targets and can ensure providing a quality service of international standards to the patients. Such a system may facilitate the management and employees for further increasing, improving, and assessment of performance. Many of the difficulties and problems may be minimized if not totally removed and higher authorities can check performance, data, and information of any hospital remotely. The patients can register themselves online, book appointments, and check their data online. The government should think of implementing globally available PMS in hospitals.

6.3 Conclusions

1. Three types of PMS: Annual Confidential Report (ACR in Allama Iqbal Hospital, Sialkot City and Tehsil Hospital, Daska), Performance Appraisal System (PAS in Sardar Begum Hospital, Sialkot City), and Indicator System (IS in Tehsil Hospital, Sambrial) have been implemented currently in the public hospitals of Sialkot district.
2. The CPMS (current performance management system) is significantly better than the olden conventional system working about 30 years ago but still many complaints, challenges, deficiencies, and needed improvements have been highlighted by the participants of the present study.
3. The system is useful to assess the performance of employees, but evaluation indicators/parameters must be reformed because there are chances of bias based on personal observation, likeness/unlikeness, and favouritism by supervisors and managers.
4. The management is generally happy by the performance, engagement in duties, and commitment of employees with a few exceptions. A system is working to award/reward good performers and punish low performers if they do not improve even after feedback, guidance, and warning.
5. There are major complaints of the shortage of the staff, medicines, equipment, IT implementation, training system, HR department and financial resources resulting in overburdening and life balance of employees and providing good quality service to patients.

6. Organisation structure, Training of employees, Employees' commitment and wellbeing, IT, and management are major factors affecting performance and efficiency of a PMS. If these factors are effectively tackled, the system may yield high efficiency, better performance, and good reputation of hospitals making these attractive for the patients.
7. Almost all the participants are unanimously of the view that CPMS need very high improvement, rather replacement with an Online fully IT-based PMS which could be fast working, saving time and resources, accessible from anywhere, acceptable to employees and management, and favourable to patients.

6.4 Recommendations and Contribution of the present study:

The results and outcomes of the current study has been used to formulate recommendations as under.

These above narrated recommendations are of relevance to different stakeholders: The Policy makers and executives of health care system of Pakistan, Managers, Head of departments and Team Leaders of hospitals, and the employees working in the system as well as the future researchers. The implementation of the recommendations will help to improve the system. The recommendations and contributions to various recipients/beneficiaries are presented subsequently (Figure 6.1).

- I. The CPMS system is better than the conventional assessment system of nineties of the twentieth century, but still needs improvement. Performance evaluation must be unbiased and based on merit, justice and achievement of assignments.
- II. Some of the supervisors and managers have identified a few parameters and indicators of performance being used for assessment but majorly, these are site observations.
- III. The training and development of employees' skills must be enhanced, and relevant system should be strengthened.
- IV. The system for appreciation, awards, rewards and the punishment (to poor performers and low achievers) need improvement.
- V. The hospitals are facing shortage of resources; especially financial and human resources, medicines, machinery and equipment.

- VI. The shortage of staff is forcing employees for extra duties and emergency calls which is even shaking the commitment of employees. Government entities must consider this issue on priority basis.
- VII. The quality of services provided to patients needs improvement.
- VIII. The current CPMS should be replaced with a modern IT-internet based PMS to make the system efficient, effective, remotely accessible online and serving to communities.
- IX. The external threats, risks, and interferences from media and political influence must be removed by the government.
- X. The hospitals should share their data and information extensively with the future researchers after taking care of security measures but should not hesitate to cooperate with researchers because the outcomes of research benefit to improve performance and management
- XI. The results and outcomes of this study should be considered as basis of further refined research on large scale. The future researchers can conduct similar studies included hospitals from primary sector as well as from other cities and provinces from public sector.

These recommendations are based on the opinions of participants, but also matching major outlines identified from the review of literature.

6.4.1 Contribution to the Literature and Academics

Performance management has remained the centre of attention for researchers from many years and all of them have adopted their own research frameworks, examining the role of few variables. The present study has adopted a holistic view and it has examined how information technology, organisational structure; training, development, and commitment level of employees could be important for performance management. Adopting this holistic perspective of performance management, which has not been examined previously, is useful contribution to the existing literature. There are many research studies which have been conducted about the performance management system, but these studies were conducted in western countries. Arnaboldi, Lapsley, and Steccolini (2015) have highlighted that there is a need for more in-

depth studies about performance management in South Asian and developing countries' context. The present research is based on the evaluation of the performance management in the healthcare system of a developing country i.e. Pakistan. Hence, this research study is a major contribution to the existing body of literature of a developing country where modern and innovative systems are in initial stage. This research study will minimize the contextual gap which existed in the literature for the academics from this part of the world. So, it is a contribution to the literature which will have worth for academicians.

This research has also contributed to the methodological gap for conducting research in Pakistan and other countries with similar conditions. It has been highlighted by Hoque (2014) that many of the studies in the performance management literature are based on quantitative methods where the focus was not on 'how' and 'why' research questions. Many of the authors say that quantitative methods do not have the potential to provide in-depth insight into the research issue. Such methods are not feasible for complex research issues and performance management is a complex research question. This could not be studied well by emphasizing on the quantitative methods (O'Toole Jr and Meier, 2014; Alves, Vieira and Ribeiro, 2017). Therefore, the present study focused on conducting a qualitative method- based research study. With the help of qualitative methods, in-depth insights into the research issues have been obtained. Hence, by working on identified methodological gap, this research has contributed to the existing literature which will be of great significance for future researchers. Ginter, Duncan, and Swayne (2018) have highlighted that health care sector is one of those sectors which is critical for every country and economy but academicians from management science studies have given lesser attention towards this sector. However, the present study considered this important sector for systematic investigations. The results are useful for future planning of the sector to take it into innovative global world. All the stakeholders of the healthcare sector can benefit the outcomes of the study.

6.4.2 Contribution to Practitioners

The present research is focused on four hospitals of public sector where most of the population of the Sialkot District go for treatment of illness. The findings of this study could be considered by managers from health care sector to improve their performance management system. Other than the sample organisations, all health care organisations from Pakistan can learn from findings of this study which will be helpful for devising their strategies. Other than health care sector organisations, managers from other industries and sectors could also get benefit from

findings of the present study. The managers, HR personnel, and other evaluators of employees must consider the reservations of employees, especially biasedness, likeness, and favouritism during assessment as well offering awards and trainings. On the other hand, response of some employees to guidance, feedback, and monitoring is also not appreciable in the view of management. They should improve their performance, consider fulfilling their duties fully and show full commitment to their work. This study is rendering an advice to poor performers for improving their behaviour who should remember that they are serving the humanity, especially patient with more problem and difficulties.

6.4.3 Contribution to Critical decisions by the Government and the Policy Makers:

The deficiencies, challenges, and problems of healthcare sector and CPMS as well complaints of practitioners have been revealed as outcomes of the present study. The major challenges are limited financial and technical resources, shortage of medical and associated staff, provision of lower standard to patients, and the implementation of full version of IT. The employees suffer of overburden of duty hours and sudden calls, poor training facilities, lesser promotions, and unjustified assessment. Hence, there was a unanimous demand of Modern Internet-IT-based PMS to meet these challenges and control the problems. All these facts need consideration and appropriate actions of policymakers and the government entities who can devise better policies by addressing the weaknesses and discrepancies identified in this study. The various reports are consistently highlighting problems. The concerned authorities must understand that they are dealing with humanity facing high problems. They must take some extra care and responsibilities to tackle the problems.

6.4.4 Contribution and recommendations to the Future Researchers:

There are certain limitations of the study which may not allow generalization of the results due to the relatively small sample size. This research has been conducted only in the context of health care sector of Pakistan where four hospitals from Sialkot district has been considered for analysis. The research findings cannot be generalized to the other sectors. So, it is recommended to future researchers that they must conduct similar research studies in different sectors and different hospitals of healthcare sector. For example, they may study private sector hospitals and compare their results with this study which studied the public sector health organisations. They can highlight the differences between public and private health organisations. This research has relied on a small sample size of 25 participants from four hospitals, but future researchers can extend the size and take samples from different provinces

and cities. The use of larger sample size will provide such findings which will have greater level of generalizability.

Figure 6.1: Contributory recommendations of the current study to various stakeholders of the Healthcare Sector of Pakistan

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Appendix A

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

School of Business
and Enterprise
Paisley Campus
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland

Tel 0141 848 3932

Dear Amer Iqbal

Personal details withheld.

Ethics Application Number: B&E90

Title of Study: To investigate the impact of Performance Management System in operation at the Orthopaedic Department of Sialkot Hospitals

The School of Business & Enterprise Ethics Committee has considered your application and we are pleased to inform you that your application has been successful. Therefore approval to conduct the research as outlined in your application has been given.

We wish you well in your DBA research.

Professor Malcolm Foley
Dean of the School

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish charity. Charity number SC002520.

Appendix. B

Consent Form

Title of Project:

“To investigate the performance management system in operation at the orthopaedic department of Sialkot hospital”.

Please initial box:

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated x-x-x for the above study with the relevant information and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
- 3 I understand that my responses will be anonymous, and that confidentiality will be ensured.
- 4 I agree to take part in the above study.

Your signature will certify that you have voluntarily decided to take part in this research study having read and understood the information in the sheet for participants. It will also certify that you have had adequate opportunity to discuss the study with the researcher and that all questions have been answered to your satisfaction.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Contact information:

Date:

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher

Appendix C

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Name of School: School of business and Enterprise

Name of Degree: DBA (Doctor of Business Administration)

Title of Project: **“To investigate the impact of performance management system in operation at the orthopaedic department of Sialkot hospitals”**

I would like to invite you to take part in my research project. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like more information. Take some time to decide whether you want to take part or not. Thank you for reading this.

My Name is Amer Iqbal, I am Postgraduate research student at the University of the West of Scotland. As my Research Project, I have chosen to research the performance management system in the orthopaedic department of Sialkot hospitals, Pakistan. The University of the West of Scotland is supporting me to undertake this project.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

This study focuses on the evaluation of implied performance management system at the orthopaedic department of Sialkot hospitals. The organisational performance criteria should include customer satisfaction and employee morale. In this perspective, employee performance is most relevant to the organisational performance. To gain operational efficiency of the employees, the organisations must think how they hire, train, reward and attitude of their employees. In this way, the employees could be encouraged to be competitive. Performance management system is one of the main organisational strategies to develop and motivate the employees and to increase their performance. Human Resource Management is responsible for setting the standards of performance management by effectively implementing performance management system in the organisations. Performance management system can be defined as, a set of performance measures which are used to quantify the efficiency and effectiveness of actions. There are various researches conducted on the performance management system and its effectiveness in the operations of organisations. Effectiveness is a degree of the customer satisfaction. This definition focuses on the internal and external reasons of operations to achieve objectives. Performance management is a parameter used to quantify the efficiency and effectiveness of undertaken actions.

Many organisations are relying on the employees for competencies and success which enhanced the importance of performance management. Considering this importance, it is highly logical to explore the performance management system in this era. In doing this, organisations need to maintain strategies to identify, encourage, measure, improve, training, and reward the performances of the employees. Performance management system is essential to improve the organisational performance. Performance management system is to ensure employee focus on their work to contribute to organisation's mission.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. I will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which will be given to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agree to take part. At any time, you are free to withdraw from a study without giving a reason.

What will you do in the project?

This study will be relying on qualitative research because nature of this research is qualitative to be conducted. Unstructured interview will be conducted with MS Medical Superintendent, doctors, nurses, managers and HR people of the orthopaedic department of selected hospitals. You will be required to attend one interview session which will cover topics of performance management system. If you agree to be interviewed the researchers will come to your premises or another location of your choice. Each interview will last approximately 30-60 minutes to allow you to ensure that you have not been misrepresented. The interviews will be recorded on a Dictaphone and handwritten, notes will be taken by your consent. In the review of guidelines by the Social Research Association (2003) principles have been taken to ensure respect for privacy, confidentiality and protection of data, honesty and integrity of information and preventing harm and risk to yourself and other participants to taking part. However, if at any time during the process you feel uncomfortable answering a question you can decline to answer it.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen to take part because you have more experience as a frontline staff of the orthopaedic department in the Hospital and thus have the expert knowledge required to answer my questions in terms of how effectively performance management system is working within a department to attain the overall objective of an organization from both employee and management perspective.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

During the research, you will be not exposed to any physical, psychological or legal risk or harm. All information pertaining to you as an individual and your organisation will be anonymised and kept confidential. The data you provide will not compromise your position in the organisation at any point in time. Any quotes will not be associated with the named organization.

What happens to the information in the project?

All information received will be stored securely in either locked or secure cabinets or password protected electronic files. All references to individuals and organisations will be removed or given pseudonyms of data is to be included within the submitted study, unless express permission has been given. All data will be kept safe in University server for at least 5 years for the guideline of the doctorate research which will be password protected and only researcher and supervisor will have access to that server.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data Protection Act 1998. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act 1998. Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in this project, please sign the consent form to confirm this. If you do not wish to be involved, thank you very much for your time. If desired, a feedback report can be sent once the investigation is complete. This investigation was granted ethical by the University ethics committee to accomplish a research project and also permission granted by the MS (Medical Superintendent) of the hospital.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or from whom further information may be sought please contact:

School of Business and Enterprise

Paisley Campus

University of the West of Scotland.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix D

Semi-Structured Interview Questions

Name of Interviewer:

Place of Interview:

Date of the interview:

Performance management system

- 1 What Performance Management system is currently in practice in your organization?
- 2 Do you think performance management system helps people to set and achieve meaningful goals?
- 3 Do you find that Performance Management is effective in your workplace? Why
- 4 How do managers react to implementing performance management system?
- 5 How do you measure the performance of the employees in your organizations?
- 6 How do you tackle with the poor performance in the workplace?
- 7 How is feedback provided on the performance management system? Are employees given feedback from the outcome of their performance to improve further?

Employee's Training

- 8 How does your organization identify skill gaps of employees?
- 9 What are the benefits of employees training to both the employee and the employer?
- 10 In what ways has employees training affected your organization's performance if yes then why?
- 11 Is there any significant relationship between employee training and organizational performance?

Information Technology

- 12 How information technology helps you achieve your organizational targets?
- 13 Is information technology increase the pace of work in your organization?
- 14 How important is the information technology for your organization?
- 15 Is there any significant relationship between information technology and organizational performance?

Organizational Structure

- 16 What you think how organizational structure helps in enhancing performance of employees?
- 17 What you think that small organizational structure helps more to enhance employees' performance or big organizational structure?
- 18 What is the link between organizational structure and employees' performance in your organization?

Employees' commitment

- 19 Do you believe that people are committed to helping an organization to achieve its goals?
- 20 What are the things about the organization that promote commitment?
- 21 Would you regard this organization as a great place to work?

- 22 What do you consider commitment of the employee can play a key role to the performance of an organization?
- 23 What problems do you face within your organization?
- 24 What recommendations do you suggest through which performance management system can improve and give a big contribution to achieve goal of an organization.

Demographic Questions

Designation of the interviewee:

Length of the Service: